

Topic:

A critical investigation into the internal factors that influence the requirements of working capital management (WCM) and its components: a case study of UK small food restaurants.

By:

Fatema Tahura Ponny (Banner Id: B00327072)

Supervised by:

Bronwyn Betts (*Director of Studies*)

A thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

March 2021

Acknowledgements

Alhamdulillah (Praise be to Allah) the Almighty Lord for giving me the opportunity and strength for writing this thesis. I am also thankful to my parents, husband, sisters, and brother-in-law, for their kind support. My mother Minara Begum always prayed to Almighty Allah for my success and encouraged my education throughout my life.

A special thanks and most heartfelt gratitude go to my lead supervisor Dr Bronwyn Betts, for all her guidance, pearls of wisdom and kind support. Her wealth of experience in the field of qualitative analysis helped me to write up mixed method research.

My sincere thanks go to assessor Dr Mizan Rahman and my second supervisor Dr Amare Desta for their prompt feedback and kind guidance. Their responses to my emails are highly appreciated. My further appreciation goes to Dr Sheraz Alam Malik, who was my first supervisor in 2018.

I would like to thank all my lecturers who taught various modules over the first year in 2017. I would also love to thank Katie Green of the doctoral college's international advice team and all the staff of the University of the West of Scotland for their assistance throughout my DBA course.

When I started writing this thesis, my son Hamza was only two months old. The writing of this thesis would not have been possible without the support of my husband. I owe him huge thanks not only for taking care of Hamza, but also for being a wonderful husband.

I therefore dedicate my thesis to my son Ali Hamza Chowdhury and my husband Ali Akbar Chowdhury.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis has not been previously, and will not be, submitted to another university for the award of any other degree either in the UK or in a foreign country.

Finally, I give consent for my thesis, if accepted, to be accessible to outside organizations and researchers, and to be available for photography and inter-library loan.

Personal details withheld.

Signed:

Date:

Fatema Tahura Ponny

B0032707

ABSTRACT

Purpose- This purpose of this study is to critically investigate the internal factors that influence the requirements of working capital management (WCM) of small food restaurants in the UK. A few research studies have investigated WCM in the context of the UK, yet to the researcher's knowledge no research has yet been conducted in relation to the firm's internal factors influencing the requirements of WCM in the sector. Accordingly, investigation of the factors contributing towards working capital investment from the UK perspective is the main motivating factor for this study.

Design/methodology- In this research, an embedded mixed methods approach was followed by combining Likert scale and open-ended questions. Data were collected by following a simple random method from 72 small food restaurants in the UK. The quantitative data from the survey questionnaire were collected from August 2019 to March 2020 in the UK. Based on the literature review, the conceptual framework is developed in chapter three. To achieve the research objectives and the answers to the research questions, hypotheses H₁, H₂, H₃ and H₄ were developed. For quantitative data analysis, this study used Pearson correlation, Spearman's rho and regression analysis and chi-square. The researcher adopted thematic analysis for qualitative data, using NVivo 12 software.

Findings- The first theme revealed that external factors such as inflation, competition and taxation can impact WCM. The second theme identified that employees are another important factor of WCM. Further, the regression analysis indicates management competencies (69.9%), size (19.9%), leverage (6%) and profitability (10.1%) have a positive impact on the requirement of WCM. The integration of qualitative and quantitative findings shows both external factors, and internal factors influences WCM in small restaurants in the UK.

Practical implications- The study suggested a conceptual framework of the internal factors impacting the requirements of WCM. This framework can be used by owner-managers of small restaurants for optimizing the underlying endogenous factors influencing effective WCM and cash flow. These findings could help managers to make strategic decisions and cash forecasts for potential economic uncertainty, and negative impacts may result from both internal and external factors of WCM. Further, results could be used by UK small restaurants to enhance knowledge in WC, most importantly management competencies. This research would be a vital tool for government, business policymakers, trade associations, small business minister, and other interested parties, such as academic practitioners, for advancing theoretical understanding around the WC practice of the small business, workforce planning and monitoring managerial competencies. Additionally, they can plan account strategy with a focus on the opportunities and future threats that may be caused due to Covid-19 pandemic and macroeconomic factors.

Originality/value- This study is unique as no research has yet followed mixed approaches to uncover the underlying endogenous factors effecting the level of WC investment by small food restaurants in the context of the UK. In particular, the resultant conceptual framework contains four firm-level determinants and shows a link with the requirement of WC for small businesses that operate in the restaurant sector.

Key words: working capital management (WCM), small food restaurants, determinants of WCM, inventory, accounts receivable and accounts payable, UK

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements.....	v
Copyright declaration	vi
Abstract	v
Table of contents	vi
List of tables and figures	vv
Tables of tables.....	viii
Tables of figures	x
Chapter 1: Objectives and overview of the research.....	1
1.1. Introduction	1
1.2. Background of the study.....	2
1.3. Problem statement	3
1.4. Rationale of the study	4
1.5. Research aims and objectives	5
1.6. Research question	5
1.7. Contributions of research to knowledge	7
1.8. Outline of the research.....	7
Chapter 2: Literature review:	10
2.1. Introduction	10
2.2. Background and context of the problem.....	10
2.3. Working capital management (WCM).....	11
2.3.1. The concept of working capital (WC)	11
2.3.2. Defining working capital management.....	12
2.3.3. The components of working capital management (WCM).....	13
2.4. Small business and Working Capital Management	16
2.4.1. The requirements of working capital management in small food restaurants.....	18
2.4.2. The requirement of WCM in small food restaurants in the uk business context:.....	20
2.5. Factors effecting working capital management	21
2.5.1. Internal factors effecting wcm	22
2.5.1.1. Management competencies.....	23
2.5.1.2. Business size.....	26
2.5.1.3. Leverage or debt ratio.....	29
2.5.1.4. Profitability	31
2.6. Conclusion.....	33
Chapter 3: Conceptual framework and development of hypotheses.....	34
3.1. Introduction	34
3.2. Conceptual framework.....	37
3.2.1. Hypotheses development	39
3.2.1.1. Development of H ¹ and H ²	39

3.2.1.2. Development of H ³ and H ⁴	40
3.3. Summary and gap in the literature	41
Chapter 4: Research design and methodology	43
4.1. Introduction	43
4.2. Mixed methods as a ‘third methodological movement’	43
4.3. Philosophical underpinnings of the research	44
4.3.1. Positivist and interpretivist paradigms:.....	45
4.3.2. Pragmatism as the research paradigm.....	46
4.4. Research approach.....	47
4.4.1. Deductive and inductive approaches:	47
4.4.2. Justification for choosing mix research approach.....	48
4.5. Research strategy.....	49
4.5.1. Survey strategy	49
4.5.2. Case study.....	49
4.5.3. Justification for embedding case study strategy in the survey strategy:	50
4.6. Research design	51
4.6.1. Quantitative research design.....	51
4.6.2. Qualitative research design:.....	52
4.6.3. Mixed methods research design:.....	53
4.6.4. Justification for choosing embedded mixed design	54
4.7. Method of data collection	55
4.7.1. Pilot study:.....	55
4.7.2. Research population and sampling	55
4.7.2.1. Justification for choosing simple size and random sample.....	56
4.7.2.2. Justification for homogeneous sample characteristics and multinational cultural diversity	57
4.7.3. Data collection techniques	58
4.7.3.1. The design of questionnaires and gathering mixed methods data.....	58
4.8. Mixed data analysis and interpretation:	59
4.8.1. Quantitative data analysis	60
4.8.1.1. Dependent variable and independent variables:.....	60
4.8.1.2. Coding and dummifying variables	61
4.8.2. Qualitative data analysis	62
4.9. Validity, reliability, generalizability, and credibility of mixed data:	62
4.9.1. Reliability, internal validity, external validity, and generalizability:.....	62
4.11 Ethical considerations.....	65
Chapter 5: Quantitative and Qualitative findings	67
5.1. Introduction and background information:	67
5.2. Quantitative results	70
5.2.1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.....	72
5.2.1.1. Descriptive statistics of the findings.....	72

5.2.2. The requirements of wcm in small food restaurants	75
5.2.2.1. The extent of working capital management (wcm)	75
5.2.2.2. Inventory, account receivables and account payables.....	77
5.2.3. The usefulness of wcm	79
5.2.4. The internal factors influence the wcm and its components	81
5.2.4.3. Management competencies.....	86
5.2.4.4. Business size and working capital requireemnt (h ₂)	90
5.2.4.4.1. The size of business and the inventory period (h _{2a})	92
5.2.4.4.2. The size of business and account receivable management (h _{2b})	93
5.2.4.4.3. The size of business and account payables management (h _{2c})	95
5.2.4.5. Leverage and working capital requirement (h ₃)	97
5.2.4.6. Profitability and working capital requirement (h ₄)	103
5.2.4.6.1. Profitability and inventory period (h _{4a}).....	105
5.2.5. Validity, reliability, and normality of measurements	108
5.2.5.1. Validity evidence.....	109
5.2.5.3. Reliability test.....	110
5.2.5.4. Normality test	112
5.2.6. Conclusion.....	114
5.3. Qualitative data analysis and findings:	115
5.3.1. Data collection and demographic findings:	115
5.3.2. Thematic analysis and findings.....	117
5.3.2.3. Theme 1 (external factors).....	119
5.3.2.4. Theme 2: internal factors	122
5.3.3. Conclusion/ summary of the qualitative findings:	126
Chapter 6: Analysis and discussion.....	127
6.1. Introduction	127
6.2.1. Discussion of quantitative findings and answers to research questions.....	128
6.2.1.1. Research question 1	128
6.2.1.1.1. The extent of wcm in small food restaurants	129
6.2.1.1.2. The usefulness of wcm in small food restaurants:	130
6.2.1.2. Research question 2	130
6.2.1.2.1. Management competencies and the requirements of wcm:	131
6.2.1.2.2. The size of business and the requirements of wcm.....	132
6.2.1.2.3. Leverage and the requirements of wcm (h ₃)	135
6.2.1.2.4. The profitability and the requirements of wcm (h ₄).....	138
6.2.1.3. Research question 4	141
6.2.2. Qualitative analysis and discusiion.....	141
6.2.2.1. Research question 3	142
6.2.2.1.1. Theme 1: external factors	142
6.2.2.1.2. Theme 2: internal factors	143

6.2.3. Integration of mixed findings:	145
6.4. Conclusion:.....	146
Chapter 7: Conclusions, limitation and recommendation	147
7.1. Introduction:	147
7.2. Summary of the research	147
7.2.1. Review of research objectives	149
7.2.1.1. Objectives 1	149
7.2.1.2. Objective 2.....	149
7.2.1.3. Objectives 3	150
7.2.2. The summary of research findings.....	150
7.2.3. Conclusion:.....	152
7.3. Contribution of research	153
7.3.2. Methodological implications	153
7.3.3. Practical implications.....	155
7.4. Limitation of the research and challenges:	160
7.5. Opportunities for future research	162
7.6. Critical reflective summary	163
Appendix: A	180
Appendix B.....	181
Appendix C.....	187
Appendix D	198
Appendix E.....	204
Appendix F	206
Participant consent form.....	213

Tables of tables

TABLE 2.1 TYPOLOGY OF DEFINITIONS OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM)	12
TABLE 2.2 METHODS OF MEASURING WCM COMPONENTS	15
TABLE 3.2 SUMMARY OF PREVIOUS EMPIRICAL RESEARCHES	35
TABLE 3.1. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESULTING HYPOTHESES	38
TABLE 5.2.1. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS	73
TABLE 5.2.2 (A) THE EXTENT OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM)	76
TABLE 5.2.2. (B): CHI-SQUARE TEST: THE EXTENT OF WCM IN TERM OF NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	76
TABLE 5.2.2. (C): WCM COMPONENTS: INV, AR AND AP	77
TABLE 5.2.2. (E): THE ONE-WAY ANOVA TEST	79
TABLE 5.2.3: FREQUENCY TABLE OF THE USEFULNESS OF WCM.....	80
TABLE 5.2.4 (A). DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS OF WCM	82

TABLE 5.2.4.(B) THE ANOVA RESULTS- INTERNAL FACTORS BASING ON THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM .	83
TABLE 5.2.4. (C) REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS AND WCM	84
TABLE 5.2.4. (D) ANOVA.....	85
TABLE 5.2.4. (E) CORRELATION BETWEEN INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	85
TABLE 5.2.4.3.(A) CORRELATION ANALYSIS: WCM AND MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES.	87
TABLE 5.2.4.3. (B) REGRESSION ANALYSIS:.....	88
MODEL SUMMARY.....	88
TABLE 5.2.4.3. (C) REGRESSION ANALYSIS ANOVA	88
TABLE 5.2.4.3. (D) REGRESSION ANALYSIS: COEFFICIENTS ^A	88
TABLE 5.2.4.3. (E) CROSSTABULATION STATISTICS.....	89
TABLE 5.2.4.3. (F) CHI-SQUARE	89
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (A): CORRELATION BETWEEN WCM AND BUSINESS SIZE.....	91
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (B) REGRESSION ANALYSIS: MODEL SUMMARY	91
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (C) ANOVA ^A	91
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (C) CROSSTABULATION STATISTICS	93
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (D) CHI-SQUARE TESTS	93
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (E) CROSSTAB: THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNT RECEIVABLES	94
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (F) CHI-SQUARE TESTS.....	94
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (G) CROSSTABULATION STATISTICS	96
TABLE 5.2.4.4. (H) CHI-SQUARE TESTS	96
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (A) LEVERAGE AND THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM:.....	98
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (B) REGRESSION ANALYSIS LEVERAGE AND WCM.....	98
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (C) ANOVA ^A	99
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (D) COEFFICIENTS ^A	99
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (E) FREQUENCY TABLE	99
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (F) CROSSTABULATION STATISTICS.....	100
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (G) CHI-SQUARE TESTS	100
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (H) CROSSTABULATION	101
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (I) CHI-SQUARE TESTS.....	101
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (J) CROSSTABULATION	102
TABLE 5.2.4.5. (K) CHI-SQUARE TESTS	102
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (A) CORRELATION ANALYSIS THE PROFITABILITY AND WC REQUIREMENT	104
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (B) REGRESSION ANALYSIS: PROFITABILITY AND WCM	104
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (C) ANOVA	104
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (E) CROSSTABULATION.....	106
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (F) CHI-SQUARE TESTS	106

TABLE 5.2.4.6. (G) CROSSTABULATION	106
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (H) CHI-SQUARE TESTS.....	107
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (I) CROSSTABULATION.....	107
TABLE 5.2.4.6. (J) CHI-SQUARE TESTS.....	108
TABLE 5.2.5.1. VALIDITY TEST	109
TABLE 5.2.5.2. VALID AND MISSING RESPONSES	110
TABLE 5.2.5.3. CRONBACH ALPHA RELIABILITY COEFFICIENTS	110
TABLE 5.2.5.4 (A). TESTS OF NORMALITY	112
TABLE 5.2.5.4 (B) DESCRIPTIVE STATISTIC (SKEWNESS AND KURTOSIS).....	113
TABLE 5.3.1. (A) OPEN ENDED QUESTIONS	115
TABLE 5.3.1. (B) DEMOGRAPHIC FINDINGS.....	116
TABLE 5.3.2. THEMES AND CODES	119
TABLE 5.3.2. A. THE RESPONSE OF THE FIRST RESPONDENT	120
TABLE 5.3.2. B. THE RESPONSES OF THE RESPONDENTS 14-18.....	120
TABLE 5.3.2.C. THE RESPONSES OF THE RESPONDENTS 4, 8 AND 19.....	121
TABLE 5.3.2. D. RESPONDENTS 2 AND 3	122
TABLE 5.3.2.(E): RESPONDENT 22.....	123
TABLE 5.3.2. F: RESPONDENTS 23 AND 24.....	124
TABLE 5.3.2. G. RESPONDENTS 20, 21, 25-18.....	124

Tables of figures

FIGURE 1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY	8
FIGURE 2.1 THE THREE STAGES OF WORKING CAPITAL CYCLE IN SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS.....	16
FIGURE 3.1 DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	61
FIGURE 3.2 INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL VALIDITY; SOURCE: PATINO AND FERREIRA (2018).....	63
FIGURE 5.1 THE STRUCTURE OF FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS	69
FIGURE 5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF THE QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS	71
FIGURE 5.2.2 PIE CHARTS.....	74
FIGURE 5.2.3: THE REQUIREMENT OF WC COMPONENTS IN THE SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS ..	78
FIGURE: 5.2.4. THE BAR CHARTS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS OF WCM IN SMALL RESTAURANT.....	82
FIGURE 5.3.2. THEMES AND NODES (CODES) AS IMPLEMENTED IN NVIVO 12:.....	118
FIGURE 6.1: THE STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION	148
FIGURE 7.2 SUMMARY OF ENTIRE RESEARCH IN A DIAGRAM	165

CHAPTER 1

OBJECTIVES AND OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Regarding literature on working capital management (WCM) in general and on the small businesses and context, it has been identified that 5.7 million small businesses (accounting for over 99% of all businesses) are the backbone of the UK economy (UK Government, 2018). Small businesses are disproportionately affected by late payment. Nearly a quarter of UK businesses reported that late payments are a threat to their survival (UK Government, 2018). Small businesses generally depend on external finance. Because of their size, small restaurants pay higher interest rates to compensate lenders for taking on higher risk than larger size businesses. According to the Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS, 2018), impacts of late and lengthy payment practices can affect small businesses negatively. Small Business Minister Kelly Tolhurst unveiled the problem of late payments to small businesses by large size businesses (UK Government, 2018). Large businesses abuse their positions in the market by exerting control over small businesses in their supply chain. According to this survey, in recent years the government has taken steps to tackle the problem of late payment through the Payment Practices Reporting Regulations (BEIS, 2018). However, the level of late payment owed to small businesses remains too high. Enow and Kamala (2016) identified that small businesses had a lower bargaining power in term of credit purchasing with suppliers and large businesses. The main causes of late payment reported by small businesses are insufficient cashflows (BEIS, 2018). An effective WCM system helps UK small business to avoid the need for expensive external finance as WC is an internal source of finance. Small restaurant businesses do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively (Mun and Jang, 2015). Therefore, investigation of the internal factors affecting the WC investment of small food restaurants from the UK perspective is the main motivating purpose of this study.

In addition, this study developed a conceptual framework of WCM for small food restaurants. An embedded mixed methods approach was adopted, to enable deep understanding of the problem. Data were collected from 72 small food restaurants through close-ended and open-ended questions from August 2019 to February 2020 in the UK. The purpose of the mixed approach was to provide wider explanation of the internal factors affecting WCM and to contribute towards the generalisation of conclusions. Simple random sampling was used to

collect reliable information for the study. This chapter starts with a general overview of the research purpose and background information on the research problem, followed by the rationale and significance of the study, research aim, objectives, and research questions. Additionally, this chapter provides an outline of the research structure.

1.2. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Small businesses are crucial both in the universal sense and in terms of their contributions to the economy of both developing (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Sadik, 2017; Jiang et al., 2018) and developed (Hillary, 2017) countries. Small businesses account for 99% of the 3.7 million businesses and 38% of total GDP in the UK (Hillary, 2017). A survey by the Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS, 2016) identified that small businesses with between 10 and 49 employees contributed 34% (870,000 jobs) in the UK. A developed country with a good infrastructure such as the UK with its large and stable financial system should be ideal for small businesses operating in the country. However, the UK economy is highly dependent on the banking sectors. According to British Business Bank (BBB), bank lending remains the single largest form of external finance for small businesses (BBB, 2020). As a result, a sudden global financial meltdown may simply devastate the UK economy (Fethi and Katircioglu, 2015). For example, in 2008 when the UK economy entered recession, external finance became more difficult for businesses. Small businesses suffered mostly as the demand for external finance increased (Cowling et al., 2012). According to a small business survey report by the Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS) (2016), small businesses are more likely to seek external finance for working capital or cash flow purposes rather than investment purposes (BEIS, 2016). Therefore, small businesses mostly rely on external finance to manage their working capital.

Furthermore, recently many UK small businesses have been negatively affected by Covid-19 because of supply disruption, lack of demand by customers and economic uncertainty (Insider, 2020). According to the National Institute of Economic and Social Research (NIESR), despite the roll-out of vaccines, UK inflation rates are predicted to rise 2% in the latter half of 2021, closer to the Bank of England's target. Such escalations in the inflation rate normally forces the Bank of England to increase the interest rate of borrowing, which eventually affects the ability of small businesses to borrow cash. Even if a negative external factor, for example, inflation rates influence the borrowing ability of a small business. With healthy WC small

businesses can tackle uncertain economic changes for the coming years. Consequently, protecting cash flow is a key concern for small businesses. Afrifa (2016) stated that effective management of working capital helps UK small businesses to avoid the need for expensive external finance. In addition, the capital structure of the small-size business is different than large-size businesses because of their sizes. Therefore, management of working capital is important to small businesses (Jiang et al., 2018). To keep WC at optimal level (Howorth and Westhead, 2003) there are many internal factors (Azami and Tabar, 2016; Muhammad and Manoori, 2012) that need to be considered and balanced. The next chapter critically reviews the concept of WCM and investigates internal factors that influence the requirements of WCM in small UK businesses. The main research problem is identified and discussed in the next section.

1.3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Small business is growing rapidly in the UK (Hillary, 2017). Rapid growth of these businesses creates financial challenges such as increased instances of late payment (Paul and Boden, 2011; Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, 2018), and difficulty with access to both short-term finance (Cowling et al., 2012) and long-term loan finance (Wapshott and Mallett, 2018; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014). Late payment is a common problem in the UK. Despite numerous legislative approaches, small businesses do not have a standard credit policy (Paul and Boden, 2011). According to a survey by the Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS, 2018), in recent years the UK government has taken steps to tackle the problem of late payment through the Payment Practices Reporting Regulations. Despite this, the problem of late payment to small businesses remains a threat to their survival (UK Government, 2018). Small businesses offer credit terms to their customer to be competitive in the market. Late payers are responsible for the excessive outstanding receivables which may lead to bad debts (Salek, 2005; BEIS, 2018). Compared to larger-size businesses, the failure rate of small businesses is very high (Jiang et al., 2018). Consequently, small businesses pay higher interest to lenders to compensate for the higher uncertainty. Referring to working capital (WC), Afrifa (2016) argued that effective management of working capital should help UK small businesses to avoid the need for expensive external finance. Therefore, it is important to successfully manage assets and liabilities, most importantly the components of working capital.

Research in the aforesaid area, if thoroughly examined, will disclose the internal factors that influence the WC requirement of small food restaurants in the UK. A few studies have investigated the WCM of small UK businesses (Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016). However, detailed study on internal factors that specifically focuses on the requirements of WCM in UK small food restaurants is still lacking. Due to the literature gap regarding WCM of small food restaurants, this study intends to examine the aforesaid area in the UK context. The research question arises from the above discussions on problem statement and articulates the rationale for this study.

1.4. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

This section rationalizes the need for conducting the study. Regarding thought and literature on WCM, it has been identified that internal factors affect the WC requirements of businesses (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Louw and Hall, 2016; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Muhammad and Manoori, 2012). Internal factors such as size, the nature of business, management competencies, cash flow, leverage and profitability are some of the important determinants of WCM. However, opinion as to the relationship between WC requirements and variable factors has been divided. As a result, mixed results have been identified based on whether there is a positive or negative correlation between the factors and the requirements of WCM. In addition, there is no common pattern in relation to WCM for at least two of the countries (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014) as they have different economies and financial markets (Fethi and Katircioglu, 2015). Even multinational small businesses operating in the same country may have cultural diversity which may impact the capital structure of their businesses (Frijns et al., 2017). Therefore, the underlying basis for this study is investigating whether the above internal factors might have a different impact on small businesses in the context of the UK.

A few studies have examined WCM in the context of the UK (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017). However, no research has yet been conducted in relation to internal factors determining the requirements of WCM in small businesses, most importantly small food restaurants. The critical evaluation of the existing literatures justifies the significance and novelty of this study. Therefore, evaluation of the internal factors that contribute towards WC investment from the UK perspective is one of the motivating factors for this study. The disclosure of this knowledge gap is the focus of this study.

1.5. RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The primary aim of this research is to evaluate the internal factors that influence the requirements of working capital management (WCM) and its components in small restaurant businesses in the UK. Furthermore, this study developed a framework of WCM strategy that identifies the endogenous factors affecting the requirements of WCM and its components in small businesses that operate in restaurant sectors. To achieve this purpose, the following objectives which relate to WCM were identified.

Objectives:

1. To critically review the concept of working capital management (WCM).
2. To evaluate the underlying internal factors influencing the working capital requirements of small food restaurants.
3. To develop a conceptual framework of the determinant's factors and the requirements of WCM for small food restaurants.

1.6. RESEARCH QUESTION

The purpose of the research is to identify the answer to the following research question through the application of appropriate methods.

Research question

What are the determinants of working capital management (WCM) practices of small food restaurants in the UK and how can a conceptual framework of the determinant's factors and the requirements of WCM be developed to enhance the financial performance of small food restaurants in the UK?

To find the appropriate answers to the above research question, the following sub-questions are identified.

(i) Why is WCM important for small food restaurants?

Critical review of the concept of WCM and literature on the extent of WCM in small businesses suggests that working capital management is crucial for a small restaurant (Mun and Jang, 2015; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016; Zariyawati et al., 2017; Louw et al., 2019). To achieve the research objective and answer to this question, this study analyses the extent of WCM and its usefulness based on the existing literature.

(ii) What internal factors influence WCM in small food restaurants?

Existing literature suggests that WCM is dependent on various internal factors (Oseifuah, 2016; Atseye et al., 2015; Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013). Internal factors such as a firm's size (Azeem and Marsap, 2015), leverage (Azami and Tabar, 2016), profitability (Atseye et al., 2015) and managerial competencies (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Orobia et al., 2016; Afrifa, 2013) affect the requirements of WCM in small businesses. Therefore, it is important to identify the relationship between different internal factors determining WCM and the requirements of WCM in small restaurant businesses. Therefore, to achieve the second objective and answer this question, the following hypotheses have been developed to evaluate whether there is a negative or positive relation between different variables.

The main hypotheses to be tested are:

H₁: Management competencies are positively with related the requirement of WCM in the small food restaurants.

H₂: The size of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants.

H₃: The leverage of the business is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

H₄: The profitability of small food restaurants has a positive impact on the requirements of WCM.

(iii) How do the internal factors influence the components of WCM in small food restaurants in the UK?

To answer this question, the researcher developed four open-ended questions to explore people's concerns in response to question (ii). The following open-ended questions are organized according to the above research question (iii).

C1: Indicate the internal factor(s) (if any) that you encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned above.

C2: How do any of the factor/factors identified in C1 affect the inventory in your restaurant?

C3: How do any of the factor/factors identified in C1 affect the receivables in your restaurant?

C4: How do any of the factor/factors identified in C1 effect the payables in your restaurant?

(iv) How can a framework of the determinant's factors be developed to enhance the financial performance of small food restaurants in the UK?

The literature on internal factors such as management competencies, size of business, leverage and profitability; the arguments based on these four internal factors; the requirements of WCM in small businesses; and the main hypotheses of this research suggest a conceptual framework

for this study. The main aim of the conceptual framework is the determination of internal factors affecting WCM in small food restaurants in the UK.

1.7. CONTRIBUTIONS OF RESEARCH TO KNOWLEDGE

Anticipated outcomes of the research will help with development of models and will suggest strategies to small businesses for their working capital management. The critical review of the concept of working capital management and the requirements of WCM in small businesses will make a significant contribution to the existing body of knowledge. Additionally, based on existing literature on the requirements of WCM and the main hypotheses, this study develops a conceptual framework. This framework can be used by owner-managers of small food restaurants for optimizing the internal factors influencing effective WCM and cash flow.

1.8. OUTLINE OF THE RESEARCH

This research is divided into seven main chapters. Figure 1.1 below outlines the structure of the thesis. The first chapter is the introduction chapter which focuses on background context of the study, statement of the research problem, rationale of the study, research objectives, contribution, and overview of the research. Chapter two demonstrates the literature review that underpins the research regarding the concept of WCM, the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants, and factors affecting WCM of small businesses. The purpose of this chapter is to address the first objectives of the research. Chapter three includes a conceptual framework of the relationship between determinant factors and the requirements of WCM and the hypotheses emanating from the literature review.

Chapter four contains an in-depth overview of the methodology used for the research. The key research methods discussed in this chapter are philosophical underpinnings of the research, research paradigms, embedded mixed research approaches, research strategy, mixed methods research design and data collection techniques. All aspects of the research methodology are reviewed and justification for choosing mixed method analysis is also extensively discussed in this chapter. This study separated findings and analysis into two discrete chapters. Chapter five presents a comprehensive explanation of the findings. Findings are divided into two main sections: quantitative results and qualitative results. Quantitative data analysis covers the demographic characteristics of the respondents, the extent of WCM, components of WCM, the usefulness of WCM, and internal factors of WCM (management competencies, size, leverage, and profitability). Key highlights in this section include analysis of the research hypotheses by

using descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression. Qualitative data analysis includes thematic analysis of the open-ended answers for an in-depth understanding of the internal factors of WCM and implications for action. Chapter six covers an extensive discussion of the research findings and answers to the research questions. This chapter is divided into two main sections: discussion of quantitative findings and discussion of qualitative findings. In this chapter, the results from quantitative and qualitative analysis are combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem. Chapters five and six address the second objective of the research. Finally, Chapter seven contains the review of research objectives and the contribution of the research findings. Further, this chapter provides a summary of the entire research, limitations of the research and recommendations for future research. The following flowchart outlines the structure of the entire research study.

Figure 1.1 **Structure of the study**

The next chapter reviews literature that underpins the research. The purpose of chapter two is to address the first and third objectives of the research.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW: THE DETERMINANTS OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM) PRACTICES

2.1. INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter introduced the research and focused on background context of the study, problem statement, research objectives and synopsis of the research in a snapshot. This chapter aims to identify and critique appropriate areas of the determinant's factors of the WCM based on the existing literature in the field. The review of the literature enabled the researcher to identify a knowledge gap in the existing literature of WCM requirements in small food restaurants. As mentioned in the previous chapter, this knowledge gap provides a rationale for this study.

2.2. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT OF THE PROBLEM

The management of working capital (WC) is not only a complex concept (Preve and Allende, 2010) but also one of the most challenging issues (Eya, 2016) for financial managers. Adekunle and Sunday (2015) stated that small firms will not be able to generate additional profits with excess working capital which is tied up unnecessarily in the form of idle funds. Meanwhile, a small business with insufficient WC might struggle to pay short-term liabilities on time and is accordingly unable to maintain good credit terms with suppliers and banks. Hence, managers of small businesses need to keep WC at an optimal level (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014). However, maintaining an optimal working capital level is a complicated task as there are many external (Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013) and internal factors (Azami and Tabar, 2016; Muhammad and Manoori, 2012) that need to be considered and balanced.

Referring to the management of working capital, existing literature suggests that WCM is dependent on various external and internal factors (Orobia et al., 2016; Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014). Existing studies are mostly based on the context of developing countries. This study investigates the internal factors determining the WC requirements of small food restaurants in the context of the UK, given that the UK is a developed country which has a well-established economy as well as financial markets and banks (Fethi and Katircioglu, 2015). Therefore, in this sense the present research differs from the existing research. The next section critically analyses the concept of WCM in relation to small businesses.

2.3. WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM)

One of the objectives of this study is to demonstrate the concept of working capital management and the implications of its practices in UK small businesses. Therefore, the focal point of this section is understanding the concept of working capital management, working capital cycle (WCC) and the three main components of WCM: inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable.

2.3.1. THE CONCEPT OF WORKING CAPITAL (WC)

Regarding the concept of working capital, Garg (2015) said WC is the part of business capital which is required to finance short-term business requirements. Cash invested in current assets is being continuously converted into cash profits, and in turn this cash is used in exchange for other current assets. According to Preve and Allende (2010), the traditional definition of working capital is the amount of cash available to maintain the requirements of current liabilities. Boopathi and Leeson (2016) defined working capital as the surplus of current assets over current liabilities. Referring to the concept of working capital, Khan and Jain (2007) argued that there are two concepts of working capital (WC), namely gross WC and net WC. Gross WC means the total current assets of a business, whereas net WC is the difference between current assets and current liabilities. In this research, it is the net concept of working capital (NWC) that has been discussed.

*Working capital is generally calculated as: working capital
= current assets - current liabilities.*

From the above discussions on WC, it can be concluded that WC is simply calculated by deducting current liabilities from current assets. However, Preve and Allende (2010) argued that WC is a complex concept. This straightforward formula may not be useful in real-life conditions, as the deeper understanding of WC is necessary for financial practitioners. In addition, Boopathi and Leeson (2016) emphasized that understanding the meaning of current assets and current liabilities is necessary for in-depth knowledge of the effective management of working capital. Further, Garg (2015) said that a current assets value is available on the assets side of the balanced sheet. Whereas, current liabilities can be found on the liability side of the balanced sheet. These liabilities must be met within one year. Current assets include receivables, inventories, work in progress, and cash and so on. Whereas, current liabilities include bank overdrafts, creditors, short-term loans, and accounts payable, etc. Deeper analysis

of WC (Preve and Allende, 2010) and its management is crucial for all types of businesses; therefore, the following sections define and interpret WCM that will allow financial practitioners to use the WCM technique correctly and effectively.

2.3.2. DEFINING WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

It has been observed that different authors and scholars have defined the concept of working capital in several ways. Some of these definitions as provided by different authors are demonstrated in Table 2.1 below.

Table 2.1 Typology of definitions of working capital management (WCM)

Authors	Definitions
Martin (2003)	Management of working capital involves managing the firm's investment in current assets and its use of current liabilities.
Khan and Jain (2007)	The management of current assets and current liabilities to maintain working capital at a satisfactory level.
Yadav and Kamath (2009)	The financing, control, and investment of net current assets within the strategic plans.
Nimalathasan (2010)	The management of WC and short-term financing.
Jain et al. (2013)	WCM is concerned with the complications that businesses face while managing current assets and current liabilities and the interrelationships between them.
Garg (2015)	A process of financing, planning, and controlling the level and mix of the current assets of the firm as well as long-term liabilities.

From the above discussion, it has been identified that different authors have defined working capital management (WCM) in different ways. The above definitions mostly focused on the two main components of WC: current assets and current liabilities (Martin, 2003; Khan and Jain, 2007). Their definitions are not clear in relation to the management of WC. However, Yadav and Kamath (2009) only mentioned the control of the process on current assets. Writing in WCM, Garg (2015) makes the point that WCM is the process of financing, planning, and

controlling the level and mix of the current assets and long-term liabilities. Despite this, this definition is not in line with that of Jain et al. (2013). According to their statement, WCM is concerned with the complications that businesses face while managing current assets and current liabilities and the interrelationships between them. Thus, integrating all definitions, it can be concluded that WCM is the process of planning and controlling the interrelationship between current assets and current liabilities to maintain the liquidity of the business.

2.3.3. The components of working capital management (WCM)

Different elements of current assets and current liabilities, such as inventory, accounts payable and accounts receivable, cash, creditors, short-term loans and so on, establish the structure of WCM (Eya, 2016). However, these elements are the main components of WCM.

2.3.3.1. Current assets management

According to Jain et al. (2013), current assets management is considered as the key goal of working capital management (WCM). Efficient management of current assets (CA) is essential to maintain liquidity of a business. The major CA are cash, both in hand and in the bank, inventories, and accounts receivable, etc. (Garg, 2015). Inventories include raw materials, work in progress, finished or unfinished goods, etc. However, types of inventories a business hold are different for different types of industries. Generally, for small retail businesses inventories are finished goods rather than raw materials (Preve and Allende, 2010).

Further, Preve and Allende (2010) noted that some inventories are less liquid; therefore, investment in inventory holdings could be tied up for an extensive period. Consequently, excess inventory in stock increases maintenance costs (Azami and Tabar, 2016). Whereas, low levels of inventory may lead to customer loss. Hence, Jain et al. (2013) stated that effective management of inventories helps a business to reduce the cost of holding excess goods while maximizing sales by holding the right products in the right amount.

Referring to account receivable management, Khan and Jain (2007) said accounts receivable are an important source of current assets; therefore, management of receivables is crucial for a small business. Businesses usually sell their products on credit and allow customers a specified time to pay their invoices. According to Preve and Allende (2010), this type of transaction generates a commercial credit. These credit sales are often referred to as trade receivables. Receivables are linked to the level of daily sales and the collection period offered to customers.

Afrifa (2016) identified that a positive cash flow can be maintained through receivables management. Extension or reduction of a credit period involves both risk and cost and therefore may affect a small business either positively or negatively. Consequently, receivables management is crucial to maintain positive cash flow as well as current assets (Jain et al., 2013). The following part discusses current liabilities management, which is another significant element of WCM.

2.3.3.2. Current liabilities management

Current liabilities are divided into short-term loans, accounts payable, bank overdrafts, and accrued liabilities (Garg, 2015). A business purchases goods or services on credit and receives invoices from its suppliers. These are known as accounts payable (Enow and Kamala, 2016). Accounts payable are considered a significant source of short-term debts available to small businesses with minimum cost (Mohamad et al., 2017). The accounts payable or supplier's account can be calculated by multiplying the daily total purchases from that supplier with the number of days the supplier allows before payment is due (Preve and Allende, 2010).

Managing accounts payable is important, as paying suppliers on time enables small businesses to minimize the risk of late payment. In addition, setting payables on the last day of payment not only enables a business to take advantage of cash discounts, but also enables a small business to re-invest the funds to secure a short-term source of finance (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013).

2.3.3.3. Working capital cycle (WCC)

The different elements of working capital are interconnected and can be articulated as a working capital or operational or cash conversion cycle. Kalsie and Arora (2016) defined the cash conversion cycle (CCC) as the average number of days between a cash payment made by a firm to its creditors and collection of cash from its debtors. According to Arnold (2008), CCC is the amount of time or a cycle a business takes in which it purchases inventory or raw materials, sells finished goods on credit, and then receives the amount due from the sale of the goods. This cycle involves three stages (Khan and Jain, 2007). In phase one, cash is transformed into inventory by purchasing goods from suppliers. This stage includes converting

raw materials into work in progress, followed by transferring finished goods to stock. However, this phase is absent in the case of the small retail industry. In the next phase, the inventory is converted into accounts receivable as credit sales are made to customers. This stage is absent in case of businesses which do not sell on credit. The final phase represents the accounts receivable stage, where receivables are collected. Thus, CCC is a measure of a business's liquidity. It calculates how quickly a business can turn its inventory or current assets into cash. The working capital cycle is managed by WCM (Garg, 2015).

Working capital cycle (CCC) is used as a measure of working capital level (Afrifa and Padachi, 2016). The longer the duration of CCC, the larger the requirement of WC for a business (Jain et al., 2013). Shorter CCC indicates that trade creditors or suppliers finance WC needs of businesses. Firms with negative WCC cannot meet WC requirements; therefore, these types of firms collect receivables quickly while paying trade creditors late. The components of WCM can be measured as mentioned in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Methods of measuring WCM components

The working capital and components	How it is measured
Working capital	Inventory + Accounts receivable – Accounts payable
Inventory (INV)	<i>Inventory = Daily cost of goods × Days in inventory</i>
Accounts receivable (AR)	<i>Trade Receivables = Daily Sales × Days of Trade Receivables</i>
Accounts payable (AP)	<i>Accounts payable = Daily purchases × Days credit from suppliers</i>
Cash conversion cycle (CCC)	<i>(Accounts receivable/sales) × 365 + (inventories/sales) × 365 - (accounts payable/sales) × 365</i>

Source: Banos-Caballero et al. (2014)

Small food restaurants transformed cash into inventory by purchasing raw goods from suppliers. In the next stage, inventory or foods are converted into accounts receivable as cash

sales are made to customers. Finally, cash receivables are collected from customers as food bills. Therefore, in this study the researcher investigates the requirement of WC by using the three main components: inventory, receivables, and payables in small restaurants. Based on the above stages suggested by Khan and Jain (2007), the following flowchart describes the three stages of CCC in small restaurants. These components are crucial for the requirement of WCM, because the shorter the duration of working capital cycle, the less the requirement of WC for a business (Jain et al., 2013).

Figure 2.1 The three stages of working capital cycle in small food restaurants

Source: Khan and Jain (2007)

2.4. SMALL BUSINESS AND WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

Small businesses are crucial both in the universal sense and in terms of their contributions to the economy of both developing (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Sadik, 2017; Jiang et al., 2018) and developed (Hillary, 2017) countries. Small businesses account for 99% of the 3.7 million businesses and 38% of total GDP in the UK (Hillary, 2017). It is evident (Jiang et al., 2018) that small businesses are the main channel to solve the problem of unemployment in both developed and developing countries. A survey by the Department for Business Innovation and Skills (BIS, 2016) identified that small businesses with between 10 and 49 employees contributed 34% (870,000) jobs in the UK.

Mohamad et al. (2017) suggest that WCM is crucial for a business of any size that operates in developed or in emerging countries. Previous studies (Banos-Caballero et al., 2014; Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Mansoori and Muhammad, 2012) argued that the management of WC is

more important for smaller businesses than larger-size businesses. Small businesses heavily rely on short-term debts. The capital structure of small-size businesses is different than large-size businesses because of their sizes. In addition, small businesses have high liquidity as compared with large businesses (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). Therefore, management of working capital is more important to small businesses than to large businesses (Jiang et al., 2018).

Working capital management is a tradeoff between risk and profitability (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). According to Jain et al. (2013), excessive working capital has adverse impacts on the performance of a business. Whereas, inadequate working capital interrupts the operational activities as well as the profitability of businesses. As a result, small business owners need to maintain an adequate amount of working capital for the smooth running of their businesses. For example, excess amounts of inventory in stock increases the cost of maintenance, whereas having low levels of inventory increases the risk of running out of stock and losing customers (Azami and Tabar, 2016). In addition, working capital management is very important to small businesses as it enable a business to maintain a perfect balance between liquidity and profitability, while in the process of conducting daily business activities (Agyei-Mensah, 2012).

Previous research (Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016) suggests that in smaller businesses, working capital management is more critical than for large enterprises. This means that the more an organization grows, the less important is working capital management (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). Despite this, many small businesses ignore the process of WCM (Orobia et al., 2016). Most of the studies (Orobia et al., 2016; Oseifuah, 2016; Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014) related to the WCM of small businesses have been undertaken in the context of developing countries. Therefore, this study evaluates the working capital requirements of small food restaurants in the context of the UK.

2.4.1. THE REQUIREMENTS OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT IN SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS

According to Crick et al. (2016), the UK exhibits a variety of restaurants with a multicultural base of customers. Managing restaurant businesses is very difficult for small business owners due to a highly competitive environment. Small food restaurants in the UK are facing growing competition from their rivals. Therefore, restaurants need to increase food quality and menu prices in uncertain economic conditions, where commodity costs increase (Mun and Jang, 2015). Even in the period of financial distress, small firms need to offer more generous credit terms to their customers (Paul and Boden, 2011). This results in low operating margins and reduced internal finance. Therefore, effective management of working capital is compulsory to meet their financial obligations (Zariyawati et al., 2017).

Mun and Jang (2015) identified that restaurant businesses require optimal levels of working capital. Unlike other industries, the restaurant industry has very low levels of WC and high levels of accounts payable. Consequently, small restaurant businesses rely significantly on suppliers' credit for managing cash flow and business operations. Mostly, this is because small restaurant businesses are financially constrained; they have limited access to credit from financial institutions. Financial institutions, for example banks, consider small firms as being high risk to offer any credit. As restaurant businesses struggle to cope with economic uncertainty more than other industries, most of the firms fail during their first year of operation (Parsa et al., 2005). The lack of capital is the main cause of failure. The management of working capital is crucial for a small restaurant in this respect.

Restaurant businesses need to manage all components of WC, because identifying and maintaining an optimal level of accounts receivable, inventories, and accounts payable leads to a significant increase in performance for financially constrained firms (Baños-Caballero et al., 2014). In the restaurant industry, food quality is crucial to maintain good customer relationships and services. Therefore, paying by the due date or early is one way to maintain a strong relationship with suppliers (Mun and Jang, 2015). Research conducted by Louw et al. (2019) confirmed the importance of inventory management and accounts payable management in the retail industry. This study further revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail (e.g. restaurant) industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Therefore, accounts receivable was found to be insignificant in the restaurant industry.

WCM is particularly important to small firms, including small restaurants, as they cannot avoid investment in inventories and cash receivables (Zariyawati et al., 2017). Since small restaurant firms are financially constrained, managing accounts receivable is crucial for small restaurants. Small restaurant owners develop a core customer base through personal networking and word of mouth (Chaudry and Crick, 2004; Crick et al., 2016). Moreover, they extend credit terms to their customers to gain competitive advantages over competitors. Credit sales to customers can enhance the sales rate of a business; however, on the other hand, excessive accounts receivable days may lead to bad debts (Salek, 2005) and late payment problems (Paul and Boden, 2011; BEIS, 2018). Ndagijimana (2014) identified that small businesses should maintain a balance between cash sales and credit sales. Restaurant businesses can generate extra cash from business operation sooner than other industry; therefore, restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively (Mun and Jang, 2015). Effective accounts receivable management reduces the challenges that are likely to result from overreliance on debts (Ndagijimana, 2014).

Adekunle and Sunday (2015) noted that keeping accounts receivable and inventories at an optimal level will help to avoid unnecessary tying up of WC. Optimal levels of working capital increase the profitability of restaurant businesses (Mun and Jang, 2015). However, the level of WC differs based on economic conditions, as well as firm-specific factors (Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014). The factors that affect the way small businesses manage their WC relate to firm size, nature of business, and leverage, etc. (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Louw and Hall, 2016). By effectively managing working capital, small restaurants will be able to manage financial crisis and increase profitability rates by controlling all factors that have an impact on working capital management (Mun and Jang, 2015). Therefore, based on existing literature, the following section evaluates the factors determining WC requirements of small businesses. While we explore this issue primarily by reference to the UK, it is likely that the nature of these problems is similar in all developed economies.

2.4.2. THE REQUIREMENT OF WCM IN SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS IN THE UK BUSINESS CONTEXT

According to a report by Industrial Facts and Forecasting (IFF) (2019), the restaurant sector in the UK (as defined by UK Standard Industrial Classification of Economic Activities (SIC) 2007 56.1 ‘Restaurants and mobile food service activities’ and 56.3 ‘Beverage serving activities’) is characterized by a high proportion of franchises. However, a smaller proportion of independent food restaurants operate in the UK alongside higher proportions of franchises. These independent small food restaurants sell healthy food and non-alcoholic drinks, and therefore have become more popular choices. An increase in the whole ‘dining experience’ quality has contributed to increased competition and challenges in the sector. This research was conducted by IFF on behalf of the Director of Labour Market Enforcement (DLME), to inform the annual strategy 2019/20. The focus of this report was the restaurant sector only.

According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS) (2020), the counts of licensed restaurants and unlicensed restaurants in the UK as of 15th March 2019 are 28,705 and 22,970 respectively. The percentage of restaurants was largest in London. In 2017 there were 7,990 licensed restaurants in London (ONS, 2018). According to recent figures, almost 10,000 licensed premises in the UK, including restaurants, closed permanently in 2020 as Covid-19 hammered this sector (Sillars, 2021). Data from the Office for National Statistics (2018) shows that small restaurants employ 10 to 49 staff. In addition, skill shortages are another challenge in small food restaurants (Winterbotham et al., 2018). As this sector is facing high levels of competition, the intensity of work is often high. From 1990 to 2004, the number of employees whose highest qualification was of QCF 3r lower. However, the number of employees with a highest qualification of QCF4 to QCF7 has been growing. Employment in the restaurant sector has grown in all parts of the UK. As a result, most parts of the country are shifting away from pubs and bars towards restaurant (IFF, 2019).

Despite this, recently many UK small businesses have been negatively affected by Covid-19 because of supply disruption, lack of demand by customers, and economic uncertainty (Insider, 2020). UK inflation rates are predicted to rise 2% in the latter half of 2021 closer to the Bank of England’s target (NIESR, 2021). Such escalations in inflation rate eventually affect the ability of small restaurants to borrow external finance. Therefore, healthy WCM will help small restaurants to tackle uncertain economic changes for the coming years. Protecting cash flow is a key concern for small food restaurants. Effective management of working capital helps UK

small businesses, including in the restaurant sector, to avoid the need for expensive external finance (Afrifa, 2016). Therefore, management of working capital is imperative to small businesses most importantly the restaurant sector (Jiang et al., 2018). Small restaurant businesses are referred to together throughout this study as ‘the small restaurant’ or ‘small food restaurants’ sector.

The restaurant sector workforce is multinational and multicultural in the UK (KPMG, 2017). A study was conducted by Singhania and Mehta (2017) to analyse the impact of working capital management on the profitability of 11 countries within the Asia Pacific region: India, Pakistan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, Hong Kong, Japan, China, South Korea, and Taiwan. Their study revealed a non-linear relationship between the profitability and WCM for all 11 countries operating in the Asia Pacific region. Another study by Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) suggests that the leverage and WCM relations between different countries indicates that there is no common characteristic for at least two of the countries.

On the contrary, Frijns et al. (2017) pointed out that multinational small businesses operating in the same country were associated with cultural diversity which affected capital structures of their businesses. Increased cultural diversity leads to a decrease in leverage ratio. Even though business-level determinants such as business size and profitability were controlled, cultural diversity directly had an impact on capital structure decisions of the US multinational firms. Thus, either small businesses operating in different countries (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014) or multinational small businesses operating in the same country manage their WCM differently due to country-specific factors such as legal environment and culture (Falconer et al., 2016). The following section situates the influence of business-level factors: management competencies, the size of business, leverage, and profitability on the WCM in the context of existing literature.

2.5. FACTORS AFFECTING WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

WCM is a challenging issue for financial managers (Eya, 2016). Maintaining the level of WCM is a complex task (Preve and Allende, 2010). A firm with higher level of WC investment may go into bankruptcy due to additional interest expenses (Baños-Caballero et al., 2014), while a small business with insufficient WC will struggle to pay short-term liabilities in time and is

accordingly unable to maintain good credit terms with suppliers and banks. Therefore, a business should aim to maintain WC as close to the optimal level as possible (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014). However, maintaining an optimal working capital level is a complicated task as there are many external (Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013) and internal factors (Azami and Tabar, 2016) that need to be considered and balanced. Previous literature (Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015) suggests that working capital management (WCM) is dependent on various factors. As stated by Mansoori and Muhammad (2012), internal factors affecting WCM focus on a firm's unique characteristics, while external factors such as economic condition cannot be controlled by firms. Vijayalakshmi and Bansal (2013) identified the price of raw materials as one important exogenous or external factor to the firm that cannot be controlled. Similarly, GDP, interest rates, and tax rates affect WCM exogenously (Atseye et al., 2015). There is no specific set of rules to determine the WC requirement (Adeniji, 2008) and the exact amount of WC for every type of business (Boopathi and Leeson, 2016). Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the data and factors affecting the WC of each type of business. The next section analyses the internal factors that determine the requirement of WCM.

2.5.1. INTERNAL FACTORS AFFECTING WCM

Previous research (Oseifuah, 2016; Atseye et al., 2015; Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013) identified that WCM is dependent on various internal factors. Endogenous factors are internal to the firm and, therefore, can be controlled to some extent (Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013). Internal factors are the firm's size (Azeem and Marsap, 2015), leverage (Azami and Tabar, 2016), profitability (Atseye et al., 2015), managerial competencies, e.g. financial knowledge (Agyei-Mensah, 2012), financial training and skills (Orobia et al., 2016), work experience (Afrifa, 2013), etc. Leverage is the amount of debt a business uses to finance capital assets (Azami and Tabar, 2016). According to pecking order theory (Myers, 1984), leverage level is determined based on financial need. A company needs to reduce debt through internal financing. Working capital is a source of internal finance. Vijayalakshmi and Bansal (2013) found that internal factors determine the requirement of WCM of a business. However, most of the existing research is based on the context of developing countries. Small businesses also operate within a developed country which has an established economy as well as financial markets and banks (Fethi and Katircioglu, 2015). Therefore, it is important to investigate whether the factors determining the WCM of a small business is different in a developed

economy. For this reason, the following sections demonstrate the concept of WCM in relation to small businesses in the UK. It explores different factors and variables that influence practice of WCM in small business.

2.5.1.1. MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES: PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND EXPERIENCES

Management's role in how working capital influences the performance of a business is very significant (Eya, 2016). It is evident (Pansiri and Temtime, 2008; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Boopathi and Leeson, 2016) that success or failure of a business is affected by managerial skills and competencies. SMEs are poorly managed because of lack of management competencies. Incompetent managers are not able to engage in strategic planning processes. Moreover, efficient management of WC is crucial for the survival of small businesses (Zariyawati et al., 2017) as WCM increases a firm's performance and liquidity (Aktas et al., 2015). Notwithstanding the relative importance of WCM practices to small businesses, knowledge and understanding of WCM practices of SMEs is not adequate (Howorth and Westhead, 2003). Work experience of managers is crucial to the effective management of WC (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). According to Afrifa (2013), experienced managers can manage all components and aspects of WCM.

Orobia et al. (2016) identified that the effect of financial knowledge on WC is considered theoretical and less relevant for small-scale businesses; rather, prior experience determines the likelihood of WCM practices in firms. Thus, the owners and managers of small businesses get knowledge and skills of WCM through prior experience as opposed to the formal education system. This result would be more appropriate in the developing country context, where managers are not high in the education hierarchy (Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017). Since Ugandan small-scale businesses are not computerized, their customers and suppliers are not sophisticated in their demands for accounting documentation. Such results may be misleading in the context of developed countries. In the UK, small business reports indicate high technical skills and sophistication, as they need to develop new products and services to meet customer demands (BEIS, 2015). Formal education and prior experience contribute to the effective WCM of UK SMEs (Afrifa, 2013) which is one of the crucial parts of the financial decision-making process (Aktas et al., 2015).

The literature (Aktas et al., 2015; Ruan and Li, 2017) suggests that WCM practice of small businesses may be influenced by knowledge management. Ruan and Li (2017) studied WCM from the perspective of knowledge management. The findings of this study indicated that skills, training, knowledge acquirement, and management are combined with knowledge management practices. Managers or owners of small businesses are the major source of financial knowledge and information. However, owner-managers tend not to share knowledge with other employees as they think it may affect their control and importance (Wong and Aspinwall, 2004). Therefore, the attitude and motivation of managers should be enhanced through knowledge management. The process of knowledge management should therefore involve retaining and sharing the knowledge and experience of managers within a small business. Orobio et al. (2013) stated that to improve WCM, owner-managers of small businesses do not require the same type of sophisticated knowledge as those of large businesses. Rather than planning, controlling, and monitoring WC activities, small business managers need soft skills. Magoutas et al. (2012) identified that managers with sophisticated knowledge possess certain leadership and organizational skills such as communication, team-working and problem-solving skills. These soft skills are useful to manage working capital.

Louw and Hall (2016) noted that financial knowledge of managers is related to the level of WCM in different sizes of firms. This study found that the requirement of WCM is determined by financial knowledge of owners or managers of small businesses. An owner-manager of a small business manages WC but might not be an expert in the area of financial management. Nevertheless, managers apply their financial knowledge based on their personal experience and opinions, which is sometimes inaccurate and can lead to business failure (Wong and Aspinwall, 2004). Moreover, small businesses are unable to afford qualified accounts staff and appropriate accounting software. The operators or managers of small businesses possess limited accounting knowledge and weak financial skills (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). Consequently, small businesses are poorly managed owing to management incompetence (Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013), therefore have poor WCM practices (Afrifa, 2013). On the other hand, larger firms prefer to recruit experienced and qualified employees to minimize the time and cost of training (Chaudry and Crick, 2004). Competent employees therefore consider their career to be more stable in larger firms. In large firms working capital is managed by knowledgeable people who work towards the same goal set by their finance department (Louw and Hall, 2016).

Previous research (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Afrifa, 2013) emphasized that work experience of managers has an impact on the management of working capital components such as inventory, accounts receivable and accounts payable. Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017) noted that educated and experienced managers can manage all components of WCM practices. For inventory control systems, for example, the two-bin system is important for a small business. According to this system a business maintains two bins. The second bin is counted as safety stock. However, an opposing point of view (Agyei-Mensah, 2012) argued that there is no association between theoretical knowledge of managers and WCM practices in small businesses. Rather, managerial practical experience was considered more significant than theoretical knowledge in both inventory and cash management. Experienced managers make fewer mistakes compared with inexperienced managers. Thus, small businesses mostly emphasize practical knowledge in the context of Ghana. However, this finding is in contradiction to Afrifa (2013). This study found that in the UK the education and prior experience of managers are crucial factors in the management of WC components. Which suggests further investigation in this area of WCM.

Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017) studied the impact of WCM on managerial performance in Nigeria. The research found that WCM and managerial performance are significantly correlated. The result suggests that majority of the respondents are not high in the education hierarchy, therefore possess insufficient knowledge and skills on WCM. Chepkemoui et al. (2017) found that the profitability of a business is significantly dependent on the financial knowledge and skills of the business owners. This study identified that lack of financial literacy on effective management of WC is one of the major problems that SMEs are facing. Financial literacy is the ability to use financial knowledge and skills. Thus, financial literacy training positively influences the working capital management of small businesses and hence profitability. Additionally, the lack of managerial skills affects the short and long-term strategic planning in small business (Pansiri and Temtime, 2008).

Most of the above studies have been undertaken in the context of developing countries. The effects of managerial competencies would be different in the context of a developed country. For example, lack of specialized skills and training is a common problem in SMEs of a developing country like Malaysia, while more than half of the British SMEs (BEIS, 2015) receive general and specialized skills and training. Nevertheless, small businesses strive to

employ knowledgeable, experienced, and qualified people to manage working capital effectively both in developing (Orobia et al., 2013; Enow and Kamala, 2016; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017) and developed (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Afrifa, 2013) countries. In the UK small businesses most importantly, small restaurants cannot afford to recruit experienced people. Owner-managers think that experienced staff will demand a high salary, which may affect the profitability of their small restaurants (Chaudry and Crick, 2004). Even though well-developed skills and managerial best practices are positively related to the performance of UK small businesses, according to the Department for Business Innovation and Skills (BEIS) (2015) leadership and management skills are relatively underdeveloped in many English SMEs. Therefore, this study will identify the impact of management competencies on the management of working capital of UK small food restaurants. Finally, there are other internal factors that determine the working capital management of small businesses, apart from managerial knowledge, skills, and experience. The effect of business size on the management of working capital is described in the following section.

2.5.1.2. BUSINESS SIZE

The size of business is one of the most important determinants of working capital management. There are empirical cases (Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Orobia et al., 2016; Baker et al., 2017; Ashhari et al., 2017) available to highlight the requirements of WCM based on business size. Previous research (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Garg, 2015) suggests that the size of a business has an impact on the practice of WCM in small businesses. However, they have conflicting opinions on the level of WC requirements of firms with different sizes. Previous researchers argued over whether there is a positive relationship between the size and the requirements of WCM (Javid, 2014; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Orobia et al., 2016). Orobia et.al. (2016) found that business size is positively related to WCM. As the businesses increases, the need for activities related to WCM becomes relevant. A small business requires less working capital than a larger firm because of the small scale of operations (Garg, 2015). Whereas, a large business requires more investment WC because of the large scale of operations (Adekunle and Sunday, 2015) and high volume of sales (Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016).

However, an opposing point of view (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016) argued that the size of business is negatively related to working capital requirements of SMEs, therefore, the small-size business requires more WC. This study is in line with the studies of

Mansoori and Muhammad (2012) and Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam (2013). Small businesses rely heavily on WCM. As the limited financial resources available to SMEs, these sizes of businesses invest more in WC to avoid the risk of financial scarcity (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013). Large businesses are financially unconstrained and better at managing their cash cycle, hence they require investment of less WC (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Wasiuzzaman, 2015), whereas small businesses are financially constrained and their firm size can lead to difficulties in managing working capital. Efficient WCM increased the value of the financially constrained firms. In addition, other researchers (Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Azeem and Marsap, 2015) have outlined that the small-size business requires more WC than a large-size business as they have less favourable credit terms with suppliers and customers. A larger-size business may have favourable credit terms with suppliers and customers (Agyei-Mensah, 2012), therefore large firms are likely to invest less in WC. In this case, a negative relationship between the size of firms and requirement of WCM should be expected.

Moreover, large and small-size businesses require different amounts of WC, but as much because of their size as because of their financial ability (Hill et al., 2010). Small businesses have limited access to capital through external financing (Zariyawati et al., 2016; Wapshott and Mallett, 2018). Therefore, they mostly depend on internal financing such as owner financing, trade credit, short-term loans, etc. Banks and investors consider small businesses as high-risk borrowers due to their insufficient assets, vulnerability to economic uncertainty, and market fluctuations (Padachi et al., 2012). In addition, inadequate business plans and financial statements make it difficult for financial investors to assess the creditworthiness of borrowers. Consequently, firms use internal funds before seeking external (Wapshott and Mallett, 2018).

The size of businesses has an impact on the management of the three main components of WCM. Baker et al. (2017) identified that the size of a business has an impact on inventory management. Small businesses generate a list of inventory requirements which is no more than a shopping list (Orobia et al., 2013). Regarding inventory management, small businesses show poor performance as they never review stock level, stock turnover, and stock reorder level (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). Ineffective management of inventory may increase the maintenance cost. Hence, small businesses implement basic inventory management processes. Furthermore, Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017) found that the choice of an inventory control system is determined by the size of a business. For instance, a small business with small scale of

operation might find that the two bin system is useful to manage its inventory, whereas a large business maintaining several types of inventories may find it unsatisfactory. Therefore, larger-size businesses may prefer to operate automatic computer systems to track their inventory position.

Management of WC components may vary with firm size (Shaista and Veeri, 2013; Ashhari et al., 2017). Small firms invest less in WC by reducing accounts receivable and inventory turnover periods. On the other hand, accounts receivable and inventory turnover in days was not significant for large firms. Rather, large businesses increase the accounts payable period. As larger firms have favourable credit terms with suppliers and customers (Agyei-Mensah, 2012), these size businesses increase profitability by investing cash which is payable to suppliers. However, Enow and Kamala (2016) identified that small businesses had lower bargaining power in terms of credit purchasing with suppliers. Lack of employees was the main factor that inhibits small businesses from managing accounts payable effectively. The requirements of accounts receivable management are also different for different size businesses. Agyei-Mensah (2012) found that accounts receivable management in Ghanaian small businesses is poor. Small businesses never review debtor credit periods, bad debts, and customer risk standing. These outcomes are contradictory with the result of Azami and Tabar, (2016). This study investigated the determinants of investment level in WC over the period of 2004 to 2014. The findings elaborated that there was no significant relationship between company size and the components of WCM. Similarly, Baker et al. (2017) identified that the size of businesses has no impact on accounts receivable management.

Howorth and Westhead (2003) found that in the UK small and large businesses manage WC differently due to the different cash conversion cycle (CCC) length. CCC represents the amount of days in which cash is tied up in WC (Atseye et al., 2015). A small firm with a shorter CCC will require a lower level of WC invested in the business. This is instinctive in the sense that small firms need to finance receivables and inventory through payables. Longer receivables days and inventory days in proportion to payables days will require more equity. Consequently, the owner of a firm with a longer CCC is forced to invest their own capital at risk (Ebben and Johnson, 2011). On the other hand, effective management of WC through a shorter CCC improves the profitability of small businesses (Pais and Gama, 2015).

Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) investigated country-specific factors that influence the WCM of small and large businesses in different EU countries. The findings identified that WCM is most affected by country-specific factors. Further, there is no common pattern in relation to WCM for at least two of the countries. For instance, the financial structure of small and large businesses may differ across countries. Most of the above studies investigated the impact of business size on the WC requirements in the context of developing countries, with the exception of a few studies (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). Therefore, there is a need for investigation into the effect of size on WCM practices in the context of the UK.

2.5.1.3. LEVERAGE OR DEBT RATIO

As mentioned earlier, the debt ratio or leverage of a business is an important factor affecting WC requirements (Muhammad and Elias, 2013). Leverage is the amount of debt a business uses to finance capital assets (Azami and Tabar, 2016). Elbadry (2018) stated that a higher debt ratio or leverage reflects more risk premium. Adekunle and Sunday (2015) noted that financial managers can practise WCM efficiently by reducing their firm's debt level. According to empirical research (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Elbadry, 2018), the relationship between leverage and WCM is usually negative. Low debt ratio or leverage leads to lower interest and risk premium (Elbadry, 2018). This study identified that smaller-size SMEs have a lower level of leverage. Low leverage has negative effects on WC requirements. Accordingly, firms with low leverage are likely to have the highest investment in WC (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Elbadry, 2018), indicating a negative relationship between leverage and WCM. This finding is in line with the concepts discussed in pecking order theory (1984). Based on this theory, Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam (2013) elaborated on the negative relationship between leverage and WCM. A business with lower levels of internal finance will depend on debt finance. The repayment of debts results in a decrease in the capital available to perform daily operations. Thus, this situation forces a business to manage its working capital efficiently.

However, Valipour (2012) argued that debt ratio is positively and significantly correlated with WCM. In this study CCC was used as a measure of WCM. Positive correlation means businesses with a high debt ratio invest more in WCM. A business with a low debt ratio tends to decrease inventory days to keep CCC shorter. Thus, the low debt ratio reflects the capability

of a business to manage WC and to shorten CCC. This result is opposite to those of Manoori and Muhammad (2012) and Qurashi and Zahoor (2017). A recent study (Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017) found insignificant results for leverage and WCM, therefore no relation of WCM with leverage for UK pharmaceutical firms. This result is aligned with the finding of Gill (2010) and Manoori and Muhammad (2012). Their studies identified an insignificant relationship between WC requirements and debt ratio. Alternatively, firms with higher levels of leverage need to release the capital that is tied up in current assets (Abbadi and Abbadi, 2013). As working capital is an internal source of finance, it can be used as an alternative to external sources of finance. Muhammad and Elias (2013) stated that businesses with higher debt levels seek to expand their accounts payable period and credit terms with suppliers. These types of firms adopt aggressive policies of WCM (Ukaegbu, 2013); therefore they tend to minimize inventories and account collection periods. Elbadry (2018) found that SMEs follow aggressive policies of WCM as these firms hold low levels of WC. These policies lead to a high degree of risk measured by leverage. Thus, firms with high leverage exhibit lower WC requirements. High levels of leverage are probably due to the problems of internal funds. Hence, businesses need to pay more attention to WCM and CCC to avoid the problems of funds shortfall (Nazir and Afza, 2009).

Referring to the relation between debt ratio and WC ratio, Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) suggests that a small business with a high level of leverage needs to maintain more working capital than other sizes of business. This study identified a positive relation between the leverage and WCM of small businesses only, and though the correlation is similar across countries, there are noticeable differences across size groups. The leverage and WCM relations between different countries indicates that there is no common characteristic for at least two of the countries. This suggests that the way leverage affects WCM and its compounds is determined by country factors. Furthermore, Fan et al. (2012) identified a significant variation in leverage and debt ratio in developed and developing countries. Most of the developing countries are politically corrupted, and therefore tend to use more short-term debt, whereas businesses operating within a better legal system tend to use more long-term debt as financial applicants receive better protection for debt financing. As a result, it is important to investigate whether this relation is positive or negative in the context of UK small-size food restaurants.

Mun and Jang (2015) examined the effect of leverage on US food restaurants. The findings revealed a significant negative relation between working capital levels and firms' leverage.

Food restaurants with high levels of leverage tend to invest less in WC. Nevertheless, this result may not be applicable to the small food restaurants operating in the UK. In Britain 80% of small businesses are reliant on bank loans for external financing (Abbott, 2013). Small business owners think that taxation policy is the main obstacle to business success (Wapshott and Mallett, 2018). Small business owners prefer debt finance, as the interest payable on debt financing is deducted from the amount of tax payable. As a result, small food restaurant businesses operating in the UK may find a positive relationship between debt ratio and working capital management. As a result, this study investigates the effect of leverage on the WC requirements of small UK food restaurants.

2.5.1.4. PROFITABILITY

Even though the determinants of working capital management (WCM) motivated and triggered many researchers (Atseye et al., 2015; Jiang et al., 2018; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014; Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013), opinions as to the relationship between WCM and a firm's profitability have been divided. There is strong evidence (Atseye et al., 2015; Garg, 2015; Padachi and Afrifa, 2016; Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016) to suggest that WCM practice has a very strong impact on liquidity and profitability of an organization. According to Atseye et al. (2015), WCM is determined endogenously by firms' profitability. There exists a very strong positive relationship between different variables such as the cash conversion cycle (CCC), debt-equity ratio, and profitability of small businesses. Mansoori and Muhammad (2012) found that profitable businesses have a longer cash conversion cycle. An optimal level of working capital is essential to maximize the profitability of SMEs (Padachi and Afrifa, 2016). However, other researchers with opposing points of view (Dinku, 2013; Alsie and Arora, 2016; Lyngstadaas and Berg, 2016) supported a negative association between the components of WCM and profitability of SMEs.

Referring to the relative importance of WCM and its components on a firm's performance, Tauringana and Afrifa (2013) said that accounts receivable (AR) management is more important than accounts payable (AP) for the profitability of SMEs. This study identified a high and significant negative association between AR and profitability, which means reducing AR days to collect AR early from its customers, increasing profitability. SMEs' shorter AR period helps SMEs to release funds from their customers to use elsewhere. However, this agreed with the findings of Duru et al. (2014) but was at odds with the results of Mbawuni et al. (2016). The findings of Mbawuni et al. (2016) showed a positive association between AR

and the profitability of firms. However, increasing investment in AR or increasing AR days may result in opportunity cost of cash tied up in AR. Duru et al. (2014) found a non-significant negative relation between AR and the profitability of firms. Thus, reducing accounts receivable days and collecting payment from their customers early increases the profitability of this industry.

Louw and Hall (2016) identified a positive correlation between accounts payable and the profitability of firms. Increasing trade payables improved the profitability of South African retail firms. However, this result contradicts other studies where researchers have found a negative relationship between AP and the profitability of SMEs (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Pais and Gama, 2015). Thus, SMEs that pay AP more quickly are more profitable because reducing AP days and making early payments to suppliers will help SMEs to maintain good relationships with suppliers and to minimize late payment costs. Pais and Gama (2015) pointed out that excessive liabilities may have a negative impact on the profitability of SMEs. Thus, their results indicate that a reduction in the number of days that SMEs take to settle their accounts payable are related to higher corporate profitability. Enow and Kamala (2016) investigated accounts payable management practices of small, medium, and micro businesses (SMMS) in South Africa. The findings indicate that 70% of the respondent SMMEs purchase on a cash basis and pay their creditors on time to take the benefits of discounts. Some 92% businesses purchased with cash and most businesses did not negotiate with their suppliers to extend the credit period.

Louw and Hall (2016) argued that inventory management has the strongest statistically significant impact on a firm's profitability. Furthermore, Bhatia and Srivastava (2016) identified a relation between working capital management and the profitability of a business. A firm's value can be enhanced by reducing accounts receivable days and inventory holding periods while extending payables days. Excessive inventory holding policy may increase inventory holding costs, whereas a reduced amount of inventory may cause an inventory stockout problem. An opposing point of view revealed that inventory (INV) is not important for the profitability of SMEs (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). This is probably because of the different types of inventory requirements by different sizes of businesses.

According to Davey et al. (2016), small businesses lack the resources to manage the components of WC effectively. Accordingly, the risk of late payment increases due to late

invoicing. Small businesses operating in emerging economies tend to neglect AR management due to its difficulty. Small businesses used manual record-keeping methods to manage their accounts payable (Mensah-Agyei, 2012). Enow and Kamala (2016) identified four factors that inhibit small businesses from managing their accounts payable effectively: lack of skills, resources, personnel, and time. Previous research (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Atseye et al., 2015; Enow and Kamala, 2016) shows significant differences between WCM and profitability of small businesses operating in different countries. Therefore, this study investigates whether WCM affects the profitability of small food restaurants in the UK, either positively or negatively.

2.6. CONCLUSION

This chapter demonstrates the background and context of the problem in relation to WCM and small businesses in the UK. Further, this chapter explores different factors and variables that influence practices of working capital management (WCM) of small businesses, in both developed and developing countries. The above literature review underpins the research and develops a conceptual framework for this study. The next chapter summarizes the previous research on WCM and develops a conceptual framework of the relationship between determining factors and the requirements of WCM. In addition, the conceptual framework emanating from the literature review that develops the four main hypotheses for this study is discussed in the next chapter. The following chapter further discusses the knowledge gap that has been identified in the literature and the motivation of this study.

CHAPTER 3

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOTHESES

3.1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this chapter is to develop a conceptual framework for this research by integrating internal factors and the requirements of working capital management (WCM). It has been identified from the previous literature that internal factors, such as management competencies, size of business, leverage, and profitability, are associated with WCM of businesses either positively or negatively. The arguments based on these four internal factors and the requirements of WCM in small businesses has developed the main hypotheses for this research (Figure 3.1).

Table 3.2 Summary of previous empirical research

Author(s) Year	Country	Methodology	Sample and length of data collection	WCM measures	Variables/Factors	Main findings
Afrifa (2013)	UK	T-test, one-way ANOVA and post-hoc test.	72 SMEs	WCM practices	Management competencies: education and work experience	Managers with higher level of education and more years of experience can manage all aspects of WCM.
Orobia et al. (2013)	Uganda	Qualitative inquiry: Content analysis techniques	Semi-structured interviewing of 10 owner-managers of small businesses	WCM	Management competencies	Owner-managers do not require educational knowledge and sophisticated techniques. They use soft skills and prior experience to manage WC and components.
Lauw and Hall (2016)	South Africa	Multiple linear regression	18 retail firms (2004-2012)	WC components: INV, AR, and AP	Management competencies Profitability: ROA, ROE,	Reducing INV and AR while increasing AP improves profitability.
Zariyawati et al. (2016)	Bursa, Malaysia	Panel data: Pooled OLS	100 small and large firms (2009-2013)	WCM: CCC	Leverage, performance, cash flow, and inflation	Firm-specific factors: leverage, cash flow, firm performance, and inflation were significantly negatively correlated with CCC.
Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017)	Nigeria	Descriptive survey	100 firms	WCM	Managerial performance	WCM and managerial performance are significantly correlated.
Ndagijimana and Okech (2014)	Nairobi	Regression analysis	84 SMEs	WCM	AR management AP management	AR and AP affect WCM practices in SME.
Wasiuzzaman and Armugam (2013)	Malaysia	OLS regression	192 companies (2000-2007)	Level of WC investment	The size of business Leverage Profitability	Size and leverage had a negative influence on the level of WC in smaller-size businesses. Profitability was found insignificant.
Wasiuzzaman (2015)	Malaysia	OLS regression	192 firms (1999-2008)	Working capital efficiency	The size of business	A significant relation between business size and firm value for small businesses.
Azeem and Marsap (2015)	Pakistan	ANOVA, regression	385 non-financial firms for period of 6 years (2004-2009)	WC requirements	The size of business, leverage, economic activity	Negative relation between variables (Size, LEV, and Eco) and WC requirements.
Orobia et al. (2016)	Uganda	Binary logistic regression	450 small-scale businesses	WCM practices	Management competencies The size of business	Prior experience of managers determines the likelihood of WCM practices. Business size is positively related to WCM.
Qurashi and Zahoor (2017)	UK	Panel data method, multiple regression	10 UK pharmaceutical firms (2009 to 2014)	Working capital	The size of business Leverage and level of economic activity	WC is negatively linked with the firm size while positively linked with economic activity. Insignificant results were observed for leverage.

Azami and Tabar (2016)	Tehran, Iran	The generalised method of moments (GMM)	143 companies (2004-2014)	Investment level in WC	Business size Leverage Profitability	Insignificant relation with firm size. Profitability and leverage are negatively related with the investment level in WC.
Koralun-Bereznicka (2014)	9 EU countries	Pearson correlation	9 EU countries (2000-2010)	Working capital	Leverage Firm size	Small firms with high leverage maintain more WC. Country-specific factors determine the effect of factors on WCM across size groups.
Valipour et al. (2012)	Tehran	Pearson correlation, multiple regression	83 firms (2001-2010)	The management of the working capital CCC	Profitability Leverage Size	Negative relation between profitability and CCC, and size and CCC. Positive relation between debt ratio and CCC.
Elbadry (2018)	Egypt	OLS regression	138 SMEs (2010-2013)	WC level measured by CCC	Leverage	Significant negative effect of SMEs profitability and leverage on WC. Significant positive effect between size and CCC.
Manoori and Muhammad (2012)	Singapore	Pooled OLS, random effects and fixed effects estimations	94 firms (2003-2010)	WCM	Business size Leverage	Firm size and WCM are negatively correlated. Positive relation between profitability and WC cycle. Insignificant relation between WC cycle and debt ratio (leverage).
Javid (2014)	Pakistan	Random effects regression model on panel data	54 SMEs for a period of five years (2006-2010)	WCM and CCC (INV< AR and AP)	Leverage Profitability Size	Leverage and size had positive significant impact on the performance of SMEs. Shorter CCC are more profitable.
Atseye et al. (2015)	Nigeria	Opinion, comments and suggestions from various research and scholars	Literature reviews	WCM	External and internal factors: size, profitability, interest rate, and tax rate	WCM is determined by both external and internal factors.
Padachi and Afrifa (2016)	UK	Regression analysis	160 AIM-listed SMEs (2005-2010)	WC level	Profitability	Optimal level of WC is recommended for AIM listed UK SMEs to maximize profitability.
Gorondutse et al. (2017)	Malaysia	Panel data regression	66 SMEs (2006-2012)	WCM, CCC	Profitability measures: ROA and ROE	Significant link between the WCM and performance of SMEs. Negative relationship between CCC and ROE.

3.2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The objective of this chapter is to develop a conceptual framework for this research by integrating internal factors: management competencies, size of business, leverage and profitability, and the requirements of working capital management (WCM). Figure 2.1 below provides the conceptual framework and resulting hypotheses. The main aim of the conceptual framework is the determination of internal factors affecting WCM in small food restaurants in the UK.

Table 3.1. Conceptual framework and resulting hypotheses

3.2.1. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The aim of these four hypotheses is to find the answers to the research questions developed in chapter one.

3.2.1.1. DEVELOPMENT OF H₁ AND H₂

It is evident that small businesses strive to employ knowledgeable, experienced, and qualified people to manage working capital effectively both in emerging (Orobia et al., 2013; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017) and developed (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Afrifa, 2013) countries. However, one group of researchers (Afrifa, 2013; Orobia et al., 2013; Louw and Hall, 2016; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017; Chepkemoi et al., 2017) argued that management competencies such as theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and skills affect the WC requirements of small businesses. On the other hand, other researchers (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Orobia et al., 2016) debated that there is no association between theoretical knowledge of managers and WCM practices in small businesses. Rather, managerial practical experience was considered more significant than theoretical knowledge in both inventory and cash management (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). The owners and managers of small businesses get knowledge and skills of WCM through prior experience as opposed to the formal education system (Orobia et al., 2016). These arguments suggest a further investigation in managerial competencies and WCM. Therefore, based on previous research (Afrifa, 2013; Orobia et al., 2013; Louw and Hall, 2016; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017; Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Orobia et al., 2016), the following hypothesis has been developed.

H₁: Managerial theoretical and practical knowledge is proportional to the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

It is widely reported in the literature (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Garg, 2015; Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Enow and Kamala, 2016; Orobia et al., 2016; Baker et al., 2017; Ashhari et al., 2017) that a firm's size has an impact on the practice of WCM in small businesses. However, mixed results have been found based on whether there is a positive (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Orobia et al., 2016) or negative (Mansoori and Muhammad, 2012; Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017) relationship between the size and the requirements of WCM. These outcomes are contradictory with the result of Azami and Tabar (2016). Their findings elaborated that there was no

significant relationship between company size and the components of WCM. Consequently, to further investigate this factor, the following hypothesis has been developed.

H₂: The size of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants.

3.2.1.2. DEVELOPMENT OF H₃ AND H₄

There is strong evidence (Shaista and Veeri, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Elbadry, 2018) to suggest that firms with low leverage are likely to have the highest investment in WC, therefore indicating a negative relationship between leverage and WCM. These findings are in line with the concepts discussed in pecking order theory (1984). However, an opposing point (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014) considers that the level of leverage is positively related to the WCM of small businesses. Furthermore, Valipour (2012) identified that debt ratio is positively and significantly correlated with WCM. Positive correlation means that a business with a high debt ratio will invest more in WCM. However, this result contradicts those of Gill (2010), Manoori and Muhammad (2012) and Qurashi and Zahoor (2017). Their studies identified an insignificant relationship between WC requirements and debt ratio. Moreover, the way leverage effects WCM and its compounds is determined by country factors. The leverage and WCM requirements between different countries indicates that there is no common characteristic for at least two of the countries (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014). Fan et al. (2012) identified a significant variation in leverage and debt ratio in developed and developing countries. Businesses operating within a better legal system tend to use more long-term debt as financial applicants receive better protection for debt financing. As a result, the following hypothesis has been developed to investigate whether this relation is positive or negative in the context of UK small-size food restaurants.

H₃: Leverage of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

Previous studies (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Atseye et al., 2015; Enow and Kamala, 2016; Pais and Gama, 2015) found significant differences between WCM requirements and profitability of small businesses operating in different countries. As a result, mixed results have been identified based on whether there is a positive (Atseye et al., 2015; Garg, 2015; Padachi and Afrifa, 2016; Mbawuni et al., 2016; Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016) or negative (Dinku, 2013; Alsie and Arora, 2016; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Lyngstadaas

and Berg, 2016) relation between the profitability and the components of WCM. This debate yields the following hypothesis.

H₄: The profitability of small food restaurants is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

3.3. SUMMARY AND GAP IN THE LITERATURE

The aim of this study is to identify the internal factors such as management competencies, size, leverage, and profitability influencing the requirements of WCM in small UK food restaurants. However, apart from a few studies (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017), most of the studies examined the impact of business size on the WCM in the context of emerging countries. Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) stated that there is no common pattern in relation to WCM for at least two of the countries. For instance, small businesses operate within a developed country which has well-developed economy as well as financial markets (Fethi and Katircioglu, 2015). Therefore, the financial structure of small and large businesses may differ across countries. This study investigates the effect of size on the WCM of small food restaurants in the context of the UK. In this sense this present study differs from the existing studies. Similarly, the effect of managerial competencies would be different in the context of a developed country. In the UK, more than half of the British SMEs receive general and specialized skills and training. Despite this, management skills are relatively underdeveloped in many English SMEs (BIS, 2015), which suggests further investigation in this area of WCM.

Concerning small food restaurants in the UK, this study further investigates the effect of leverage or debt ratio on the WCM. Zariyawati et al. (2016) stated that working capital policy is different in a developed country than a developing country due to different legislative systems. Fan et al. (2012) identified a significant variation between leverage in emerging and developed countries. Legal systems in emerging economies are corrupted, coupled with lack of financial stability and high levels of political risk. However, a business operating within a stronger legal system may tend to have a capital structure with more equity and long-term debt because of the strength of legislative safeguards. For instance, small businesses operating in the UK tend to use more long-term debt as financial applicants receive better protection for borrowing. In the UK, 80% of small businesses are reliant on bank loans for external financing (Abbott, 2013). A research study on small food restaurants operating in the UK may reveal a positive correlation between debt ratio and WC requirements as the interest payable on debt financing is deducted from the amount of tax payable. This

inconclusive relationship between the management of WC and financial leverage of small businesses suggests further investigation in this context.

This study further investigates the effect of profitability of a firm on WCM. There is strong evidence (Atseye et al., 2015; Garg, 2015; Padachi and Afrifa, 2016; Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016) to suggest that WCM practice has a very strong impact on liquidity and profitability of an organization. However, other researchers (Alsie and Arora, 2016; Lyngstadaas and Berg, 2016; Azami and Tabar, 2016), supported a negative association between the components of WCM and profitability of SMEs. Therefore, this study analysed whether WCM components, including accounts receivable period, accounts payable period, and inventory holding period, affect small food restaurants in the UK either positively or negatively.

A few studies (Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Afrifa and Tingbani, 2018) have been carried out in the UK context. Previous research (Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016) investigated working capital management of small UK businesses, though detailed study on the external and internal factors that specifically influence the level of WCM in UK small food restaurants is still lacking. Therefore, this study will examine the factors that contribute towards WC investment from the UK perspective. The investigation of factors influencing WCM practices in the UK context is one of the motivating factors for this study.

Some thought and literature (Atseye et al., 2015; Sadiq, 2017) **regarding** WCM and small business in the UK (Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013; Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa, 2016) has identified that the failure rate of WCM practices is very high due to the factors associated with WCM practices. Nonetheless, study on determining the factors influencing WCM practices, particularly in small food restaurants, is still lacking. Although the magnitude of WCM by small businesses has motivated many researchers (Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014; Atseye et al., 2015) to evaluate various determinants of WCM, opinion as to the correlation between WC requirements and variables such as managerial competencies, size, leverage, profitability, etc. has been divided. Therefore, it is important to **categorize** whether the above variables might have a different effect on small food restaurants in the UK. Due to the literature gap regarding small business management, this study intended to examine the aforesaid area in the UK context. The disclosure of this knowledge gap is the focus of this study. A research study in the aforesaid area, if thoroughly examined, will disclose the internal factors that affect the WC requirement of small restaurant firms. Consequently, small food restaurants will be able to maintain an optimal level of WC. These findings can be deeply rooted in empirical evidence as these findings will add additional value to future research.

Chapter 4

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

4.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to design and develop an appropriate methodology. According to Bryman and Bell (2011), the term ‘methodology’ denotes the way in which research is required to be undertaken. Research methodology is a very systematic manner of conducting research (Achari, 2014). The purpose of the research is to identify answers to research questions through the application of appropriate methods. This section provides a comprehensive introduction to the research design and method followed for this study. The philosophy used in this research influences the choice of research methods. Therefore, the next section (4.2) covers discussion on mixed methods as a ‘third methodological movement’.

Section 4.3 discusses the philosophical underpinnings of the research. This chapter explains the choice of methods and justification for choosing a mixed approach (4.4), research design and strategy (4.5) and the data collection methods (4.7). Section 4.8 explains the mixed data analysis: qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods. The validity, generalizability, and credibility of the mixed data of the research are discussed in section 4.9. The next sections articulate the research methods and philosophy that have been followed in this study.

4.2. MIXED METHODS AS A ‘THIRD METHODOLOGICAL MOVEMENT’

Mixed methods research formally began in the late 1980s (McKim, 2015; Molina-Azorin, 2016) and promoted a separate design period from the 2000s (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Prior to that, researchers used quantitative, qualitative, or multiple methods to describe their study titles and methods. According to Bazeley (2019), quantitative approaches to research include descriptive, experimental, and correlational methodologies. Quantitative methods focus on quantities and use mathematics or statistics for analysis. Qualitative approaches include grounded theory, ethnography, and phenomenology, and therefore generally employ text, audio, or visual data with a variety of methods for analysis. Bazeley (2019) identified acrimonious arguments across qualitative and quantitative methods based on fundamentally different ontological (nature of reality) and epistemological (justifiable knowledge) assumptions that prevented their

combinations. The debates and the paradigm wars associated with mixed approaches were eventually resolved by the rediscovery of pragmatism as a philosophical basis of mixed methods research. As a methodology, mixed methods involves philosophical assumptions that combine quantitative and qualitative approaches in a single study or series of studies for a better understanding of research problems (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018) than a purely quantitative or purely qualitative study (McKim, 2015).

Prominent writers and theorists of mixed methods have emerged, and conceptual evolution of the methods is being used by a growing number of scholars (Cameron and Molina-Azorin, 2011; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Bazeley, 2019). The widespread adoption of mixed methods across the social and behavioural sciences has been described as ‘a third methodological movement’ (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Bazeley, 2019). However, early adopters of mixed methods embraced the risk of laying the ground open for subsequent followers (Cameron and Molina-Azorin, 2011). Conducting a mixed methods study requires additional time, resources, and expertise to collect and analyse two different types of data (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). In this research, the researcher has used embedded open-ended questions within a quantitative survey to collect both qualitative and quantitative data in a single phase. Furthermore, the researcher was required to seek out support mechanisms such as Web resources and software training such as NVivo workshops to cover the complex elements of qualitative and quantitative approaches. However, it was worth overcoming these limitations of mixed methods as the combination of open-ended and closed-ended questions provides a complete understanding of the internal factors affecting the working capital management of small restaurants (Bazeley, 2019). The researcher developed a broader set of skills (Molina-Azorin, 2016) and found a new way to answer the research questions.

4.3. PHILOSOPHICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF THE RESEARCH

Blaxer (2010) identified that methodology has a more philosophical meaning. Understanding philosophical assumptions is important before choosing and designing research methods. Stokes and Wall (2014) says that research philosophies underpin the research strategy and research methods. Philosophical assumptions are adopted and shaped through the belief of a scholar and the way they understand the world. Every research method has its own ontology (the what), epistemology (the how), and axiology (the why) that eventually form a research paradigm. Ontological considerations deal with the subjective or objective nature of reality. Meanwhile, epistemological considerations focus on the path or drivers that cause knowledge (Stokes, 2011). Saunders et al. (2015) stated that axiology focuses on what researchers value in their research. Pragmatists adopt both objective and subjective points of view; therefore, values play a large role in interpreting data.

Saunders et al. (2015) further mentioned that there are four types of research philosophies, namely positivism, interpretivism, realism, and pragmatism. These assumptions underpin research strategy and the methods researchers choose as part of their strategy.

Bazeley (2019) argued that researchers' epistemological and ontological assumptions influence, but do not necessarily limit, the choices they make about research methods. One might adopt a pragmatic assumption that combines methods. Pragmatists believe that it is appropriate to work with variations in epistemology, ontology, and axiology (Saunders et al., 2015). This research intended to identify the internal factors affecting WCM of small restaurants by combining both positivist and interpretivist epistemologies. The researcher accepts both observable facts and subjective meanings as knowledge. Saunders et al. (2015) identified that the research problem or question is the most important determinant of the epistemology, ontology, and axiology. One may be more appropriate than the other for answering a question. In this study, pragmatic philosophy has been chosen to achieve complete knowledge of the internal factors of WCM. The following section articulates the positivist and interpretivist paradigm and justification for choosing pragmatism over the other philosophies.

4.3.1. POSITIVIST AND INTERPRETIVIST PARADIGMS

As stated by Brannen (2016), two distinct paradigms are quantitative and qualitative paradigms. Differences between the two paradigms are based on their epistemological and methodological underpinnings. Epistemological assumptions focus on either positivism or interpretivism. Positivist researchers prefer working with observable social reality and hypothesis development based on existing theory (Stokes and Wall, 2014). Therefore, positivism is most often associated with quantitative research. Realism is like positivism as this philosophy assumes a scientific approach to the development of knowledge. Development of knowledge and nature of reality are influenced by the ways a researcher understands the world (Bazeley, 2019). Epistemological assumptions are interconnected with ontological assumptions. Ontologically, positivist researchers believe in an objective reality of physical, mental, or social phenomena. The world is objectively real to them. As a result, positivists are compatible with realism (Stokes, 2011). The positivist paradigm is also called the scientific paradigm (Mack, 2010). Bryman (2015) noted that positivists are likely to use existing theory to develop hypotheses. Tested and confirmed hypotheses then lead to the further development of theory by future research (Saunders et al., 2015).

Interpretivists on the other hand focus on subjectivity (Stokes and Wall, 2014). Interpretivism opposes the positivism of natural science, and is therefore compatible with subjectivity and relativism ontology (Stokes, 2011). Epistemological perspectives on what counts as knowledge are considered as a social development involving individuals' points of view and investigating the social world. Consequently, a different paradigm is required to understand that humans are distinct from the natural order (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This type of philosophy is associated with qualitative methods of data collection such as participant observations or similar material recording participant perspectives (Bazeley, 2019). Interpretivists rely on a subjective relationship with the subjects. Debate based on philosophical assumptions among scholars is often framed in relation to a choice between positivism and interpretivism. Many interpretivists oppose the benefits of positivism as positivist researchers always assume the objectivity of a social reality; therefore, there is no absolute objectivity (Mark, 2010). On the other hand, an interpretivist perspective is highly appropriate for business and management research (Saunders et al., 2015). However, the challenge here is entering the social world and understanding the feelings of social actors from their own points of view. Pragmatism as a standpoint was developed to bridge the gap between positivism and interpretivism (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Bazeley, 2019).

4.3.2. PRAGMATISM AS THE RESEARCH PARADIGM

The research philosophy of this study is pragmatist as the researcher focused on both the positivist and interpretivist paradigms. Pragmatists gain knowledge regardless of the methods used; therefore, different knowledges of a phenomenon are equally truthful to each knowledgeable person (Bazeley, 2019). In this study, the researcher combined both philosophical traditions, each with an epistemology that embraces both qualitative and quantitative methods. By embracing both qualitative and quantitative forms of data, the researcher can gain better insights into the factors associated with the WCM of small restaurants.

Previous research (Muhammad and Elias, 2013; Afrifa, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Fatimatuzzahra and Kusumastuti, 2016; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018) on WCM adopted the principles of positivism. On the other hand, Orobio et al. (2013) conducted a qualitative inquiry on the management of working capital of small businesses operating in an emerging economy. As no single point of view can ever give the whole picture (Saunders et al., 2015; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018), in this study both objective aspects of WCM and opinions of managers are considered. In addition, recently, mixed methods has become a more widely recognized approach that brings benefits for

business and management practitioners (Bazeley, 2019), particularly for those researchers who continually try to add value and gain a better understanding of increasingly complex business and management phenomena (Cameron and Molina-Azorin, 2011). Therefore, this research philosophy reflects the principles of pragmatism. Information on internal factors such as business size, management competencies, leverage, and profitability are collected based on objective evidence as well as the opinions and feelings of owner-managers. The researcher followed a mixed approach by mixing both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The next section articulates the reasons behind choosing a mixed research approach.

4.4. RESEARCH APPROACH

In scientific research, two approaches are usually adopted such as an inductive approach and a deductive approach (Bryman, 2008; Saunders et al., 2015). In this research, a mixed methods approach is adopted for gaining better understanding of the research problems (Evankova et al., 2006). The following sub-sections of this section explain the differences between deductive and inductive approaches in detail and the justifications for choosing a mixed approach for this study.

4.4.1. DEDUCTIVE AND INDUCTIVE APPROACHES

A deductive approach underpins positivist philosophy (Stokes, 2011); therefore, it tends to employ quantitative data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). According to Creswell (2014), philosophical standpoints, research strategies, and the methods all contribute to a research approach that tends to be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed. A quantitative approach focuses on testing a theory deductively. Conversely, an inductive approach is more linked to interpretivism and has an emphasis on qualitative data. A qualitative approach allows inductive reasoning and is therefore based on qualitative data, e.g. observations (Bryman and Bell, 2015). According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), mixed methods involves philosophical assumptions that focus on collecting, analysing, and mixing both qualitative and quantitative approaches in a single study. Mixed methods research helps restaurant managers to answer questions that cannot be answered by a single method. This method is useful to obtain detailed information (Blaxer et al., 2006) about WCM practices in the small food restaurants. The quantitative approach helps the researcher to describe the internal factors effecting WCM and the qualitative approach adds value to the findings by explaining the

factors of WCM in small restaurants (Bazeley, 2019). The following section provides the justification for choosing a mixed methods approach in this research.

4.4.2. JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING A MIXED RESEARCH APPROACH

Evidence suggests that the volume of research on WCM has been undertaken by using quantitative approaches (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Louw and Hall, 2016; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Muhammad and Manoori, 2012; Agyei-Mensah, 2012). Large numbers of quantifiable data were identified by using quantitative questionnaires. However, a criticism of this approach is that quantitative questionnaires do not require understanding on WCM from the informants' perspective (House, 2018). Therefore, a quantitative approach does not provide deep and comprehensive understanding of WCM. Orobio et. al (2016) undertook a research study on WCM practices in small businesses by using a survey questionnaire. However, the need for a qualitative approach is evident. A qualitative approach would have informed the reasons why owner-managers of small businesses held certain views. On the other hand, Orobio et al. (2013) identified the WCM of 10 small business owners by adopting an interpretivist methodological approach in Uganda. Even though this qualitative approach provided in-depth knowledge of the WCM of small businesses, generalization of the findings was restricted due to the small sample size. Most of the previous research (Afrifa, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Fatimatuzzahra and Kusumastuti, 2016; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018) followed a quantitative approach. Consequently, the small sample of 10 participants was not large enough to compare the results with previous research in the similar area of WCM and small businesses.

In this research mixed methods are followed by collecting data from 100 small restaurants through both close-ended and open-ended questions. The mixture of quantitative and qualitative approaches provides wider explanation of the internal factors affecting WCM and contributes towards the generalization of conclusions (Maxwell, 2016). Turner et al. (2017) stated that mixed methods are well-placed to contribute to generality. Furthermore, House (2018) argued that a large sample size produces reliable and replicable data. Mixed methods provide strengths to the weakness of quantitative and qualitative methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Even though previous research on WCM has been undertaken in the context of the UK, no research has yet followed mixed approaches to identify the internal factors of WCM (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016; Qurashi and Zahoor,

2017). Therefore, this study is unique as the combination of both quantitative and qualitative research design helps to collect rich data which is discussed in the next sections.

4.5. RESEARCH STRATEGY

Achari (2014) stated that research design requires a choice of research strategy. Experiment, survey, action research, cross section, case study, and comparative are some of the common methods of research strategy (Achari, 2014; Bryman and Bell, 2011). In this study, a case study strategy of small restaurants is embedded within the survey strategy for the deep understanding of the problem (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders et al., 2016). The next sections depict the survey and case study strategies and justifies the use of mixed strategies in this research.

4.5.1. SURVEY STRATEGY

Referring to survey strategy, Bryman and Bell (2015) say that survey is an effective strategy to collect data from many respondents in a low-cost and time-effective way. Survey strategy was identified by Saunders et al. (2016) as a popular and common strategy in business and management research. In this study, the researcher collected quantitative data on the internal factors affecting WCM of 100 small restaurants in the UK by using survey questionnaires. It would have been difficult for the researcher to collect data from 100 small restaurants in the UK within the limited time available for this research. Survey questionnaires are valued for capturing many responses in minimum time (Bazeley, 2019). Therefore, survey strategy allows the collection of large and reliable data in a highly economical way compared to case studies. Saunders et al. (2016) argued that survey questionnaires offer only one chance to pull data together and so it is difficult to gather additional data and problems. Therefore, in this study, a case study approach can provide a supportive role to the quantitative questions (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007).

4.5.2. CASE STUDY

A case study refers to a research strategy where data is gathered from a group, industry, or a situation (Bryman and Bell, 2015). As stated by Saunders et al. (2016), in-depth investigation of an industry produces rich descriptive data. In-depth inquiry needs to understand the effects of the situation and implications for action. Therefore, case study research can be designed either within a quantitative or qualitative or mixed methods approach, to understand the dynamics of the case. In this study a case of the small restaurant industry

was chosen for in-depth understanding of the internal factors of WCM. Case study produced rich descriptive data and helped the researcher to investigate the factors of WCM in small food restaurants more accurately and deeply (Blaxer, 2010; Saunders et al., 2015). The next section justifies the reason for embedding a case study approach in the survey strategy.

4.5.3. JUSTIFICATION FOR EMBEDDING CASE STUDY STRATEGY IN THE SURVEY STRATEGY

In this study, a case study of small restaurants is embedded within the survey strategy by administering questionnaires for the deep understanding of the problem (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This section justifies the use of embedded mixed strategy in this research. Case study strategy has been used in some previous studies (Darun, 2011; Afrifa et al., 2014). However, one of the criticisms of case study is attempting to ensure accuracy at the cost of generality (Woodside, 2010). Afrifa et al. (2013) investigated the effect of WCM on the performance of AIM-listed SMEs over an eight-year period (2007-2014). They followed a case study strategy, which therefore cannot be generalized beyond AIM. Analysis of such a large amount of data required a longer period and higher cost. A questionnaire survey could have alleviated the problem. A survey strategy would have been more appropriate to gather a large amount of data in a low-cost and time-effective way (Bazeley, 2019). Previous research used survey strategy (Baker, 2017). However, survey strategy has been criticized for lack of in-depth understanding. In addition, this method offers only one chance to pull data together, and therefore it is difficult to gather additional data and problems (Saunders et al., 2016). Consequently, a fixed-point scale survey restricts human judgement (Woodside, 2010). The cost of administering a questionnaire over an extended period could outweigh the benefits. As a result, bridging the gap between case study and survey is important for fulfilling generality of findings and achieving accuracy of the outcomes (Woodside, 2010).

In this study the researcher combined survey questions and open-ended questions to bridge the gap between case study and survey strategies. Similarly, a previous study (Oseifuah, 2016) used mixed strategies to analyse the key factors influencing WC requirements of five listed non-financial firms by combining Likert scales and open-ended questions. However, results cannot be generalized from a case of five non-financial firms. Further, deep insights into the internal factors of WCM cannot be identified by using positivistic tools. Embedding a questionnaire survey could have alleviated the problem.

Time was a concern for this study as the questionnaire survey has been administered for only eight months. It would have been difficult for the researcher to collect large amount of data within the limited time available for this research. Therefore, in this research, a combination of Likert scale and open-ended questions were asked to investigate the internal factors affecting WCM of 100 small restaurants in a low-cost and time-effective way (Saunders et al., 2016; Bazeley, 2019). Survey questionnaires are valued for capturing many responses in minimum time (Bazeley, 2019). Furthermore, open-ended answers can provide a supportive role to the quantitative questions (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007) without restricting human judgement (Woodside, 2010). In this study, a case study strategy of small restaurants is embedded within the survey strategy not only for deep understanding of the problem (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders et al., 2016) but also for fulfilling generality of findings and achieving accuracy of the outcomes (Woodside, 2010; Bazeley, 2019).

4.6. RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the process of building a structure or plan of a research (Leavy, 2017). Before conducting a study, researchers mostly plan their research at the level of methods, methods of data collection, and the process of data analysis. The distinctions are mostly found in term of research design. Generally, there are three types of research design: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed design (Gibson, 2017). Both quantitative and qualitative design belong to distinctively different paradigms (Barren, 2016); therefore they follow different methods for data collection and analysis. As stated by House (2018), quantification is not only a feature of quantitative research but also a feature of qualitative study. Inductively gained categories are also quantifiable, and therefore open for statistical use. As a result, many studies combine quantitative and qualitative designs within a single piece of research (Barren, 2016; Bazeley, 2019; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). The following sections depict the main distinctions that differ between the quantitative and qualitative paradigms, fruitfulness and non-fruitfulness of quantitative and qualitative design, the importance of stressing the non-fruitfulness of the quantitative-qualitative dichotomy and justifications of combining the two designs in a mixed methods design.

4.6.1. QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH DESIGN

According to Yilmaz (2013), quantitative and qualitative research designs differ in terms of their epistemological, theoretical, and methodological underpinnings. Quantitative design is informed by

objectivist epistemology. This approach endorses the view that social phenomena have an objective reality. Researchers following quantitative design seek to develop measurable (observable) facts, assuming that measurable statistical data describes the objective reality of the subjects being observed and measured (Bazeley, 2019). Therefore, the knower (researcher) and the knowledge (subjects) are independent. Quantitative research is generally associated with positivism. Therefore, a deductive approach is followed to develop a theory, where the focus is on using data to test theory. Researchers following this design may use a single method or multiple methods to collect data. For example, quantitative data can be collected by using both questionnaires and structured observation (Saunders et al., 2016). According to Yilmaz (2013), quantitative design involves survey, questionnaires, and systematic measurements involving numbers. Quantitative research design uses graphs, mathematical models, and statistical techniques to analyse the data numerically. This design generally demands randomly selected large samples to generalize the findings from the samples. Quantitative research allows the researcher to involve many participants within a limited time, which is a major advantage of this approach. As stated by House (2018), the quantitative research method focuses on the development of generalizable regularities and rules; therefore, data is considered reliable and replicable. However, the quantitative method and procedure allow the researcher to identify a broad and generalizable set of findings, but they fail to provide deep insight into the participants' opinions, feelings, thoughts, and experiences (Yilmaz, 2013).

4.6.2. QUALITATIVE RESEARCH DESIGN

Qualitative research design is based on a different paradigm which requires the understanding that humans are distinct from the natural order (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The epistemological perspective on what counts as knowledge is considered as a social development involving individuals' points of view and investigating the social world. As a result, the qualitative paradigm views a direct relation between the researcher and the subjects as an in-depth description of the phenomenon from the perspectives of the people involved (Yilmaz, 2013). The researcher seeks to understand the meaning of social, mental, and physical phenomena through interaction with those phenomena (Bazeley, 2019). Knowledge can only be obtained, therefore, directly from the subjective relationship with the subjects.

This type of design is associated with qualitative methods of data collection, which include (but are not limited to) participant observations, in-depth interviews, focus groups, or similar material recording participant perspectives (Yilmaz, 2013; Bazeley, 2019). Open-ended responses assist the researcher to understand the world as it is experienced by the participants without predetermining those feelings,

experiences, and thoughts. The purpose of qualitative design is to study a small group of participants or unique cases for the identification of detailed information and in-depth understanding of the phenomena. However, Yilmaz (2013) argued that the researcher follows this design uses a small sampling procedure, therefore limiting the possibility of generalizing research findings to other situations. Qualitative research design, e.g. in-depth interviews, can draw upon a quantitative numerical inquiry. Similarly, questionnaires and structured interviews can be used to explore theory. House (2018) said that integrating quantitative and qualitative research provides a better understanding of a research problem. There is a need for the awareness of the relative fruitfulness and non-fruitfulness of the quantitative and qualitative design. The next sections articulate the mixed research design and the justifications for mixing two different designs for this study.

4.6.3. MIXED METHODS RESEARCH DESIGN

As stated by Bazeley (2019), building a design framework serves as a guide for carrying out a mixed methods study as mixed methods studies are inherently more complex than a single method study. Three key dimensions that have been identified in mixed methods design are timing in data collection, dominance given to either quantitative or qualitative approaches, and the theoretical drive of the study. Molina-Azorin (2016) emphasized two dimensions: priority and implementation of data collection that determine the type of mixed methods design for a study. Regarding priority, the researcher can give equal priority to both quantitative and qualitative methods or emphasize either a quantitative or qualitative method. Implementation of data collection refers to the sequence of data collection. This option creates further designs such as concurrent design and sequential design. Researchers can gather the information at the same time by following a concurrent design of mixed methods or may seek to compare different methods by introducing data in two distinct phases. This sequence of data collection mostly depends on the objectives of the study. For example, when the quantitative phase precedes the qualitative phase, the researcher may intend to test a large data set and then to explore in more depth with qualitative data (Molina-Azorin, 2016).

Furthermore, referring to the timing of data collection and the priority given to approaches, Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) suggested three main design prototypes: the convergent parallel design, explanatory sequential design, and the exploratory sequential design. Variations of these three primary designs create further options. Quantitative and qualitative data strands are given equal priority and are collected concurrently in the convergent parallel design. However, parallel design creates further options either to compare findings, or to complement one method or both.

Sequential design is common in business studies, with a quantitative phase preceding the qualitative phase, or vice versa. In a sequential design the collection and analysis of one type of data occurs after the collection and analysis of another type. Even though several methodologists (Molina-Azorin, 2016; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018) have attempted to develop typologies based on intersecting the two or perhaps three of these above different dimensions in design, Bazeley (2019) argued researchers should not be limited to thinking in terms of the above three designs. These typologies list and classify options for the researcher, although they cannot capture the wide variety of mixed methods studies. Gibson (2017) observed innovative combination as a possible design model and emphasized the potential for wide variation in mixed methods design, with relevance to business and management studies.

In this research, an embedded mixed methods design is followed. In embedded design, data is collected concurrently, but with one method dominant (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). A qualitative method is embedded as a supplement to a larger data set which is quantitative in this research. Embedded design is a single-phase design where the researcher embeds a qualitative strand within a primary quantitative design which helps to explore the reliability and validity of initial quantitative data (Creswell and Clark, 2018). In this research, both qualitative and quantitative data are collected in a single phase.

4.6.4. JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING EMBEDDED MIXED DESIGN

The justification of the research design and strategy adopted mostly depend on the research aims and objectives. The main aim of this research is to evaluate the internal factors affecting WCM of small food restaurants. In this research, data is collected concurrently, but with one method dominant (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). There is strong evidence (Afrifa, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Fatimatu Zahra and Kusumastuti, 2016; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018) to suggest that the research problem in WCM is more quantitatively oriented. Therefore, quantitative research design is the grounding for this research. In this research the quantitative data type is given more priority than the qualitative type; therefore the researcher does not have enough resources to commit to extensive qualitative data collection.

Quantitative data is collected based on the internal factors affecting WCM in small food restaurants. The main purpose of quantitative research design is to quantify data from the population of interest by the application of statistical interpretations. The major advantage of quantitative research is that a wide range of data can be collected from many respondents (Leavy, 2017). However, Woodside (2010) argued that bridging

the chasm between case study and survey is important for fulfilling generality of findings and achieving accuracy of the outcomes. The purpose of embedding open-ended questions in the same set of questionnaires is to identify if there are any other internal factors effecting the WCM of small restaurants. The four internal factors asked about in the closed-ended questions may not be internal factors for some small businesses. Therefore, combination of the results from quantitative and qualitative data helps the researcher to identify a complete and accurate answer to the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007).

4.7. METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The following sections describe the research population, research sample and justification for choosing a simple random sample.

4.7.1. PILOT STUDY

The researcher conducted a pilot study to test the questionnaires in term of ambiguity, understanding of questions, and communication between researcher and participants. Smail (2018) explained the pilot study as a strategy that is used to test a smaller sample size before conducting the actual larger sample size. Bryman and Bell (2011) suggest that pre-testing a questionnaire allows the researcher to determine the adequacy of instructions to participants completing questionnaires. However, Ismail (2018) argued that a pilot study is always based on a small number of participants and therefore the reliability of findings is limited. In this study, questionnaires were distributed to a pilot sample of six owner-managers of small food restaurants in the UK due to time limitations. However, this mini version of the actual large study enabled the researcher to identify whether the structure of the questions was simple and unambiguous to participants. Six restaurant owner-managers with expertise in restaurant management revised and accepted the appropriateness of the questionnaires. The researcher incorporated relevant suggestions from owner-managers prior to use. The final reviewed questionnaire was sent to all 100 UK small food restaurants participating in the study.

4.7.2. RESEARCH POPULATION AND SAMPLING

Bryman (2016) says the population is the universe of units from which a sample is selected. Universe units means the universe of nations, cities, and firms, etc. Thus, the sample is the segment of the population that is selected for research. In mixed methods research, combining different sampling strategies further complicates the integrating (Bazeley, 2018). Different samples in mixed methods can be combined in four

primary ways to facilitate the integration of results: identical, parallel, nested, and multilevel (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). In this study, nested design is followed to combine qualitative sampling and quantitative sampling. However, in embedded (nested) mixed design one data type is given less priority than the other (Morse and Niehaus, 2009). In this study, data is collected concurrently, but with quantitative methods dominant (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018); therefore, sampling for quantitative research is followed.

According to Bryman (2016), in quantitative research probability or non-probability sampling is used. The simple random sample is the most basic form of random sample. A sample of 100 small food restaurants that met the definition of small business as defined by the UK Companies Act 2006 (sections 382 and 465) were selected randomly in this research. The researcher used a computer-based random number calculator. The sample size helped the researcher to have information from a well-defined sample size rather than very large or very small (Blaxer, 2010). According to Saunders et al. (2015), simple random sampling helps to collect bias-free information compared with non-probability sampling. In non-probability sample selection, human judgement affects the selection process (Bryman, 2016). Simple random sampling gives equal opportunity to each sample being selected. Mixed method collection of quantitative and qualitative data can be a rigorous and time-consuming process, but Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) suggested that an embedded model of design is less time-consuming. For this study, the researcher used the same sample to collect both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time in the same visit to the field. Simple random sampling was used for the open-ended questions. Simple random sampling provides the most authentic and reliable information for the study (Bryman, 2016). A copy of the questionnaires used has been included in Appendix F. The following section discusses the data collection techniques and the design of the questionnaires in more detail.

4.7.2.1. JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING SIMPLE SIZE AND RANDOM SAMPLE

Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) emphasized the importance of appropriate sample sizes for mixed methods as it determines the extent of statistical and analytic generalization of a research study. In this study the data sample is composed of approximately 100 small food restaurants in the UK. It is comparable to similar studies by Javid (2014); Muhammad and Elias (2013); Mohamad et al. (2017); Gorondutse et al. (2017), with sample sizes of 54 SMEs, 150 public listed companies between 2002 to 2011, 103 SMEs 2008 to 2013, and 66 SMEs between 2006 and 2012 respectively. The choice of different sample sizes was influenced by different time periods. However, these studies adopted only quantitative approaches; therefore their sample sizes should be large. Although a large sample being associated with a quantitative approach represents the most common way of linking sample size research paradigm, this representation is too simplistic and

misleading (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) argued that there are times when it is appropriate to use a small sample in quantitative research, e.g. exploratory basic research, and large samples can be linked to qualitative research, e.g. in the case of program evaluation research. However, this study adopted mixed approaches; therefore, a qualitative approach was combined with quantitative to provide a supportive role (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Therefore, side-stepping too small or too large a sample size was appropriate to justify the most suitable sample size of 100 food restaurants for this study.

In addition, the previous studies on WCM were undertaken over an extended period. Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam (2013) analysed 192 companies for 8 years and Elbadry (2018) investigated 138 SMEs for four years. In this study, data is collected on a weekly basis over a six to eight-month period. In an embedded mixed study the researcher has insufficient time and resources to commit to extensive data collection (Morse and Niehaus, 2009). Therefore, the researcher found two useful criteria in selecting sample size and design: time orientation (concurrent) and relationship of the qualitative and quantitative samples (nested) (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). Therefore, a sample of 100 small businesses was appropriate for a short timeframe.

100 small food restaurants participated in the questionnaire, which contains both closed and open-ended responses. Large restaurants are excluded; this is because large and small-size businesses require different amounts of WC (Hill et al., 2010). Small businesses have limited access to capital through external financing (Zariyawati et al., 2016; Wapshott and Mallett, 2018). The analysis of the factors influencing the requirements of WCM of a large business would be different than that of a small business because of their different financial structures and access to capital markets. Consequently, including large-size food restaurants would bias the results.

4.7.2.2. JUSTIFICATION FOR HOMOGENEOUS SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS AND MULTINATIONAL CULTURAL DIVERSITY

Small restaurants operating in the UK share multinational cultural diversity. As a result, to confirm the robustness of the results, homogeneous samples were chosen randomly from the small food restaurants. Simple random sampling was appropriate for this study as the entire population of small food restaurants from which the random sample was taken shares similar employment. Research samples are homogeneous in nature as restaurants' main product is food and respondents' (owner-managers) roles are similar in managing working capital.

4.7.3. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

Collection and analysis of mixed methods data usually take longer than expected as more than one form of data is being sought (Bazeley, 2019). This study was undertaken within a short period compared with previous studies (Javid, 2014; Muhammad and Elias, 2013; Mohamad et al., 2017). In this study, data is collected on a weekly basis over a six to eight-month period. Therefore, a questionnaire was used to gather both quantitative and qualitative data. The questionnaires together with participant information forms and consent sheets were sent to 100 small restaurants in the UK. A copy of the questionnaire, participant information and consent sheets can be found in Appendix F. The questionnaire was designed for mixed data collection to allow enough time for analysis and writing (Bazeley, 2019). The next section expands on the design of questionnaires. In this study, information from various secondary sources such as websites, journals, and textbooks are collected (Saunders et al., 2015). This is beneficial not only in making critical analysis of past data, but also in comparing current and past data on working capital. In addition, secondary data saves time and costs as these have already been collected by other researchers.

4.7.3.1. THE DESIGN OF QUESTIONNAIRES AND GATHERING MIXED METHODS DATA

The primary data collection is intended to contribute towards identifying the factors influencing WCM of small food restaurants to facilitate the evaluation of research aims and objectives. Internal factors, such as a firm's size (Azeem and Marsap, 2015), leverage (Azami and Tabar, 2016), profitability (Atseye et al., 2015), managerial competencies, e.g. financial knowledge (Agyei-Mensah, 2012), financial training and skills (Orobia et al., 2016), work experience (Afrifa, 2013), etc. are determinants of WCM. Gathering mixed methods data is a very time-consuming process as the sample size is big. As a result, collecting data from 100 restaurants is further complicated in this regard (Bazeley, 2019). Therefore, mixed questionnaires were distributed to all participants as it is cheaper and quicker than interviews (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Bryman and Bell (2015) described mixed questionnaires as a blend of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. The mixed questionnaire for this study contains 21 questions, divided into three sections. In the quantitative section, questions A1-A5 are about participants and their role in the restaurants. Section B includes eight (B1-B8) Likert-scale questions on the internal factors affecting WCM in small restaurants. In question B1 respondents were asked about the extent of WCM in their restaurants by using a four-level rating scale: to a high extent, to some extent, not at all, do not know. In questions B3-B8, the Likert scale was restricted to six categories: Strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, strongly disagree, do not know. The

Likert scale was used to provide participants an opportunity to indicate the degree to which they agree or disagree with the internal factors that influence working capital management practice in their businesses (Saunders et al., 2015). To best answer the research question, this research included some open-ended questions in the qualitative or unstructured section seeking information on internal factors of WCM. Section C (C1-C4) includes open-ended questions allowing the researcher to further understand if there any other internal factor(s) that participants encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned in section B.

This study used mixed data collection techniques for gaining better understanding of the research problem while offsetting the weaknesses inherent in using only one approach (Evankova et al., 2006). According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), mixed methods provide strengths to the weakness of quantitative and qualitative methods. Therefore, in this research, the mixed methods approach is used to gather data, as gathering data by using different methods can be the key to further data collection and insightful analysis (Bazeley, 2019).

4.8. MIXED DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

As stated by Bazeley (2019), analysis is the critical examination and interrogation of data. In mixed methods study, analysis is supported by complementary, comparative, and transformative data conversion processes to facilitate data interpretations. In this study, analysis is supported by a complementary process where both qualitative and quantitative data are collected concurrently and merged. The purpose of embedding open-ended questions in the same set of questionnaires is to provide a supportive role to the closed-ended questions (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Furthermore, the embedded design of this study helped the researcher to anticipate the kinds of analysis strategies needed and to be aware of the skills required for the integration process (Bazeley, 2018). Information collected through closed-ended and open-ended questions is deliberately brought together during the process of analysis. According to Bazeley (2019) this the final key to integration in mixed data analysis. In this study the embedded nature occurs at design level. This section explains when and how mixing occurs in this study. Both quantitative and qualitative data are analysed separately by using appropriate software. Finally, the results from quantitative and qualitative analysis are combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). The following section discusses the kinds of data analysis strategies that are required for this study.

As stated by Bazeley (2019), data collected from mixed sources are inherently messy. Therefore, preliminary sorting, coding, and initial descriptive analysis of each set of data are needed to facilitate description, combination, and comparison. The researcher used multiple techniques so that more updated and correct data analysis is done using appropriate techniques. For instance, the researcher used statistical tools such as SPSS for quantitative data analysis and NVivo for thematic analysis of qualitative data. Bazeley (2018) noted that software, both quantitative and qualitative, assists the process of analysis, interpretation, and reporting by reducing the time needed to complete complex computations.

4.8.1. QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

IBM SPSS statistical software is a widely used statistical software for the management and analysis of quantitative data (Saunders et al., 2015; Bazeley, 2018). The numerical data collected from the respondents was placed in Excel sheets. Finally, the numbers were transferred to SPSS to test the data statistically. Quantitative data was analysed by using graphs, tables, and charts. In this section statistical tools such descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistical tools such as frequencies, percentages, and mean were used to analyse the questions included in section A (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Inferential statistical tools included Pearson correlation and regression analysis. For data analysis, this study used inferential statistical tools to test the hypotheses developed in chapter 2 (Saunders et al., 2016). The researcher identified the relationship between different factors and WCM practices by using inferential statistics such as Pearson correlation, OLR regression analysis, and chi-square etc. Similar studies that used these tools are Afrifa, 2013; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018; Muhammad and Elias, 2013; and Ndagijimana, and Okech, 2014.

4.8.1.1. DEPENDENT VARIABLES AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

To test the hypothesis developed in the previous chapter, the researcher used dependent and independent variables. According to Saunders et al. (2016), the use of dependent and independent variables assists in meeting the requirements of scientific lines of investigation. Therefore, the researcher used the requirements of WCM as the dependent variable. Independent variables revealed the level of variation in the dependent variable. The factors that accounted for variations in the requirements of WCM by the small food restaurants in the context of this research include management competencies, the size of business, leverage, and Profitability. Figure 3.1 below illustrates the dependent variable and independent variables.

Figure 3.1 Dependent and independent variables

4.8.1.2. CODING AND DUMMYING VARIABLES

For the quantitative analysis the researcher collapsed the dependent variable into two-level binary scales, e.g. Yes and No, to identify the requirements of WCM in small restaurants. In addition, a six-point Likert scale used in section B of the questionnaires was transformed into dummy variables to facilitate the regression analysis. However, this may lead to loss of information. (Micioiu and Atkinson, 2017). Therefore, to compensate for this loss of information, this study identified the descriptive statistics, e.g. frequencies and chi-square test (non-parametric), on the original ranking data.

4.8.2. QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

In this study textual data has been gathered from four open-ended questions. Bazeley (2018) identified that qualitative data analysis software (QDAS) has made the most remarkable contributions to the mixed method analysis. NVivo software assists integration through combination or comparison of different qualitative and quantitative data types in an analysis. Answers from the open-ended questions were first coded to identify relevant codes. The open codes were then collapsed into themes to detect similarities and differences among participants.

4.9. VALIDITY, RELIABILITY, GENERALIZABILITY, AND CREDIBILITY OF MIXED DATA

Referring to the quality of mixed method research (MMR), Johnson and Christensen (2017) stated that assessing the validity or trustworthiness criteria to the quantitative and qualitative phases is complex as it involves integration of two types data and analysis throughout the research design. This section explains the validity, reliability, generalizability, and credibility of mixed data.

4.9.1. RELIABILITY, INTERNAL VALIDITY, EXTERNAL VALIDITY, AND GENERALIZABILITY

According to Bryman and Bell (2015), reliability is basically concerned with the issues of consistency of measures. In this study, the researcher ensured that research is clear and transparent to another researcher (Stokes and Wall, 2014). Therefore, it was essential to calculate Cronbach's alpha coefficient for internal consistency reliability. Cronbach's alpha is a commonly used test of internal reliability (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The researcher used Cronbach's alpha to measure internal consistency reliability. The researcher collected information from managers of small food restaurants in the UK without any assumptions. Therefore, this information was collected from most reliable sources. As stated by Patino and Ferreira (2018), the validity of research data includes two domains: internal validity and external validity. Internal validity refers to the extent to which the results represent the truth within the population. Thus, internal validity detects the systematic error. This study used Pearson correlation to test the validity between variables. The researcher scrutinized the available information. To cover the validity of this study, findings were compared with previous literature to confirm the truth of the population, the accuracy, and the transparency of measures. External validity examines the generalizability of the results in real life (Patino and Ferreira, 2018). Generalization is the final phrase of the deductive process. Since this research collected samples

through a random sampling method, the findings are generalized to some extent. The sample is representative of the population; therefore, the findings can validly be generalized to the population (Andrade, 2018). After meeting all requirements, e.g. sample size and evaluating collected data thoroughly, it is important to generalize the findings. Therefore, comparative analysis of the results with previous research in the similar area of WCM and small business was conducted.

Figure 3.2 Internal and external validity; Source: Patino and Ferreira (2018)

4.9.2. CREDIBILITY AND DEPENDABILITY

The concept of validity does not work well in qualitative research (Lub, 2015). Internal and external validity represents a problem for qualitative research because of small sample sizes (Bryman and Bell, 2018). Qualitative researchers must examine their research validity. As a result, research validity has been labelled with alternative terms, such as credibility, dependability, and transferability, each of which has an equivalent criterion in quantitative research (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Interpretive validity focuses on providing accurate meanings to events, people, and behaviours that are being studied (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). Credibility, which parallels internal validity, represents the truth within the population. As stated by Bryman and Bell (2018), understanding of members of the social world is evident in the trustworthiness criterion of credibility.

This criterion is often referred to as respondent validation or member validation. Member validation is a process whereby a researcher provides participants with an account of their findings. Guba and Lincoln formulated procedures such as peer debriefing and member checking to increase the credibility of qualitative research. Creswell and Miller (2000) suggested that rich and thick description and member checking are easy and cost-effective procedures of validation. However, the actual validity procedures of member checking take time and energy (Lub, 2015). Member checking generally takes place several months after data collection. Therefore, for the timeframe of this study it was difficult to maintain this standard. In this study, the researcher used member checking, a qualitative technique to examine the credibility of the research. Even though the researcher was able to claim validity for quantitative data, examining the validity of the qualitative data was challenging due to subjectivity issues. As a parallel to reliability in quantitative study, Guba and Lincoln proposed the idea of dependability (Bryman and Bell, 2018). To demonstrate the trustworthiness and enhance the dependability of qualitative business research, auditing trail strategy was proposed by Guba and Lincoln (1985). Auditing ensures that complete accounts are kept of all stages of the data collection and analysis process including selection of research participants, interview transcripts, and data analysis decisions.

4.10 MISSING DATA CHECK AND CORRECTION

Valid and missing responses were checked in the findings and analysis chapter. No missing data were identified. All 72 respondents answered the research questionnaires. However, the researcher corrected some questionnaire values before conducting statistical analysis. To compare the mean values between variables, the researcher grouped the answers of question B1 (the extent of WCM) in the questionnaire into two categories. For those respondents who claimed to manage WC ‘to a high extent’ and ‘to some extent’, the researcher grouped them into the ‘Yes’ category. On the other hand, those participants who answered ‘Not at all’ and ‘do not know’, were modified with the ‘No’ category to facilitate statistical analysis. Similarly, another question (A1 in the questionnaires) about the educational qualifications of the respondents was edited into two groups such non-graduate owner-managers (GCSE and A level) and graduate (BA and MA) owner-managers. All 72 respondents answered the research questionnaires. Each answer was checked and corrected to eliminate errors from the collected data.

4.11 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Referring to ethical considerations, Bazeley (2019) said that ethical concerns are applicable to all research that connects either with human participants or institutions of which people are a part. As the research involves owners and managers of small food restaurants, the researcher followed ethical principles around conducting research with human participants. The most obvious principles and interrelated issues are minimizing the risk of harm, obtaining informed consent, (Appendix F), providing the right to withdraw from the study, maintaining confidentiality, respecting privacy, avoiding deceptive practices, and taking care in reporting (Bazeley, 2019).

The researcher followed the framework of ethical guidelines and procedures for research students of the University of the West of Scotland.

4.11.1 PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Participation in this research was voluntary. It was made clear that if participants do not want to carry on with the study, all the data collected to date would be destroyed and erased. Confidentiality was clearly explained in participant information sheets and consent forms. A copy of these forms can be found in the Appendix F. Owner-managers of small food restaurants were made fully aware of how privacy of the data would be maintained to protect the confidentiality and the anonymity of data. The researcher has followed the Data Protection Act 1998, to ensure that no law should be broken. The privacy of the participants was maintained by anonymizing the data through the coding process, so that participants and their organization cannot be identified. In addition, the researcher obtained the permission of respondents regarding the data usage accepted by the educational assessment board, to be used for publication, conference presentation, etc. Participants will not be identified in any report or publication. As stated by Bazeley (2019), for anonymous forms of data collection, e.g. questionnaires, signed permission from individual participants is not required. In this study, respondents implied their consent by returning completed questionnaires to the researcher.

4.11.2. BENEFITS AND HARM

Participants were provided with details of the study through information sheets explaining the purpose of the research, what participation in the research involves, how they would be benefited from the results and how data will be used. The researcher followed the ethical principle to minimize the risk of both psychological and physical harm to participants. No vulnerable participants were involved. Participants had no risk of compulsion or undue influence to take part in the research. The researcher followed non-maleficence and beneficence obligations of the research. Participation in this research is not going to risk the managers' ongoing employment in any way. After voluntary participation, they can withdraw from the study without consequences or loss of benefit to their future treatment by the researcher.

4.11.3 HONESTY AND INTEGRITY

The researcher followed Harvard referencing guidelines throughout the study to protect this paper from plagiarism. The researcher followed ethical guidelines in writing the research with honesty and integrity (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). The researcher provided information regarding the methodology used in collecting and analysing data as accurately as possible. This study used the contributions of the other researchers in the introduction and in the discussion section by giving authors' credits.

The next chapter covers the mixed data analysis and discussion on findings. Furthermore, the next chapter concentrates on the discussion of the statistical data analysis, hypothesis, answering research questions, and comparing findings back to literature (chapter two).

CHAPTER 5

QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND INFORMATION

The main objective of this research is to evaluate the internal factors affecting working capital management (WCM) of small food restaurants in the UK. This chapter covers the findings of questionnaires and the secondary data collected from previous research. Information collected through closed-ended and open-ended questions was brought together during the process of analysis. This is the final key to integration in mixed data analysis (Bazeley, 2019). In this chapter, the results from quantitative and qualitative analysis are combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). In the context of this study, approximately eight months was expended in the analysis of mixed data to ensure robustness of study. Identification of the factors and findings of data analysis can be used by the owners and managers of small restaurants in the UK to improve their WCM and financial performance.

To identify the research problem and the answers to the research question, findings and analysis were separated into two chapters: quantitative and qualitative findings, and discussion of the findings. This chapter covers the quantitative and qualitative findings and the next chapter (chapter six) analyses the results as set up in Figure 5.1. This chapter is divided into two main sections: quantitative findings and qualitative findings. To clarify the findings of the quantitative and qualitative data of the research questionnaires, it is important to restate the research questions and objectives in this chapter. As discussed in the previous chapter, this research investigates the determinants of working capital management (WCM) practices of small food restaurants in the UK and to develop a conceptual framework of the determinants' factors to enhance the financial performance of small restaurants in the UK. To find the appropriate answers to the above research question, the following sub-questions were identified in chapter one.

- i. Why do small restaurants manage working capital in their businesses in the UK?
- ii. What internal factors influence the requirements of WCM in small restaurants in the UK?
- iii. How do the internal factors influence the components of WCM in small restaurants in the UK?

iv. How might it be possible to develop a framework of the determinants' factors to enhance the financial performance of small restaurants the UK?

Objectives:

- Critical review of the concept of working capital management (WCM).
- To evaluate the internal factors effecting WCM of small food restaurants in the UK.
- To develop a framework of the determinants' factors of WCM for small food restaurants in the UK.

As mentioned earlier in chapter three, in this study, a case study of small food restaurants was embedded within the survey strategy by combining Likert-scale and open-ended questions. Section A of the questionnaire includes demographic information of the owner-managers. Section B contains Likert-scale questions to identify the answers to research questions (i) and (ii). And finally, respondents were asked open-ended questions in section C of the questionnaires to examine research question (iii). A copy of the questionnaire can be found in Appendix F. Both quantitative and qualitative data were analysed separately by using SPSS and NVivo software correspondingly. Preliminary sorting, coding, and initial descriptive analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data were needed to facilitate description, analysis, and interpretation. Finally, this chapter shows both quantitative and qualitative findings by using appropriate statistical tools and thematic analysis respectively. The next chapter outlines how quantitative and qualitative findings were combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Figure 5.1 summarizes the structure of findings and analysis for this study. The following sections discuss the results of the quantitative and qualitative data respectively.

Figure 5.1 The structure of findings and analysis

5.2. QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

In this section, the findings of quantitative data are presented. As stated in chapter three, the quantitative data from the survey questionnaires were collected from August 2019 to February 2020 in the UK. The questionnaire survey was preceded by a pilot study questionnaire sent to six restaurants included in the target sample of 100 food restaurants. Six restaurant owner-managers with expertise in restaurant management revised and accepted the appropriateness of the questionnaires. The final reviewed questionnaire was sent to all 100 small food restaurants in the UK. Out of 100 questionnaires, 72 questionnaires were returned, representing a 72% response rate. This sample size was comparable to similar studies involving questionnaire surveys of SMEs conducted by Afrifa (2013), Javid (2014) and Mohamad et al. (2017), with sample sizes of 72, 54, and 103 SMEs respectively.

In this study, quantitative data was analysed with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 25. IBM SPSS is one of the most widely used statistical software for the management and analysis of quantitative data (Saunders et al., 2015; Bazeley, 2018). In this section statistical tools such descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistical tools such as frequencies, percentages, bar charts, and pie charts were used to analyse the demographic data included in section A of the questionnaire. The researcher has identified relationships between different factors and WCM practices by using inferential statistics such as Pearson correlation coefficient, one-way ANOVA, chi-square, and regression analysis. Similar studies that used these tools are Afrifa, 2013; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018; Muhammad and Elias, 2013; Fatimatuzzahra and Kusumastuti, 2016; and Adekunle and Sunday, 2015. Baker et al. (2017) used chi-square and t-test to determine the effect of factors on the components of WCM. The structure of quantitative findings is as set up in Figure 5.2.

The following hypotheses were developed in chapter three to achieve the research objectives and the answer to the above research question (ii).

H₁: Management competencies are proportional to the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

H₂: The size of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants.

H₃: Leverage of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

H₄: The profitability of small food restaurants has a positive impact on the requirements of WCM.

FIGURE 5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF THE QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS

5.2.1. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

As mentioned above, 100 owner-managers of small food restaurants were asked the closed-ended questions (sections A and B of the questionnaire). During data collection, the target was to reach a rational number of small restaurants of the target sample. However, because of time limitations, only 72 owner-managers responded and returned questionnaires. In this section the researcher identified some general information related to the respondents. To process data, 72 valid questionnaires were applied (Table 5.2.2). The complete descriptive statistics of the results of percentages, bar charts (Figure 5.2.1) and pie charts (Figure 5.2.2) can be found in the following section.

5.2.1.1. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE FINDINGS

As mentioned above, a total of 72 owner-managers of small food restaurants answered the questionnaire, of which 5.6% were directors of their businesses. The following table (5.2.1) represents the demographic profiles of respondents in term of educational qualifications, types of business, number of employees, experience, and position of participants. Most of the participants (66.7 %) were managers and only 12.5% of the respondents were business owners, whereas 8.3% of the participants were managing both owner and management roles and 6.9% were working as partners. The demographic statistic reveals the types of small businesses that participated in the study. Half of the small restaurants were Limited Liability Company (LLC) (50%), 33.3% were sole proprietorship restaurants and only 16.7% were partnership restaurants. Qualifications of the owner-managers as reported in the above figure show that most of the owner-managers had completed GCSEs (62.5%), and 20.8% had finished A level. Only 9.7% had the highest qualification of Bachelor's degree and 6.9% respondents had achieved a Master's degree. A complete table of frequencies can be found in Appendix A.

Table 5.2.1. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Types of business enterprise	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sole proprietorship	24	33.3
Partnership	12	16.7
LLC	36	50
Total	72	100
Number of employees	Frequency	%
0-9	40	55.6
10-19	32	44.4
Total	72	100
Highest qualification	Frequency	%
GCSE	45	62.5
A level	15	20.8
BA	7	9.7
MA	5	6.9

Work experience	frequency	%
2	6	8.3
4	16	22.2
5	1	1.4
6	11	15.3
10	30	41.7
20	8	11.1
Total	72	100

Current position	frequency	%
Managers	48	66.7
Director	4	5.6
Owner	9	12.4
Owner-manager	6	8.3
Partner/managers	5	6.9
Total	72	100

The bar charts (Appendix A) and pie charts illustrate the results graphically. It is also evident from the bar chart that the participants were mostly managers. To make the analysis easier, the researcher modified the years of experience mentioned by the respondents slightly. In response to the question ‘How many years of experience in your current position?’, all respondents answered with different lengths of work experience. Thus, the researcher modified some numbers, if one number was smaller than or bigger than another number. The bar chart shows that the majority of

participants had 10 years of work experience (41.7%). Only 8.3% had 2 years of experience and 11.1% owner-managers were working in small food restaurants for 20 years. Orobia et al. (2016) identified that the owner-managers of small businesses get knowledge and skills on WCM through prior experience as opposed to the formal education system. Agyei-Mensah (2012) stated that work experience of managers is crucial to the effective management of WC.

Figure 5.2.2 Pie charts

The above pie charts visually represent the employee numbers in small food restaurants. The restaurants with employees between 10 and 19 were visually smaller than the small restaurants with employees between 0 and 9. The slice representing employee numbers between 10 and 19 was visually smaller than the slice representing employees between 0 and 9. The pie charts visually illustrate the highest qualifications of respondents. The largest slice in the pie chart shows GCSE level. Therefore, the majority of owner-managers had educational qualifications of GCSE level.

5.2.2. THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM IN SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS

As explained in the literature (chapter two), working capital management is crucial for small businesses (Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014; Mun and Jang, 2015; Atseye et al., 2015; Zariyawati et al., 2017; Louw et al., 2019). Restaurant businesses require an optimal level of working capital (Mun and Jang, 2015; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014). Zariyawati et al. (2017) confirmed the importance of inventories and cash receivables management in small businesses. On the other hand, Louw et al. (2019) confirmed the importance of inventory management and accounts payable management in the retail industry. Accounts receivable were found to be insignificant in the retail industry. An opposing point of consideration is that accounts receivable and accounts payable were most important, and inventory was found not to be important for SMEs (Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013). In the opinion of Mun and Jang (2015), the restaurant industry has a high level of accounts payable. The conflicting findings relating to the requirements of WCM in SMEs including small restaurants suggests that there is a requirement for further research. Based on the existing literature, the following section analyses the extent of WCM and its components in the context of small food restaurants in the UK.

5.2.2.1. THE EXTENT OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM)

This section analyses the extent of WCM in small food restaurants in the UK. The question was rated in scales as: ‘To a high extent’; ‘To some extent’; ‘Not at all’; and ‘Do not know’. In this section, the researcher used statistical tools such as frequency and chi-square tests. The frequency table 5.2.2 (a) provides the number of respondents and the percentage belonging to each of the Likert-scale variations in question (Bell et al., 2019). Furthermore, the chi-square test allowed the researcher to establish statistical association between the extent of working capital management by small restaurants based on the number of employees (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The complete table can be found in Appendix B.

TABLE 5.2.2 (A) THE EXTENT OF WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT (WCM)

To what extent does your restaurant manage WC?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
To a high extent	22	30.6
To some extent	45	62.5
Not at all	2	2.8
Do not know	3	4.2
Total	72	100.0
Valid		72
Missing		0
Mean		1.81

The above frequency table provides the statistics for valid values, missing values, frequency, and percentage of the extent of working capital management in small food restaurants. It shows that 22% of the total respondents agreed that their restaurants manage working capital to a high extent, whereas 45% of small restaurants manage WC to some extent. Only 2% responded to the question negatively. Furthermore, 3% of restaurants do not know the extent of working capital management in their businesses. The above results show that 45% of small restaurants manage WC to some extent and 5% of businesses do not know how to manage their WC. Therefore, the following section evaluates the requirements of WCM and its components in small restaurants.

TABLE 5.2.2. (B): CHI-SQUARE TEST: THE EXTENT OF WCM IN TERM OF NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES

Chi-square tests	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	12.567 ^a	3	.006
Likelihood ratio	14.567	3	.002
Linear-by-linear association	11.474	1	.001
N of valid cases	72		
a. 4 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .89.			

The chi-square value in Table 5.2.2 (b) is 12.567^a. This value means nothing on its own (Bryman and Bell, 2018). This value can be interpreted in relation to its association level $p = .006$ which indicates that two variables are positively correlated. Thus, there is positive relation between the extent of WCM and the number of employees in their businesses. The more a small business grows, the more important is working capital management.

5.2.2.2. INVENTORY, ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE, AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE

Literature on the requirements of WCM and its components suggests that inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable are useful for SMEs (Afrifa, 2013; Afrifa and Tauringana, 2013; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Zariyawati et al., 2017). As stated earlier, there are conflicting findings in respect to the WC components; this section analyses the requirement of WC components in small food restaurants. The complete frequency table can be found in Appendix B.

TABLE 5.2.2. (C): WCM COMPONENTS: INV, AR, AND AP

WCM Components	Priority	Frequency	Percent
Inventory (INV)	High priority	31	43.06%
	Moderate priority	38	52.78%
	Do not know	1	1.39%
	Low priority	1	1.39%
	Not a priority	1	1.39%
Accounts receivable (AR)	High priority	21	29.17%
	Moderate priority	37	51.39%
	Do not know	2	2.78%
	Low priority	6	8.33%
	Not a priority	6	8.33%
Accounts payable (AP)	High priority	30	41.67%
	Moderate priority	38	52.78%
	Do not know	1	1.39%
	Low priority	2	2.78%
	Not a priority	1	1.39%
All three components	High priority	21	29.2%
	Moderate priority	43	59.7%
	Do not know	5	6.9%
	Low priority	3	4.2%
Total		72.00	100%

The above frequency table analyses the extent of WCM and its components (INV, AR, and AP) in the context of small food restaurants in the UK. The researcher used requirements prioritization scales to analyse the requirement of WC components in small food restaurants. The question was rated in scales as: ‘high priority’; ‘moderate priority’; ‘do not know’, ‘low priority’, and ‘not a priority’. Percentages resulting from the descriptive analysis show that 43.06% of respondents agreed that inventory management is the highest priority component, 52.78% of owner-managers give moderate priority to the management of WC in their restaurants, and only 1.39% of respondents rated inventory management as ‘low priority’ and 1.39% as ‘not a priority’. Just 1.39% of respondents did not have knowledge on INV. Likewise, 29.17% of owner-managers agreed that AR management is the highest priority component, with 51.39% prioritizing moderately and 8.33% not prioritizing this component. Similarly, 41.67% of owner-managers give high priority to the management of accounts payable, while 52.78% agreed that AP management is the moderate priority component and 1.39% not prioritizing AP. Whereas, 2.78% owner-managers agreed that low priority is given to this component of WC in their businesses. Further it can be analysed from the above frequency table that in total (43+21) 64 owner-managers agreed with the statement that all three components, inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable, are useful for their small restaurants.

FIGURE 5.2.3: THE REQUIREMENT OF WC COMPONENTS IN THE SMALL FOOD RESTAURANTS

The above bar chart visually represents the extent of WC components INV, AR, and AP by small restaurants. Most of the owner-managers agreed (43) that moderate priority is required for the management of WC in their businesses. The second highest scores (21) were from the respondents who prioritize all three components of WC. A total (43+21) of 64 owner-managers agreed with the statement that inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable are required for management of WC in small restaurants. The bar charts representing the individual components of WC in terms of their requirements in small restaurants can be found in Appendix B. Furthermore, this study investigated whether educational qualification of the respondents affected the priority level of WCM components. Table 5.2.2. (E) outlines the one-way ANOVA test of priority given to WCM components by work experience.

TABLE 5.2.2. (E): THE ONE-WAY ANOVA TEST

ANOVA Table of the priority given to WCM components by work experience						
		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Does your company prioritize all the above three components of WCM? * Number of years of experience in your current position?	Between groups	6.670	4	1.668	3.732	0.008
	Within groups	29.941	67	0.447		
	Total	36.611	71			

The above ANOVA results of WCM priority based on number of years of work experience show that there is a significant difference between the priority given to the components of WCM based on the work experience of owner-managers of small restaurants with $F=3.732$, $p<0.01$. Thus, the priority given to the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM is related to the work experience of the owner-managers of small restaurants.

5.2.3. THE USEFULNESS OF WCM

Literature on the usefulness of WCM suggests that effective management of WC increases the performance of SMEs including small restaurants (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Mun and Jang, 2015; Zariyawati et al., 2017). Restaurant businesses maintain an optimal level of working capital to increase the performance of their businesses (Mun and Jang, 2015). In addition, effective management of stock helps to reduce maintenance costs (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). Moreover, small businesses invest more in WC to avoid the risk of financial shortage (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). Therefore, effective management of working capital is compulsory to meet their financial obligations (Zariyawati et al., 2017). Based on the existing literature, this section analyses the usefulness of WCM in small food restaurants in the UK. The question was rated in scales as: ‘Strongly agree’; ‘Agree’; ‘Neither agree nor disagree’; ‘Strongly disagree’, ‘Disagree’; ‘Do not know’. In this section, the researcher used statistical tools such as mean, frequencies, and percentage.

TABLE 5.2.3: FREQUENCY TABLE OF THE USEFULNESS OF WCM

	Mean	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know	Total
The restaurant invests in WC to avoid the risk of financial shortage	2.44	15.3%	43.1%	31.9%	4.2%	2.8%	2.8%	100%
The effective management of stock level reduces the maintenance cost	2.29	18.1%	55.6%	19.4%	0%	0%	6.90%	100%
WCM helps the restaurant to meet financial obligations such as debt financing	2.53	15.3%	38.9%	37.5%	1.4%	0%	6.9%	100%
Business performance increases by maintaining an optimal level of working capital	2.4	12.5%	51.4%	30.6%	0%	0%	5.6%	100%

The above frequency table (4.2.4) shows that (15.3% + 43.1%) 58.4% of small businesses invest in WC to avoid the risk of financial shortage, whereas 31.9% of owner-managers neither agreed nor disagreed about this usefulness of WCM. Only 7% of businesses disagreed with this statement. The mean score for this motive is 2.44. The second and the most important statement to respondents was the effective management of stock level. Even though 19.4% of respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement, (18.1% + 55.6%) 73.7% of owner-managers

agreed that the effective management of stock level reduces maintenance costs in their restaurants. WCM helped 54.2% of small restaurants to meet financial obligations, e.g. debt financing, whereas 6.9% of respondents did not know about this statement. In addition, (12.5% + 51.4%) 63.9% of owner-managers agreed that restaurants maintain an optimal level of working capital to increase the performance of their businesses. This result corroborates the findings of Mun and Jang (2015). There was a slight difference between the mean scores of the above usefulness of WCM in small restaurants. The lowest mean score of 2.29 indicates the most significant reason of considering WCM. Thus, the above findings revealed that effective management of stock helps to reduce maintenance costs in small food restaurants.

5.2.4. THE INTERNAL FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE WCM AND ITS COMPONENTS

Previous sections analysed the requirements of WC management and components by small food restaurants. However, maintaining an optimal working capital level is a complicated task as there are many external and internal factors that need to be considered and balanced (Mansoori and Muhammad, 2012; Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013; Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017). As stated by Mansoori and Muhammad (2012), internal factors affecting WCM focus on a firm's unique characteristics. There is no specific set of rules to determine the WC requirement (Adeniji, 2008) and the exact amount of WC for every type of business (Boopathi and Leeson, 2016). Most of the existing research is based on the context of developing countries. The following sections analyse the internal factors of WCM requirements in small food restaurants in the context of the UK.

5.2.4.1. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

In this study, the researcher used the requirements of WCM as the dependent variable. The internal factors that accounted for variations in the requirements of WCM by the small food restaurants in the context of this research include management competencies, business size, leverage, and profitability. As a result, based on the literature on these above factors, the researcher has developed the four hypotheses of this study. The aim of these hypotheses is to find the answer to the research question (ii) (Figure 5.1). The following table 5.2.4 (a) shows the descriptive statistics

of the above four internal factors of WCM. In addition, the researcher identified whether there were any significant differences between the internal factors effecting WC requirements in small restaurants based on the management of WC. Table 5.2.4 (b) shows ANOVA results. The complete tables of analysis can be found in Appendix C.

TABLE 5.2.4 (a). DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS OF WCM

Frequency table (%)	Mean	Std. deviation	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Do not know
Management competencies	1.71	0.568	34.7%	59.7%	5.6%	0.0%	0.0%
Business size	2.00	0.964	27.8%	54.2%	13.9%	1.4%	2.8%
Leverage	2.29	1.067	19.4%	45.8%	29.2%	1.4%	4.2%
Profitability	1.90	0.695	29.2%	51.4%	19.4%	0.0%	0.0%

It is evident from the above descriptive statistics that 94.4% (34.7% + 59.7%) of owner-managers agreed with the statement that the most important factor was management competency. The lowest mean score 1.71 indicates the most important factors of WCM. The second most important internal factor was business size (82%). Only 13.9% neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement, whereas 2.8% did not know whether business size has any effect on the WCM. The mean scores for profitability (80.6%) and leverage (65.2%) are 1.90 and 2.29 respectively. Just 4.2% respondents did not know about the impact of leverage on WCM in their restaurants.

Figure: 5.2.4. The bar charts of the internal factors of WCM in small restaurants

The above bar charts visually represent the internal factors of WCM. 80.6% of owner-managers agreed that profitability affects WCM, whereas 65.2% of respondents think leverage effects their WCM. Thus, the descriptive statistics and bar charts showed that management competency (94.4%), business size (82%), leverage (65.2%) ,and profitability (80.6%) influence WCM in small food restaurants.

TABLE 5.2.4.(B) THE ANOVA RESULTS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS BASED ON THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM

ANOVA		df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Management competency	Between groups	1	2.571	8.862	0.004
	Within groups	70	0.29		
	Total	71			
The size of business	Between groups	1	10.531	13.29	0.001
	Within groups	70	0.792		
	Total	71			
Leverage	Between groups	1	6.6	6.221	0.015
	Within groups	70	1.061		
	Total	71			
Profitability	Between groups	1	4.325	10.095	0.002
	Within groups	70	0.428		
	Total	71			

The ANOVA result suggests that there is a significant difference between the effect of internal factors on the small restaurants who are required to manage WC in their restaurants and who do not manage WC. Thus, internal factors determine the requirement of WCM of small businesses.

5.2.4.2. MEASUREMENT OF VARIABLES AND HYPOTHESIS (REGRESSION ANALYSIS)

This study determines the effect of internal factors on WCM and its components in the following sections using Pearson correlation and OLS regression. The researcher used both Spearman’s and Pearson correlation to identify the relationship and strength between the internal factors and the requirement of WCM. The researcher collapsed the dependent variable (6-point Likert scale) into a binary scale. However, this may lead to loss of information (Micioiu and Atkinson, 2017). Therefore, to compensate for this loss of information, this study identified the difference between scores based on a chi-square test (non-parametric) on the original ranking data. Regression analysis helped to reveal the level of variation in the dependent variable (Micioiu and Atkinson, 2017). The equation of regression analysis in the context of this study is listed below-

$$y = \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

In the above equation, y is the dependent variable to be estimated. X1, X2, X3 and X4 are the four internal factors. This analysis explains how the effect of internal factors (independent variables) reveals the level of variation in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable).

y. β s are the regression coefficients and ε is the error term.

TABLE 5.2.4. (C) REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNAL FACTORS AND WCM

Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.514 ^a	.265	.221	.604	1.609

a. Predictors: (Constant), the effect of management competencies, profitability, the size of business, and leverage on the choice of the WCM in restaurants?

b. Dependent variable: extent of WCM

TABLE 5.2.4. (D) ANOVAa

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.808	4	2.202	6.029	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.470	67	.365		
	Total	33.278	71			

a. Dependent variable: extent of WCM

b. Predictors: (Constant), the effect of management competencies, profitability, the size of business, and leverage on the choice of the WCM in restaurants.

From the above model summary and ANOVA table it can be identified that $R = .514$. The significant level of F statistics ($.000 < 0.01$) shows that the model is highly significant at 99% level. However, insignificant coefficients (Beta and p value) identified the predictors (Appendix C). Referring to the multiple linear regression, Shrestha (2020) stated that multicollinearity occurs when the regression model includes variables that are significantly correlated not only with the dependent variable but also with each other. As a result, the following correlation coefficients between independent (predictors) variables were carried out to detect collinearity between variables.

TABLE 5.2.4. (e) CORRELATION BETWEEN INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Model		The management competency	The size of business	Leverage	Profitability
The management competency	Pearson correlation	1	.488**	.296*	.359**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.012	0.002
	N	72	72	72	72
The size of business	Pearson correlation	.488**	1	.568**	.606**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	72	72	72	72
Leverage	Pearson correlation	.296*	.568**	1	.742**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.012	0.000		0.000
	N	72	72	72	72
Profitability	Pearson correlation	.359**	.606**	.742**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.000	0.000	
	N	72	72	72	72

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From the above correlation table, it can be analysed that independent variables are significantly correlated at 0.01. Consequently, insignificant coefficients (Beta and p value) identified the

predictors (Appendix C). However, collinearity does not influence the predictions and the goodness-of-fit statistics (Shrestha, 2020). The aim of this study is to identify the effect of each of the internal factors on the WCM requirement; therefore, the researcher needs to identify the role of each independent variables. Correlation analysis only explains the relation between variables, while regression indicates the impact of internal factors (independent variables) on the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). Thus, this analysis helps to see how independent variables affect the dependent variable (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). The next sub-sections investigate the relationships between each internal factor: management competency, the size, leverage, and profitability, and the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants using Pearson correlation, Spearman's correlation and OLS regression analysis. In addition, the following sections evaluate the impact of these four internal factors on the WCM components: inventory, accounts receivable and Accounts payable by using cross-tabulation statistics and chi-square on the original ranking data as to avoid loss of data (Micioiu and Atkinson, 2017).

5.2.4.3. MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES

It is widely reported in the literature that small businesses strive to employ knowledgeable, experienced, and qualified people to manage working capital effectively both in emerging (Orobia et al., 2013; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017) and developed (Howorth, and Westhead, 2003; Afrifa, 2013) countries. However, one group of researchers argued that management competencies such as theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and skills affect the WC requirements of small businesses (Afrifa, 2013; Orobia et al., 2013; Louw and Hall, 2016; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017; Chepkemoi et al., 2017). On the other hand, other researchers debated that there is no association between theoretical knowledge of managers and WCM practices in the small businesses (Agyei-Mensah, 2012; Orobia et al., 2016). The owners and managers of small businesses gain knowledge and skills of WCM through prior experience as opposed to the formal education system (Orobia et al., 2016). Therefore, based on the above arguments, the following hypothesis has been developed to investigate the effect of managerial theoretical and practical knowledge on the requirement of WCM and components of the small restaurants. This study developed two sub-hypotheses H_{1a} and H_{1b} to investigate the main hypothesis H_1 .

H₁: Management competencies are positively related to the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

H_{1a}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on the managerial theoretical knowledge.

H_{1b}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on the managerial practical knowledge.

5.2.4.3.1. MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES AND WORKING CAPITAL REQUIREMENTS (H₁)

To investigate the impact of management competencies on the requirements of WCM in small restaurants, this section tested hypothesis H₁ by using Spearman’s rho, Pearson correlation and OLS regression. The purpose of using both parametric (Pearson) and non-parametric (Spearman’s) analysis was to identify whether there was any significant difference between the statistical significances and p-values. The complete correlation tables can be found in Appendix C.

TABLE 5.2.4.3.(a) Correlation analysis between the extent of WCM and management competencies

Spearman’s rho		Pearson correlation	
Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
.234**	0.048	.314**	0.007

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It can be identified from the above table that Spearman’s (.234**, P = 0.048) and Pearson correlation (.314**, P = 0.007) lead to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance. Therefore, linear models used in this study without normal distribution of data should nevertheless produce valid results (Schmidt and Finana, 2018). Hypothesis H₁ is accepted because management competency is significantly positively related to the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.3. (b) Regression analysis:

Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted square	R	Std. error of the estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.836 ^a	0.699	0.695		0.14136	2.045

a. Predictors: (constant), The influence of management competencies

b. Dependent variable: working capital management

Table 5.2.4.3. (c) Regression analysis **ANOVA**^a

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.254	1	3.254	162.847	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.399	70	0.020		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent variable: working capital management

b. Predictors: (constant), the influence of management competencies

Table 5.2.4.3. (d) Regression analysis: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	0.203	0.221		0.918	0.362		
Management competencies	1.499	0.198	0.670	7.555	0.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent variable: the requirements of WCM

The regression analysis from the above tables (Table 5.2.4.3 a, b, c) demonstrates how the effect of management competency reveals the level of variation in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). As can be identified from the model summary in Table 5.2.4.3. (a), R square is 0.699 which means that the management competency has a 69.9% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Furthermore, the significant level of F statistics (.000<0.01) shows that the model is highly significant at the 99% level. The regression coefficient value (β 0.670) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of management competency and the requirement of WCM in small restaurants at the 99% level ($t=7.555$, .000<0.01). In addition, the value of the

variance inflation factor (VIF) is 1, which specifies that there is no problem of collinearity. VIF determines the strength of the relationships (Shrestha, 2020).

5.2.4.3.2. MANAGERIAL THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE AND WCM COMPONENTS (H_{1a}) and (H_{1b})

This section analyses the following hypotheses to identify whether theoretical and practical knowledge of managers have any impact on the priority given to WCM components: inventory and accounts receivable and payable.

H_{1a}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on managerial theoretical knowledge.

H_{1b}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on managerial practical knowledge.

Table 5.2.4.3. (e) Cross-tabulation statistics

Crosstab Count		Components of WCM		Total
		Priority	Not a priority	
Education	Agree	60	5	65
	Do not know	7	0	7
Total		67	5	72
Experiences	Agree	62	4	66
	Do not know	5	1	6
Total		67	5	72

Table 5.2.4.3. (f) Chi-square

Chi-square tests	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	.957 ^a	1	0.328
Likelihood ratio	0.731	1	0.393
Linear-by-linear Association	0.944	1	0.331
N of valid cases	72		

a. 2 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .42.

From the above tabulated statistics, it can be revealed that a total of 60 owner-managers who give priority to the WCM components agreed with the statement that small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on managerial theoretical knowledge. Similarly, a total of 62 owner-managers who give priority to the WCM components agreed with the statement that small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on managerial practical knowledge. Furthermore, from the above Table 5.2.4.3. (f) the results of Pearson chi-square $\chi^2(2) = .957^a$, indicating that the difference between the effect of managerial practical knowledge and theoretical knowledge on the requirement of WCM components is insignificant: $p = 0.328 > 0.05$. Thus, hypothesis H_{1a} and H_{1b} can be accepted. Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on both practical and theoretical knowledge.

5.2.4.4. BUSINESS SIZE AND WORKING CAPITAL REQUIREMENT (H_2)

Previous literature suggests that the size of a business has an impact on the practice of WCM in small business (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Garg, 2015). However, there are **conflicting** opinions on the level of WC requirements of firms of different sizes. Previous researchers disagree about whether there is a positive relationship between business size and the requirements of WCM (Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Orobia et al., 2016). A large business requires more investment in WC because of its large scale of operations (Adekunle and Sunday, 2015) and high volume of sales (Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016). However, an opposing point of view (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013) argued that the size of business is negatively related to working capital requirements of SMEs; therefore, the small-size business requires more WC. On the other hand, Azami and Tabar (2016) found an insignificant relationship between the business size and the level of working capital management. Therefore, based on the above arguments, the following hypothesis has been developed to investigate the effect of business size on the requirement of WCM and components of small restaurants. This study developed three sub-hypotheses H_{2a} , H_{2b} , and H_{2c} to investigate the effect of the business size on the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM.

H_2 : The size of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants.

H2a. There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the size of the small food restaurants.

H2b. There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the size of small food restaurants.

H2c. There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the size of small food restaurants.

Correlation analysis (H₂)

Table 5.2.4.4. (a): Correlation between WCM and business size

Spearman's rho		Pearson correlation	
Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
.350**	0.003	.428**	0.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (-tailed).

It can be identified from the above table that Spearman's (.350**, P = 0.003) and Pearson correlations (.428**, P = 0.000) lead to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance. Thus, hypothesis H₂ is accepted because the size of business is significantly positively related to the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

Regression analysis (H₂)

Table 5.2.4.4. (b) Regression analysis: Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.446 ^a	0.199	0.187	0.23076	2.464

a. Predictors: (constant), the size of business

b. Dependent variable: WCM

Table 5.2.4.4. (c) ANOVA^a

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	0.925	1	0.925	17.374	.000 ^b
Residual	3.728	70	0.053		
Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent variable: working capital management

b. Predictors: (constant), the size of business

Table 5.2.4.4.(d) Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	0.740	0.084		8.849	0.000		
The size of business	0.286	0.069	0.446	4.168	0.000	1.000	1.000

The regression analysis from the above tables (Table 5.2.4.4. a, b, c) shows how the effect of business size (independent variables) reveals the level of variation in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). As can be seen from the model summary in Table 5.2.4.4. (a), $R = .446$ showing that there is positive correlation between variables. Additionally, $R\text{ square} = 0.199$, which shows that management competency has only 19.9% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. The higher variability of independent variables around the requirement of WC produces a lower R-square value (0.199). However, the significant level of F statistics ($.000 < 0.01$) shows that the model is highly significant at the 99% level. In addition, the regression coefficient value (β 0.446) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of business size and the requirement of WCM in small restaurants. The value of VIF shows that there is no problem of collinearity.

5.2.4.4.1. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND THE INVENTORY PERIOD (H_{2a})

Previous research identified that the size of businesses has an impact on inventory management (Baker et al., 2017; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017). Small businesses generate a list of inventory requirements which is no more than a shopping list (Orobia et al., 2013). Small businesses show poor performance if they never review stock level, stock turnover and stock reorder level (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). However, excess amounts of inventory in stock increases the cost of maintenance, while low levels of inventory increases the risk of running out of stock and losing customers (Azami, and Tabar, 2016). The following hypothesis was developed based on existing literature.

H_{2a}. There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the size of the small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.4. (c) Cross-tabulation statistics

Crosstab count		Does your restaurant keep a high inventory level?		Total	Does your business review and control inventory?		Total
		Agree	Disagree		Agree	Disagree	
The size of business	Agree	61	1	62	61	1	62
	Do not know	5	4	9	5	4	9
	Disagree	0	1	1	0	1	1
	Total	66	6	72	66	6	72

Table 5.2.4.4. (d) Chi-square tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	30.029 ^a	2	0.000
Likelihood ratio	18.701	2	0.000
Linear-by-linear association	29.469	1	0.000
N of valid cases	72		

a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

The results from the cross-tabulated table shows that 61 owner-managers agreed that their business size has an impact on inventory management. Therefore, they keep a high inventory level. Similarly, 61 respondents stated that their restaurants review and control inventory. Pearson chi-square statistics of 30.029^a and the p-value = .000, indicating that the association between inventory management and the size of business is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, H_{2a} is accepted. There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the size of the small food restaurants.

5.2.4.4.2. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE MANAGEMENT (H_{2b})

Small firms are required to offer more generous credit terms to their customers (Paul and Boden, 2011). This results in low operating margins and reduced internal finance. Ndagijimana (2014) identified that small businesses should maintain a balance between cash sales and credit sales to increase operating margins and internal finance. On the other hand, Mun and Jang (2015) stated

that restaurant businesses can generate extra cash from business operation more quickly than other industry; therefore, they do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively. These outcomes are contradictory with the result of Azami and Tabar (2016) and Baker et al., 2017. The size of businesses has no impact on accounts receivable management (Baker et al., 2017). These studies elaborated that there was no significant relationship between company size and the components of WCM. Furthermore, Agyei-Mensah (2012) found poor accounts receivable management in Ghanaian small businesses, as they never review debtor credit period, bad debts, or customer risk standing. However, these studies were conducted in developing countries. The UK exhibits a variety of restaurants with a multicultural base of customers (Crick et al., 2016). Therefore, based on the above literature, this study developed the following hypothesis (H2b).

H2b. There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the size of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.4. (e) **Crosstab: The size of business and accounts receivable**

Crosstab count		Use of computers in managing receivables from customers		Total	Extend accounts receivable period to encourage customers to spend more		Total
		Agree	Disagree		Agree	Disagree	
The size of business	Agree	55	7	62	53	9	62
	Do not know	1	8	9	3	6	9
	Disagree	0	1	1	0	1	1
Total		56	16	72	56	16	72

Table 5.2.4.4. (f) Chi-square tests

Chi-square tests (Use of computer in AR)				Chi-square tests (Extent of AR period)			
	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)		Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	30.930 ^a	2	0.000	Pearson chi-square	15.916 ^a	2	0.000
Likelihood ratio	26.283	2	0.000	Likelihood ratio	13.457	2	0.001
Linear-by-linear association	28.773	1	0.000	Linear-by-linear association	15.557	1	0.000
N of valid cases	72			N of valid cases	72		
a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.				a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.			

The findings from the above tabulated table (Table 5.2.4.4. e) shows that 55 owner-managers agreed that their business size has an impact on AR management, and they use computers in managing AR from customers. Similarly, out of 72 respondents, 53 answered that their restaurants extend the accounts receivable period to encourage customers to spend more; therefore, the size of business has an impact on AR management.

Pearson chi-square statistics 30.029^a and 15.916^a with a p-value = .000 for both results indicate that the association between accounts receivable management and the size of business is statistically significant, at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, H2b is accepted. Small firms are required to offer more generous credit terms to their customers, therefore extending their AR period to encourage customers to spend more. It can be concluded from the above findings that effective management of AR, computerized systems, and extending the AR period to encourage customers to spend more are crucial in small food restaurants in the context of the UK.

5.2.4.4.3. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE MANAGEMENT (H2c)

Mun and Jang (2015) identified that restaurant businesses have very low levels of WC and high levels of accounts payable. Consequently, small restaurant businesses rely significantly on suppliers' credit for managing cash flow and business operations. Paying by the due date or early is one way to maintain a strong relationship with suppliers. Other researchers have outlined that small-size businesses require more WC than large-size businesses as they have less favourable credit terms with suppliers and customers (Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Azeem and Marsap, 2015). Enow and Kamala (2016) identified that small businesses had a lower bargaining power in term of credit purchasing with suppliers. Lack of employees was the main factor that inhibits small businesses from managing accounts payable effectively. As a result, the following hypothesis is developed.

H2c. There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the size of small food restaurants.

5.2.4.4. (g) Cross-tabulation statistics

Crosstab count		Paying supplier early		Total	Reliance on supplier credit		Total
		Agree	Disagree		Agree	Disagree	
Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Agree	59	3	62	61	1	62
	Do not know	5	4	9	6	3	9
	Disagree	1	0	1	0	1	1
Total		65	7	72	67	5	72

5.2.4.4. (h) Chi-square tests

Paying supplier early				Reliance on supplier credit			
	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)		Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	14.155 ^a	2	0.001	Pearson chi-square	25.826 ^a	2	0.000
Likelihood ratio	9.538	2	0.008	Likelihood ratio	14.621	2	0.001
Linear-by-linear association	8.524	1	0.004	Linear-by-linear association	24.191	1	0.000
N of valid cases	72			N of valid cases	72		
a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .10.				a. 4 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.			

The results from the cross-tabulated table shows that 59 owner-managers agreed that business size has an impact on AP management, and they prefer to pay suppliers early, while 61 respondents agreed with the statement that they rely significantly on supplier credit. Thus, they did not negotiate with their suppliers to extend credit periods. In addition, Pearson chi-square statistics 14.155a and the p-value 0.001, 25.826a with the p-value = 0.000 indicate that the association between AP management and the business size is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. Small food restaurants in the UK rely significantly on suppliers' credit for managing cash flow and business operations. As a result, small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain strong relationship with suppliers. They mostly depend on internal financing such as owner financing, supplier credit, etc.

5.2.4.5. LEVERAGE AND WORKING CAPITAL REQUIREMENT (H₃)

According to empirical research, the relationship between leverage and WCM is usually negative (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Elbadry, 2018). Accordingly, smaller-size firms with low leverage are likely to have the highest investment in WC (Shaista and Veeri, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Armugam, 2013). Elbadry (2018) found that SMEs with high leverage depend on debt finance. The repayment of debts forces a business to manage its working capital efficiently. On the other hand, Valipour (2012) and Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) argued that debt ratio is positively and significantly correlated with the WCM of small businesses only. A recent study (Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017) found insignificant results for leverage and WCM, therefore no relation of WCM with leverage for the UK pharmaceutical firms. This result is aligned with the findings of Gill (2010) and Manoori and Muhammad (2012). Fan et al. (2012) identified a significant variation in leverage and debt ratio in developed and developing countries.

In relation to WC components, Mun and Jang (2015) reported that small food restaurants keep a high inventory for daily operations, prefer collecting payments from customers on time because of the cash sales nature of the industry, and pay their suppliers early to maintain a strong relationship with suppliers. Nevertheless, previous studies identified an insignificant relationship between WCM components and debt ratio (Gill, 2010; Manoori and Muhammad, 2012; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017). Therefore, no relation of INV, AR, and AP was found with the leverage of a business. On the contrary, according to Abbadi and Abbadi (2013), firms with high level of leverage decrease inventory days and account collection periods and expand payables periods and credit terms with suppliers because of high levels of debt. As stated by Zariyawati et al. (2017), the inventory level does not associate with debt ratio in a business. Evidence (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014) suggests that the way leverage effects WCM and its compounds is determined by country factors. As a result, the following hypotheses have been developed to investigate the effect of leverage on the requirement of WCM and components of the small restaurants.

H₃: Leverage (debt ratio) of a business is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

H_{3a}: There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the debt level of small food restaurants.

H_{3b}: There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

H_{3c}: There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.5. (a) Leverage and the requirements of WCM

Spearman's rho		Pearson correlation	
Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
.354**	0.002	.358**	0.002

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It can be identified from the above table that Spearman's (.354**, p = 0.002) and Pearson correlation (.358**, p = 0.002) lead to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance. Thus, hypothesis H₃ is accepted because leverage has significant positive effect on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. However, this result does not reveal the level of variation in the requirements of WCM. Therefore, the regression analysis (Table 4.2.5.3. a, b, c) would help to identify the level of variation in the dependent variable.

Table 5.2.4.5. (b) Regression analysis leverage and WCM

Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate
1	.245 ^a	0.060	0.047	0.24994

a. Predictors: (constant), leverage

b. Dependent variable: WCM

Table 5.2.4.5. (c) ANOVA^a

		Sum squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.280	1	0.280	4.478	.038 ^b
	Residual	4.373	70	0.062		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent Variable: WCM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leverage

Table 5.2.4.5. (d) Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.903	0.084		10.749	0.000		
	Leverage	0.124	0.058	0.245	2.116	0.038	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent variable: working capital management

As can be identified from the model summary in Table 5.2.4.5. (b), R square is 0.060 which means that the management competency has a 6.0% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Furthermore, the significant level of F statistics (.038<0.05) shows that the model is highly significant at the 95% level. The regression coefficient value (β 245) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of leverage and the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. In addition, the value of variance inflation factor (VIF) is 1, which specifies that there is no problem of collinearity (Shrestha, 2020). VIF determines the strength of the relationships. However, it can be identified from the R square result that the leverage has only a 0.6% impact on the requirement of WCM. Therefore, it is important to identify whether small food restaurants rely significantly on debt financing rather than owner financing.

Table 5.2.4.5. (e) Frequency table

Debt financing				Owner financing			
		Frequency	Valid Percent			Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid	Agree	9	12.5	Valid	Strongly agree	27	37.5
	Disagree	9	12.5		Agree	39	54.2
	Do not know	54	75		Do not know	6	8.3
	Total	72	100		Total	72	100

The above frequency table shows that only 12.5% respondents rely on debt financing, whereas the majority (37.5 + 54.2) 91.7% of owner-managers rely on owner financing. As a result, due to lower dependence on debt financing, the regression results identified lower impact (0.06%) on the requirement of WCM.

5.2.4.5.1. LEVERAGE AND INVENTORY MANAGEMENT (H3a)

To investigate the impact of leverage on the inventory level in small restaurants, this section tested hypothesis H_{3a} by using cross-tabulation statistics and chi-square.

H_{3a}: There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the debt level of the small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.5. (f) Cross-tabulation statistics

Crosstab count		High level of debt cause inventory holding period to decrease			Total
		Agree	Do not know	Disagree	
The effect of leverage	Agree	15	31	2	48
	Do not know	5	17	1	23
	Disagree	1	0	0	1
Total		21	48	3	72

Table 5.2.4.5. (g) Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	3.149 ^a	4	.533
Likelihood ratio	3.220	4	.522
Linear-by-linear association	.012	1	.911
N of valid cases	72		

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

The findings from the above cross-tabulated statistics show that only 15 respondents agreed to both statements that leverage has an impact on WCM, and the high level of debt causes the inventory holding period to decrease. 31 respondents agreed with the statement that leverage has

an impact on WCM; however, they do not know whether there is a relation between the INV holding period and debt level. 2 respondents disagreed with this statement. In addition, (Table 5.2.4.5. g) Pearson chi-square statistics 3.149a and the p-value .533 indicate that the association between the INV holding period and the debt level is statistically insignificant at a significance level of 0.05.

5.2.4.5.2. Leverage and accounts receivable

This section analyses the following hypothesis (**H_{3b}**) to identify whether leverage has any impact on the accounts receivable of small restaurants by using cross-tabulation and the chi-square test.

H_{3b}: There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.5. (h) Cross-tabulation

Crosstab count		Reduce debt level by shortening account collection periods			Total
		Agree	Do not know	Disagree	
Leverage	Agree	29	15	3	47
	Do not know	3	18	2	23
	Disagree	1	0	0	1
Total		33	33	5	71

Table 5.2.4.5. (i) Chi-square tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	16.289 ^a	4	.003
Likelihood ratio	18.075	4	.001
Linear-by-linear association	6.714	1	.010
N of valid cases	71		

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.

The above cross-tabulated statistics show that only 29 respondents agreed with the statement that leverage has an impact on the WCM requirement, and they reduce debt levels by collecting payments from customers early. 15 owner-managers do not know whether there is a relation between collecting payments from customers and debt level. Only 3 respondents disagreed with this statement. Pearson chi-square statistics 16.289^a and the p-value .003 indicate that the association between the AR period and the debt level is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05.

5.2.4.5.3. Leverage and accounts payable (H_{3c})

To investigate the impact of leverage on the level of accounts payable, this section analysed **H_{3c}**.

H_{3c}: There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.5. (j) Cross-tabulation

Crosstab count		Expand payables period and credit terms with suppliers because of high level of debt			Total
		Agree	Do not know	Disagree	
Leverage	Agree	11	31	6	48
	Do not know	4	16	3	23
	Disagree	1	0	0	1
Total		16	47	9	72

Table 5.2.4.5. (k) **Chi-square tests**

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	3.826 ^a	4	.430
Likelihood ratio	3.352	4	.501
Linear-by-linear association	.052	1	.820
N of valid cases	72		

a. 4 cells (44.4%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .13.

The above cross-tabulation results reveal that only 11 owner-managers agreed that leverage has an impact on the WCM requirement, and they seek to expand the payables period and credit terms with suppliers because of high levels of debt. 31 respondents do not know whether there is a relation between the payables period and debt level, and 6 respondents disagreed with this statement. Pearson chi-square statistics 3.826a and the p-value .430 indicate that the association between the AP period and the debt level is not statistically significant. Thus, H_{3a} and H_{3c} are rejected. Therefore, there is no relation of INV and AP with the leverage of the small food restaurants. On the other hand, H_{3b} is accepted. A significant relation between AR and debt ratio has been identified. Small food restaurants reduce debt level by shortening account collection periods.

5.2.4.6. PROFITABILITY AND WORKING CAPITAL REQUIREMENT (H₄)

Even though the determinants of working capital management (WCM) motivated and triggered many researchers, their opinions as to the relationship between WCM and firms' profitability have been divided. There is strong evidence to suggest that WCM practice has a very strong impact on liquidity and profitability of an organization (Atseye et al., 2015; Garg, 2015; Padachi and Afrifa, 2016; Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016). However, other researchers with opposing points of view (Alsie and Arora, 2016; Lyngstadaas and Berg, 2016) supported a negative association between the components of WCM and profitability of SMEs. Tauringana and Afrifa (2013) identified that inventory (INV) is not important for the profitability of SMEs. On the other hand, Louw and Hall (2016) argued that inventory management and accounts payable have the strongest statistically significant impact on a firm's profitability. Pais and Gama (2015) pointed out that excessive liabilities may have a negative impact on the profitability of SMEs. Reducing the AP days and early payment to suppliers will help SMEs to maintain a good relationship with suppliers and to minimize late payment costs. Louw et al. (2019) revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail (e.g. restaurant) industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Restaurant businesses can generate extra cash from business operation sooner than other industry (Mun and Jang, 2015). Therefore, this study investigates whether the profitability affects WCM and its components either positively or negatively. The following hypothesis (H₄) has been developed to investigate the effect of profitability on the requirement of WCM and components of small food restaurants. This study developed three sub-hypotheses H_{4a}, H_{4b} and H_{4c} to investigate the effect of profitability on the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM.

H₄: The profitability of small food restaurants has a positive impact on the requirements of WCM.

H_{4a}: A statistically significant relationship exists between the inventory holding period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

H_{4b}: An insignificant relationship exists between the accounts receivable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

H4c. An insignificant relationship exists between the accounts payable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.6. (a) Correlation analysis between the profitability and working capital requirement

Spearman's rho		Pearson correlation	
Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
.344**	0.003	.400**	0.000

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It can be identified from the above table that Spearman's (.344**, $p = 0.003$) and Pearson correlation (.400**, $p = 0.000$) lead to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance. Thus, hypothesis H4 is accepted because profitability has a significant positive impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.6. (b) Regression analysis: Profitability and WCM

Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted square	R	Std. error of the estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.317 ^a	0.101	0.088		0.24451	2.283

a. Predictors: (constant), profitability

b. Dependent variable: WCM

5.2.4.6. (c) ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.468	1	0.468	7.828	.007 ^b
	Residual	4.185	70	0.060		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent variable: WCM

b. Predictors: (constant), profitability

Table 5.2.4.6. (e) **Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
		B	Std. error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.864	0.079		10.969	0.000	1.000	1.000
	Profitability	0.166	0.059	0.317	2.798	0.007		

a. Dependent variable: WCM

The regression analysis from the above tables (Table 5.2.4.6. a, b, c) demonstrates how the effect of profitability reveals the level of variation in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). As can be identified from the model summary in Table 5.2.4.6. (a), R square is 0.101 which means that the profitability has only 10.1% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Furthermore, the significant level of F statistics (.007<0.01) shows that the model is highly significant at the 99% level. The regression coefficient value (β 0.317) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of profitability and the requirement of WCM in small restaurants. In addition, the value of variance inflation factor (VIF) is 1, which specifies that there is no problem of collinearity (Shrestha, 2020). VIF determines the strength of the relationships. Furthermore, it can be analysed from the above R square that the profitability has only 10.1% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Therefore, to investigate the lower percentage impact of profitability on WCM, the researcher placed components of WCM, inventory, receivables, and payables, into sub-groups based on the main factor.

5.2.4.6.1. PROFITABILITY AND INVENTORY PERIOD (H_{4a})

Based on the existing literature discussed in the previous section, this section analysed the relationship between the inventory period and profitability of small restaurants.

H_{4a}: There is a significant relationship between the inventory holding period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.6. (e) **Cross-tabulation**

Crosstab count		Inventory holding period		Total
		Agree	Do not know	
Profitability	Agree	47	10	57
	Do not know	3	10	13
	Disagree	1	1	2
Total		51	21	72

Table 5.2.4.6. (f) **Chi-square tests**

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	18.498 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood ratio	17.164	2	.000
Linear-by-linear association	13.933	1	.000
N of valid cases	72		

a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .58.

The results from the cross-tabulated table shows that 47 owner-managers agreed that the inventory holding period is important for the profitability of their businesses. They also think that profitability influences the WCM requirement in their restaurants. Pearson chi-square statistics 18.498a and the p-value = .000 indicate that the association between the inventory holding period and the profitability is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. H_{4a} is accepted. Inventory management has a significant impact on small restaurants' profitability.

5.2.4.6.2. PROFITABILITY AND ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE PERIOD (H_{4b})

To investigate the impact of profitability on the accounts receivable period, this section tested H_{4b} . H_{4b} : There is a significant relationship between the accounts receivable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.6. (g) **Cross-tabulation**

Crosstab count		Accounts receivable period			Total
		Agree	Do not know	Disagree	
Profitability	Agree	30	26	1	57
	Do not know	3	10	0	13
	Disagree	1	1	0	2
Total		34	37	1	72

Table 5.2.4.6. (h) **Chi-square tests**

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	4.245 ^a	4	.374
Likelihood ratio	4.607	4	.330
Linear-by-linear association	1.639	1	.200
N of valid cases	72		

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

The results from the cross-tabulated table shows that only 30 owner-managers agreed that collecting payment from customers early, thus reducing the accounts receivable period, is important for the profitability of their businesses. Most of the respondents do not know whether profitability influences the WCM requirement and accounts receivable in their restaurants. Pearson chi-square statistics 4.245a and the p-value = .374 indicate that the association between the accounts receivable period and the profitability is not statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. Thus, the findings suggest that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in small food restaurants because of the cash sales nature of the business. Therefore, accounts receivable is found to be insignificant in the restaurant industry.

5.2.4.6.3. PROFITABILITY AND ACCOUNT PAYABLES PERIOD (H_{4c})

In this section, cross-tabulation and chi-square statistics were used to test hypothesis H_{4c}.

H_{4c}. There is a significant relationship between a shorter accounts payable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

Table 5.2.4.6. (i) Cross-tabulation

		Accounts payable period (Late payment)			Total
		Agree	Do not know	Disagree	
Profitability	Agree	19	12	26	57
	Do not know	3	7	3	13
	Disagree	1	0	1	2
Total		23	19	30	72

Table 5.2.4.6. (j) **Chi-square T-tests**

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	6.740 ^a	4	.150
Likelihood ratio	6.651	4	.156
Linear-by-linear association	.218	1	.640
N of valid cases	72		

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .53.

The results from the cross-tabulated table show that only 19 owner-managers agreed that late payment to suppliers is profitable for their businesses. 26 respondents disagreed with the statement that paying suppliers late is profitable for their businesses and 12 owner-managers answered that they do not know whether late payment to suppliers is profitable or not. Thus, they did not negotiate with their suppliers to extend credit periods. In addition, Pearson chi-square statistics 6.740^a and the p-value = .150 indicate that the association between the accounts payable period and profitability is statistically insignificant at a significance level of 0.05. Small food restaurants pay their creditors on time to take advantage of the benefits of discounts and to maintain strong relationships with suppliers.

5.2.5. VALIDITY, RELIABILITY, AND NORMALITY OF MEASUREMENTS

Validity and reliability are the most important measures of a research study (Bryman and Bell, 2018). The validity of this study was divided into two parts: internal validity and external validity (Creswell, 2014). In this study the researcher was able to draw conclusions from the data. The reliability was measured to examine internal validity and findings were compared with previous literature to confirm the truth of the population. External validity examines the generalizability of the results in real life (Patino and Ferreira, 2018). The researcher used Cronbach's alpha to measure internal consistency and to confirm the reliability of the instrument. Thus, the researcher was able to confirm the repeatability of the procedure to produce the similar results if applied in other settings and contexts.

5.2.5.1. VALIDITY EVIDENCE

Validity of a research depends on reliability. Validity evidence for this study was achieved by the evidence based on internal structure and relations between variables (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). The researcher calculated coefficient alpha in the next section. Thus, this study measured validity based on relations between variables as shown in Table 5.2.5.1. The complete table of correlation analysis between dependent and independent variables can be found in Appendix D.

Table 5.2.5.1. Validity test

Validity evidence based on relation between dependent and independent variables	Pearson correlation (validity coefficients)
The extent of working capital management	1
Management competency	.314*
The size of business	.428**
Leverage	.358**
Profitability	.400**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sample size for this study is N=72. The degree of freedom (df) = N-2 (72-2). Critical value at (72-2) 70 df can be found from the table of critical values for Pearson correlation.

For this study, the critical value is 70 df (0.01) = 0.303. The above table shows all obtained values (.314*.428**.358**.400**) are > critical value of 0.303 and are highly significant at the 0.01 level.

Therefore, variables are valid. Validity coefficients show positive significant correlation between variables.

5.2.5.2. VALID RESPONSE RATE

This section checks missing responses to eliminate errors from the collected data. The following Table 5.2.5.2 shows the percentage of the valid and missing responses.

Table 5.2.5.2. Valid and missing responses

		Respondent	Type of business enterprise	Highest qualification	Number of employees	The current position/Job?	Experience in your current position?
N	Valid	72	72	72	72	72	72
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0

All 72 respondents found the above questions relevant to the survey questions. The researcher emphasized the anonymity of the questionnaires (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). Therefore, respondents were confident to answer the demographic questions. In the next section the reliability was measured to examine internal validity by using Cronbach’s alpha measurement (Table 5.2.5.3).

5.2.5.3. RELIABILITY TEST

In section B of the questionnaire, the researcher used Likert scales. Therefore, it was essential to calculate Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for internal consistency reliability. Cronbach’s alpha is a commonly used test of internal reliability (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The acceptable result for Cronbach’s alpha coefficient internal consistency is usually 0.7 and above (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). SPSS version 25 was used to compute the reliability coefficient (Appendix D). The following coefficients (Table 5.2.5.3) resulted from the reliability test.

Table 5.2.5.3. Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficients

Item-total statistics					
Question no	Scale mean if item deleted	Scale variance if item deleted	Corrected item-total correlation	Squared multiple correlation	Cronbach's alpha if item deleted
B1.1	7.37	7.464	0.795	0.680	0.794
B2.2	7.52	7.539	0.723	0.851	0.807
B2.3	7.04	6.527	0.488	0.555	0.909
B2.4	7.49	7.511	0.665	0.841	0.819
B2.5	7.31	7.131	0.850	0.751	0.777
Reliability statistics of the requirements of WCM			Alpha	0.850	
B3.1	7.10	8.976	0.857	0.737	0.887
B3.2	7.27	8.799	0.806	0.726	0.903
B3.3	7.00	8.571	0.768	0.647	0.919
B3.4	7.15	9.133	0.864	0.761	0.886

Reliability statistics of the usefulness of WCM			Alpha	0.922	
B4.1	6.19	4.919	0.538	0.408	0.722
B4.2	5.90	3.582	0.571	0.376	0.686
B4.3	5.61	3.368	0.533	0.390	0.727
B4.4	6.00	4.197	0.672	0.497	0.646
Reliability statistics of the internal factors of WCM			Alpha	0.752	
B5.1	5.40	3.483	0.542	0.361	0.680
B5.2	5.21	3.491	0.513	0.296	0.695
B5.3	5.31	3.933	0.472	0.240	0.719
B5.4	5.13	2.618	0.645	0.452	0.618
Reliability statistics of the effect of management competencies				Alpha	0.742
B6.1	18.94	27.715	0.243	0.284	0.849
B6.2	19.65	23.835	0.648	0.751	0.790
B6.3	19.54	23.801	0.627	0.729	0.793
B6.4	20.13	22.702	0.606	0.645	0.796
B6.5	20.21	21.970	0.716	0.666	0.776
B6.6	19.29	22.914	0.580	0.498	0.801
B6.7	19.82	24.235	0.590	0.456	0.799
Reliability statistics of the effect of business size				Alpha	0.713
B7.1	9.44	11.249	0.728	0.704	0.861
B7.2	9.15	11.019	0.700	0.555	0.869
B7.3	9.37	9.807	0.745	0.698	0.854
B7.4	9.61	9.242	0.837	0.800	0.815
Reliability statistics of the effect of leverage				Alpha	0.884
B8.1	7.65	4.483	0.266	0.345	0.628
B8.2	7.38	3.618	0.520	0.453	0.453
B8.3	7.69	4.215	0.451	0.421	0.521
B8.4	6.74	3.014	0.406	0.374	0.563
Reliability Statistics of the effect of the profitability				Alpha	0.614

The reliability coefficients for total 33 items: Alpha 0.786

The results in Table 5.2.5.3 indicate that the value of Cronbach's alpha (α) for 28 questions shows a high degree of reliability (more than 0.7) (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Johnson and Christensen, 2017). This suggests that the Likert-scale questions were valid and of a high degree of reliability. The reliability coefficients for the total 33 items were 0.786. Even though the alpha score for questions B8.1-B8.4 was 0.614, items were kept in the questionnaires, when there are fewer than 20 items; as in the case for only four items of the B8.1 to B8.4, a value of 0.614 is satisfactory (Dall'Oglio et al., 2010). Alpha is influenced by the number of items. Alpha increases as the number of items increase (Hayes and Coutts, 2020). As a result, a large number of items will inflate the value of alpha (Cohen and Swerdlik, 2010). Alpha should be calculated for each of the variables or concepts rather than for the total scale, according to Cohen and Swerdlik (2010). Thus, α does

not measure the homogeneity of variables directly. Therefore, to avoid misinterpretation of the alpha, this study computed the reliability coefficients for each of the variables or concepts in the questionnaires rather than for the entire scales.

5.2.5.4. NORMALITY TEST

To measure whether the quantitative data has been drawn from a normally distributed population, this study used a normality test. The normality test has been summarized in Table 5.2.5.4 (a) and Table 5.2.5.4 (b) below. The Kolmogorov-Smirnova test revealed that significant values for the scales were less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Similarly, values of the Shapiro-Wilk test are smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), which indicates a violation of normality assumptions. In addition, skewness and kurtosis values show that the sample data was not normally distributed. However, according to Schmidt and Finana (2018), these values are acceptable when the sample size is large. In this study the researcher used correlation, linear regression, chi-square, and one-way ANOVA as the sample size is large ($N=72$). Schmidt and Finana (2018) identified that the linear regression model is robust to violations of the normality assumption in a large sample size setting.

Table 5.2.5.4 (a). Tests of normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage working capital	0.319	72	0.000	0.713	72	0.000
To which of the following three components of working capital management do you give priority?	0.267	72	0.000	0.789	72	0.000
What internal factors influence the WCM in your restaurants?	0.205	72	0.000	0.914	72	0.000
Please indicate the extent to which the management competencies affect the working capital management in your restaurants	0.150	72	0.000	0.902	72	0.000
Please indicate the extent to which the size of your business affects the working capital management?	0.123	72	0.009	0.959	72	0.019
Please indicate the extent to which the leverage or debt ratio affect the working capital management in your restaurants	0.280	72	0.000	0.780	72	0.000
To what extent do you agree or disagree with the effects of profitability on the WCM in your restaurants?	0.230	72	0.000	0.909	72	0.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 5.2.5.4 (b) Descriptive statistic (Skewness and Kurtosis)

Descriptive statistic	Skewness	Kurtosis
The extent of working capital in small restaurants	1.08088859917761 (Std. error 0.283)	2.65754800568443 (Std. error 0.559)
Priority is given to the components of working capital management	1.2099740643473 (Std. error 0.283)	3.63400174507662 (Std. error 0.559)
The internal factors influence the WCM in restaurants	0.572968880488147 (Std. error 0.283)	1.34558193963061 (Std. error 0.559)
The extent to which the management competencies affect the working capital management	0.283 (Std. error 0.283)	-0.570 (Std. error 0.559)
The extent to which the size of business affects the working capital management	-0.605 (Std. error 0.283)	0.292 (Std. error 0.559)
The extent to which the leverage or debt ratio affect the working capital management in restaurants	1.562 (Std. error 0.283)	2.072 (Std. error 0.559)
The extent to which the profitability affects the WCM in restaurants	-0.890 (Std. error 0.283)	0.429 (Std. error 0.559)

For this study, the questions in the questionnaires are mostly Likert-scales (ordinal data), therefore they do not have equal gaps in units. According to Johnson and Christensen (2017), multiple item scales provide more reliable scores and variability compared to a single item rating scale, whereas Ghosh et al. (2018) argued that ordinal data is frequently skewed, kurtotic, and violates the assumption of normal distribution. However, these inconsistencies should not have any impact on the research findings if the parametric model produces robust results. Norman (2010) argued that several studies dating back to the 1930s constantly showed that parametric statistics are robust even when assumptions are violated. This study concluded that parametric models can be used without concern for ‘getting the wrong answer’. Additionally, non-parametric tools can be used to compare the robustness of the results. In this study, the researcher used both parametric (Pearson) and non-parametric (Spearman’s) correlation to compare the results. Both tests gave similar answers even when assumptions were violated. Therefore, linear models used in this study without normal distribution of data should nevertheless produce valid results (Schmidt and Finana, 2018).

5.2.6. CONCLUSION

In this section data were analysed with SPSS version 25. As mentioned above, a total of 72 owner-managers of small food restaurants participated in the study. The demographic statistics reveal the profiles of respondents in terms of educational qualifications, types of business, number of employees in restaurants, number of employees, experience, and position of participants. 64 owner-managers agreed with the statement that all three components, inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable are useful for their small restaurants. The higher percentage of GCSE education reveals that theoretical knowledge is insignificant in small food restaurants. The regression analysis demonstrates how the effect of independent variables reveals the level of variation in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). Even though F statistics ($.000 < 0.01$) show that the regression model was highly significant at the 99% level, R squares show that size (19.9%), leverage (6%), and profitability (10.1%) have a low impact on the requirement of WCM, except management competencies (69.9%). However, the regression coefficient value (β) indicates a positive correlation between the internal factors and the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. All hypotheses can be accepted, implying that there are associations between the internal factors affecting the working capital requirements of small food restaurants in the UK. In addition, the researcher measured validity and reliability of the data followed by a normality test. This section attempted to evaluate the internal factors of WCM by using statistical tools. The next chapter (chapter six) of this study provides a discussion on the both quantitative and qualitative findings, and a summary of the mixed findings by reviewing the research questions. The next section presents the qualitative data analysis and findings.

5.3. QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

In this section, findings of the qualitative data were presented according to the research questions set for this study. Data were collected from four open-ended questions. However, preliminary sorting, coding, and initial descriptive analysis of qualitative data are presented in the following sections to facilitate description, combination, and comparison (Bazeley, 2019). Out of 70 questionnaires, 30 were returned uncompleted. Out of the remaining 40 questionnaires only 28 participants responded appropriately. Although the response rate was low, it was comparable to previous study involving qualitative inquiry of small businesses (Orobia et al., 2013). Answers from the four open-ended questions were first coded to identify relevant codes. The open codes were then collapsed into themes to detect similarities and differences among participants. The following sections discuss demographic findings, via thematic analysis.

5.3.1. DATA COLLECTION AND DEMOGRAPHIC FINDINGS

Data analysis is supported by complementary processes, where both qualitative and quantitative data are collected concurrently. In this research mixed methods are followed by the researcher. The researcher intended to collect data from 100 small restaurants through both close-ended and open-ended questions. However, only 28 participants responded to the following (Table 5.3.1.a) four open-ended questions.

Table 5.3.1. (a) Open-ended questions

C1: Indicate the internal factor(s) (if any) that you encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned above	C2: How do any of the factor/factors identified in QC1 affect the inventory in your restaurant?	C3: How do any of the factor/factors identified in QC1 affect the receivables in your restaurant?	C4: How do any of the factor/factors identified in QC1 affect the payables in your restaurant?
--	---	---	--

The above four questions are organized according to the following research question: (iii) How do the internal factors influence the components of WCM in small restaurants in the UK?

The details of these respondents are presented in Table 5.3.1 (b). Each question and answer session lasted for half an hour. Preliminary sorting and labelling of participants' answers were followed

by the researcher by using indicators such as Participant 1, Participant 2, and so on. Indicators were used by the researcher to reduce the risk of identification and the anonymity of data (Bazeley, 2019). According to Saunders et al. (2016), revealing identification may lead to jigsaw identification, which means cross linking online information on individuals by assembling different information from different sources. Each participant received and signed a consent sheet, which confirmed that they did not want to be identifiable.

Table 5.3.1. (b) Demographic findings.

Participant	Type of business	Number of employees	Current job position	Education	Experiences
1	Limited liability company (LLC)	0-9	Waiter	Master's degree	3 years
2	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Chef/manager	GCSE	5 years
3	Partnership	10-19	Manager	GCSE	10 years.
4	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Chef	GCSE	10 years
5	LLC	10-19	Waiter	BA	6 years
6	LLC	0-9	Partner/Owner	GCSE	4 years
7	LLC	0-9	Manager	A level/college	19 years
8	LLC	10-19	Manager	GCSE	3 years
9	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Manager	A level	18 Years
10	LLC	10-19	Director/manager	Master's degree	3 years
11	LLC	10-19	Owner	Bachelor's degree	12 years
12	Partnership	0-9	Owner/Manager	A level/College	5 years
13	LLC	10-19	Assistant manager	A level/college	5 years
14	LLC	0-9	Chef	GCSE	15 years
15	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Owner/Chef	GCSE	15 years
16	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Manager	Master's degree	20 years
17	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Manager	GCSE	7 years
18	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Manager	A level/College	30 Years
19	LLC	10-19	Manager	Master's degree	11 years
20	Sole proprietorship	10-19	Manager	GCSE	6 years
21	Partnership	0-9	Manager	GCSE	10 years
22	LLC	10-19	Manager	BA	5 years
23	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Owner	GCSE	8 years.
24	Partnership	10-19	Manager	A Level	7 years
25	Sole proprietorship	10-19	Manager	Bachelor's degree	5 years
26	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Owner	GCSE	10 years
27	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Manager	GCSE	10
28	Sole proprietorship	0-9	Owner	GCSE	20 years

The above table shows the demographic data collected about the participants. The demographic results show that most of the small businesses were sole proprietorship (13) and limited liability companies (11). The majority of respondents were managers and owners. 14 respondents (50%) have completed GCSEs, while only 4 respondents have obtained a Master's degree.

5.3.2. THEMATIC ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Data collection was followed by analysis through yielding themes. According to Flick (2018), each participant is assumed to be a separate individual with personal beliefs, thoughts, and desires. Therefore, in this research, responses from each participant has been demonstrated in this section. As mentioned in chapter four, respondents were asked the four questions (C1-C4) in section C of the questionnaire (Appendix F).

C1. Indicate the internal factor(s) (if any) that you encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned above.

This question C1 was followed by questions (C2-C4): How do any of the factor/factors identified in Q C1 effect the components of WCM in your restaurant?. Thus, these open-ended questions were asked to small restaurant owners and managers to identify the following research question.

(iii) How do the internal factors influence the components of WCM (inventory, accounts payable, and accounts receivable) in small restaurants in the UK?

5.3.2.1. INITIAL CODING

While using thematic analysis, the researcher followed two process-identifying codes at the initial stage of coding, followed by examining commonality and relationships through initial coding (Flick, 2018). Secondly, reducing and clustering similar codes to the key themes enabled the researcher to see the most important themes that are most relevant to the research questions (Harding, 2013). The researcher conducted initial or open coding to compare data with data and to remain open to explore 'What is the participants' main concerns?' (Flick, 2014). Initial coding led to sorting and clustering themes. Clustering themes may result in constructing new themes.

Moreover, paraphrasing the initial codes into a shorter form helped the researcher to reduce unnecessary repetitions (Flick, 2014).

5.3.2.2. THEMES AND CODES

The collected open-ended responses from 28 respondents were imported in NVivo 12 to identify codes and themes nodes. The researcher gathered references to the theme by dragging sources at the node. For example, NVivo helped to gather all 28 responses to question C1 (Indicate the internal factor(s) (if any) that you encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned above) at a node. This helped the researcher to explore people’s concerns in response to question C1. As themes emerged, the researcher created more nodes and merged similar nodes together (Figure 5.3.2 and Table 5.3.2). The complete figure of themes and nodes as implemented in NVivo 12 can be found in Appendix E. Finally, codes were clustered into themes to address the research question (iii) in the next section. Detailed analysis of each theme yielded from open coding follows in the next section. The following section discusses the details of the emerging themes: Theme 1 and Theme 2.

Figure 5.3.2. Themes and nodes (codes) as implemented in NVivo 12:

Table 5.3.2. Themes and codes

Themes	Codes
External factors	Competition Inflation Tax Other
Internal factors	Human resources Employee competencies Number of staff Salary

The researcher applied an open coding procedure to the open-ended answers from the above 28 participants. Several codes were revealed from the initial coding. Similar codes were clustered into two themes: Theme 1, external factors, and Theme 2, internal factors (Table 5.3.2.). However, a new theme (external factors) has been yielded from the open-ended questions (Table 5.3.1.a). The following sections briefly discuss the findings that resulted from the thematic analysis.

5.3.2.3. THEME 1 (EXTERNAL FACTORS)

Most of the respondents (Figure 5.3.2) mentioned that external factors have an impact on the components of working capital management (WCM). When respondents were asked in the questionnaires what other internal factors affect the WCM of small restaurants, respondents 1 and respondents 4-19 noted external factors (Table 5.3.2 a, b, and c).

When looking at the external factors like ‘Inflation’, respondent 1 (Table 5.3.2.a) said ‘Inflation e.g. suppliers increase the price of raw materials’ and affect the inventory.

Therefore, ‘suppliers increase the price of raw materials, e.g. onion price. Less purchase of raw materials to minimize waste’ (Respondent 1).

Based on the respondent’s response, there was no impact of inflation on the management of accounts receivable and accounts payable. The following Table 5.3.2.a demonstrates the response of the first respondent.

Table 5.3.2. a. The response of the first respondent

Respondent No	C1. Factor	C2. Inventory (INV)	C3. Accounts receivable (AR)	C4. Accounts payable (AP)
1	Inflation e.g. suppliers increase the price of raw materials.	Suppliers increase the price of raw materials e.g. onion price. Less purchase of raw materials to minimize waste.	No effect on receivables as restaurant cannot pass on the price increase on to their customers.	None

Similarly, respondents 4 to 19 claimed that inflation, tax, competitions, and other seasonal factors affect the WCM and its components. The following table (5.3.2.b) demonstrates the detailed responses of respondents 14, 16, 17, and 18.

Table 5.3.2. b. The responses of respondents 14-18

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
14	Inflation, tax, wages increase	Less purchase, low stock level	None	None
16	Increase prices	Reduced stock level	N/A	N/A
17	External: Inflation	Less purchasing and waste	N/A	N/A
18	External factors: Inflation, tax, salary increase	Less purchase, low stock levels	None	None

As can be identified from the above Table 5.3.2.(b), respondents 14, 16, 17, and 18 stated that ‘inflation’ has an impact on WCM of their restaurants. Two respondents indicated that ‘Inflation, tax, salary increase’ affect the inventory level such as ‘less purchase and low stock level’ (respondents 14 and 18). The other two respondents reported that ‘inflation’ has an impact on inventory. When they were asked how inflation affects inventory, one said, ‘reduced stock level’ (Respondent 16) and the other said, ‘Less purchasing and waste’ (Respondent 17). Meanwhile, all of them agreed that these factors did not affect the accounts receivable and accounts payable. Therefore, uncontrollable factors like inflation did not affect the accounts payable and accounts receivable. The following Table 5.3.2.c. shows the responses of respondents 4, 8, and 19.

Table 5.3.2.c. The responses of respondents 4, 8, and 19

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
4	External factors such as completions and inflation	Both inflation and competitions increase the need for better inventory management	Increasing prices on inventory does affect the sale prices, e.g. menu prices. Competition further can reduce receivables due to increased menu prices	Inflations and less receivables affect paying suppliers on agreed terms
8	External factors such as inflation and competition	Inflation and competitions result in effective inventory management to avoid short or excess stock levels	Cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices. No effects on customers and receivables (AR). AR can further be reduced due to promotional offers	Inventory cost and less receivables affect payables, e.g. late payments to suppliers
19	External factors: The economy, politics, competitors, and weather are uncontrollable factors that can influence WC	Some good rules of thumb for inventory turnover period, e.g. 3-4 times a month would help to maintain inventory effectively	Accounts receivable are not an important component of a restaurant	External factors affect accounts payable, e.g. seasonal factors affect profitability which results in late payments to suppliers

Respondents 4 and 8 stated that ‘Competition’ can have an impact on WCM of their restaurants.

When looking at the external factors like ‘Inflation and competitions’, one respondent said,

‘Inflation and competitions result in effective inventory management to avoid short or excess stock levels’ (respondent 8).

The same respondent went on to say, ‘Cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices. Therefore, no effects on customers and receivables.’

Answers from respondent 8 revealed that inflation and competition both affect the management of inventory and payables, e.g. late payment to suppliers. Cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices. Therefore, no effects on receivables. These answers of respondent 8 could, however, be contrasted with the answers of respondent 4, who again agreed that competitions affect accounts receivable and said:

‘Both inflation and competitions increase the need for better inventory management. Competition further can reduce receivables due to increased menu prices’ (respondent 4).

Thus, this answer is in line with the conclusions reached by Mun and Jang (2015), who argued that commodity costs reflect on menu prices.

One of the managers noted, ‘The economy, politics, competitors, and weather are uncontrollable factors that can influence WC. Shorter inventory turnover period, e.g. 3-4 times a month, would help to maintain inventory effectively’ (respondent 19).

This manager went on to say, ‘Accounts receivable are not an important component of a restaurant.’

All three respondents’ answers revealed that external factors such as the economy, politics, competitors, and weather can influence inventory management and accounts payable. These uncontrollable factors affect paying suppliers on agreed terms. Effective management of inventory, e.g. a shorter inventory turnover period, would help small restaurants to maintain their inventory effectively. Having looked at the external factors, the next section discusses Theme 2.

5.3.2.4. THEME 2: INTERNAL FACTORS

When respondents were asked in the questionnaires about what other internal factors affect WCM, respondents 2, 3, and 20-28 noted internal factors such as human resources, number of staff, wages, employee competencies, etc. Table 5.3.2.d demonstrates the responses of respondents 2 and 3.

Table 5.3.2. d. Respondents 2 and 3

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
2	Human resources/number of staff	More staff help to manage inventory, therefore less waste	More services results in more receivables from customers	High number of employees means more payables, therefore results in late payment to employees
3	Human resources/number of staff affect the business	More staff, better inventory management and reduced waste of stock	More staff are required to maintain customer service level. Extra staff salary would affect the receivables of business	Hiring and paying staff affects payables. Less profit

Two (2 and 3) managers noted that human resources affect the WC components. As one said, ‘More staff help to manage inventory, therefore less waste. More services results in more receivables from customers. High number of employees means more payables, therefore results in late payment to employees’ (respondent 2).

The other reported, ‘More staffs, better inventory management and reduced waste of stock’ (respondent 3). The same manager went on to say, ‘More staff are required to maintain customer

service level. Extra staff salary would affect the receivables of business. Hiring and paying staff affects payables. Less profit.’

Both managers (respondents 2 and 3) reported that human resources help to manage inventory and accounts receivable effectively. On the other hand, hiring and paying high numbers of employees affects payables.

Table 5.3.2.(e): Respondent 22

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
22	Employee competencies, skilled and trained staff	Employee efficiencies would affect the inventory in the restaurant. Trained employees can manage inventory more effectively. Therefore, less waste	Trained employees can contribute to better receivables by building long-term relationships with customers	Employee training affects the payables in the businesses as skilled and trained staff demand high wages

When respondents were asked in question C1 whether they have encountered any internal factor in managing working capital (other than the factors mentioned in the closed-ended questions), respondent 22 noted, ‘Employee competencies, skilled and trained staff would affect the inventory in the restaurant. Trained employees can manage inventory more effectively. Therefore, less waste.’

This manager went on to say, ‘Trained employees can contribute to better receivables by building long-term relationships with customers. Employee training affects the payables in the businesses as skilled and trained staff demand high wages’ (respondent 22).

Thus, this participant stated that employee competencies can influence inventory management, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. Additionally, demographic data (Table 4.2) revealed that this manager has been working at the restaurant for five years and obtained a Bachelor’s degree. This response reckons with a new internal factor, ‘employee competencies’, that affects the components of WCM.

Table 5.3.2. f: Respondents 23 and 24

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
23	Number of staff, wages, income tax	It affects taking credit. More staff, better inventory management	Highly important. More services, therefore more receivables from customers	Shorter payable days, e.g. paying employees weekly, helps to motivate employees. However, it depends on profit and costs
24	Human resources- The number of employees, wages	The employees can manage inventory effectively, therefore less waste and effective stock management	Better customer services and more receivables	More employees, more payables. Less profit

As can identified from the table, respondents 23 and 24 claimed that ‘Number of staff, wages’ affect the WCM.

One of the owners explained how ‘Number of staff, wages, and income tax’ affect the components of WC.

‘It affects taking credit. More staff, better inventory management highly important. More services, therefore more receivables from customers. Shorter payable days, e.g. paying employees weekly, helps to motivate employees. However, it depends on profit and costs’ (respondent 23).

Another manager reported that ‘The employees can manage inventory effectively, therefore less waste and effective stock management. Better customer services and more receivables, more employees, more payables. Less profit’ (respondent 24).

These answers of respondent 24 could, however, be compared with the answers of respondent 23. As one said, ‘Shorter payable days, e.g. paying employees weekly, helps to motivate employees. However, it depends on profit and costs’ (respondent 23). And the other reported, ‘more employees, more payables. Less profit’ (respondent 24). This contrast indicates that respondent 23 preferred shorter payable days. Thus, this respondent thinks paying employees early helps to motivate employees. A reduction in the numbers of days for accounts payable and a shorter working capital cycle improves the profitability of small restaurants. Further, participant 23 claimed that ‘Income tax’ affects the management of WCM.

Table 5.3.2. g. Respondents 20, 21, 25-18

No	C1. Factors	C2. INV	C3. AR	C4. AP
----	-------------	---------	--------	--------

20	Employees	Less inventory to reduce waste	Less receivables	Less profit or cash flow make it difficult to hire and retain good employees
21	Human resources, number of staff	More people, better inventory management, less waste	Less receivables	More salary, more payables, less profits
25	Human resources- number of staff	Efficient staff can manage inventory more effectively. Therefore, better inventory management and less waste	Staff management affects receivables, e.g. salary	Skilled staff demand high wages, therefore more payables and less profits
26	Number of people	Less employees, less stock management, and more waste	Less employees, less services, and less receivables	Less employees, less payables, and less profits
27	The number of staff	Less waste	Less receivables	Less profit
28	The number of workers	Less waste, more profit	Less receivables	More worker, more wages, therefore, less profits

Six of the owner-managers reported that human resources/ number of staff affect WCM in their restaurants. The following direct quotations confirm this:

‘Less inventory to reduce waste, Less receivables. Less profit or cash flow make it difficult to hire and retain good employees’ (respondent 20).

‘More people, better inventory management, less waste, less receivables. More salary, more payables, less profits’ (respondent 21).

‘Efficient staff can manage inventory more effectively. Therefore, better inventory management and less waste. Staff management affects receivables, e.g. salary. Skilled staff demand high wages, therefore more payables, less profits’ (respondent 25).

‘Less employees, less stock management, and more waste. Less employees, less services, and less receivables. Less employees, less payables, and less profits’ (respondent 26).

‘Less waste, less receivables, less profit’ (respondent 27).

‘Less waste, more profit. Less receivables. More workers, more wages, therefore less profits’ (respondent 28).

From the above direct quotations, it can be identified that all six respondents except respondent 25 reported ‘number of employees’ as an internal factor of their WCM. Number of employees can maintain inventory effectively, therefore there is less waste and more profit. Less employees affects customer services, therefore there is less receivables from customers. In addition, paying staff wages would increase payables. As a result, staff salary affects the profitability of small restaurants. Small restaurants cannot hire and manage the size of workforce because of high salaries. As a result, small business owners need to maintain an adequate amount of working capital for the smooth running of their businesses.

Furthermore, respondent 25 emphasized ‘employee competencies’ as an internal factor of WCM of business. This respondent is a graduate manager as well as a sole proprietor of his own business (Table 5.3.1.b). According to respondent 25, efficient staff can manage inventory effectively. However, skilled and efficient staff demand high salaries, which eventually affects payables and profitability. Thus, size is positively related with the profitability of businesses.

5.3.3. CONCLUSION/SUMMARY OF THE QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

In this chapter, the results of the qualitative findings have been discussed according to the themes and codes identified through the thematic analysis. The thematic categories mentioned in Table 5.3.2 have been discussed and analysed in relation to research question (iii), how the internal factors influence the components of WCM: inventory, accounts payable, and accounts receivable. The first theme explored that most of the respondents mentioned how external factors, e.g. inflation, competition, and taxation, have an impact on the components of working capital management (WCM). Based on the respondents’ responses, these uncontrollable factors can influence the management of inventory and payables, e.g. late payment to suppliers. The second theme identified that most of the respondents reported ‘number of employees’ as an internal factor of their WCM. Efficient employees can maintain the inventory and receivables effectively, therefore there is less waste and more profit. On the other hand, skilled and efficient staff demand high salaries, which eventually affect accounts payable and profitability. Qualitative findings reflect the opinions and experiences of both owners and managers of small food restaurants in the UK regarding the factors of WCM. Thus, qualitative analysis revealed the external factors as well as internal factors effecting WCM and its components. The next chapter involves discussion of quantitative and qualitative findings in the context of existing literature.

CHAPTER SIX

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.1. INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter covered the quantitative and qualitative findings. This chapter discusses the quantitative and qualitative findings from the previous chapter and analyses them in the context of existing literature. Analysis covers the discussion of the findings obtained from the mixed methods and comparison of the results back to the literature. Furthermore, the results from quantitative and qualitative analysis are combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). In the context of this study, approximately eight months were expended in the analysis of mixed data to ensure the robustness of the study. This chapter concludes with some implications that resulted from the mixed analysis and integration of the findings. Identification of the factors and findings of data analysis can be used by the owners and managers of small restaurants in the UK to improve their WCM and financial performance. The next section reviews, discusses, and integrates the mixed findings, summarizes the key findings, and relates the findings directly to the aims of the research as stated in the introduction chapter.

6.2. DISCUSSION OF QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

This section reviews the research questions to discuss the findings. The aim and objective of this piece of research which was mentioned in the introductory chapter of the study led to development of the research questions (See section 1.6 in chapter one). The research questions were developed from the integration of the concepts of working capital management, requirements of working capital management in restaurants, and the internal factors influencing WCM in small businesses. This integration helped in generating hypotheses that sought to answer research question 2. Finally, these hypotheses suggested a conceptual framework of WCM for small food restaurants which answers research question 4. Additionally, critical review of the concept of WCM and literature on the WCM of small businesses suggested the following research questions 1 and 3. This section covers the discussion and analysis of major findings that resulted from both quantitative data analysis (research questions 1 and 2) and qualitative data analysis (research question 3) in the

previous chapter. Further, this section discusses the conceptual framework (research question 4) that emanated based on existing literature in chapter two.

6.2.1. DISCUSSION OF QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS AND ANSWERS TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Quantitative data was analysed with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 25, in the previous chapter five. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, regression analysis, and chi-square were used in the previous chapter to analyse quantitative data.

Demographic findings (Table 5.2.1 in chapter five) revealed that most of the participants (66.7%) were managers and had completed GCSEs (62.5%). However, the majority of participants had 10 years of work experience (41.7%). Only 8.3% had 2 years of experience, and 11.1% of owner-managers were working in small food restaurants for 20 years. The importance of work experience in small restaurants is aligned with the findings of Agyei-Mensah (2012) and Orobio et al. (2016). Agyei-Mensah (2012) stated that work experience of managers is crucial to the effective management of WC. However, H1a and H1b (chapter five, Table 5.2.1) confirmed that small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on both practical and theoretical knowledge. These findings were accorded with those of Afrifa (2013); Orobio et al. (2013); Louw and Hall (2016); Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017), and were at odds with the findings of Agyei-Mensah (2012) and Orobio et al. (2016). The owners and managers of small businesses get knowledge and skills on WCM through prior experience and theoretical knowledge. Even though education and prior experience of managers are crucial factors in the management of WC components in the UK (Afrifa, 2013), demographic findings (Table 5.2.1 in chapter five) revealed that the importance of work experience was higher compared to education. Most of the owners and managers of small restaurants had completed GCSEs (62.5%).

The following sub-sections cover the discussion on major findings and answers to the research questions one, two and four.

6.2.1.1. RESEARCH QUESTION 1

'Why is working capital management important for small restaurants in the UK?'

To achieve the first objective based on the existing literature, this study investigated the main purpose for prioritizing WCM, the extent of WCM, and its components.

6.2.1.1.1. The extent of WCM in small food restaurants

As mentioned in the previous chapter, working capital management is crucial for small businesses (Baños-Caballero et al., 2014; Mun and Jang, 2015; Zariyawati et al., 2017; Louw et al., 2019). Agyei-Mensah (2012) identified that business size is positively related to WCM. The more an organization grows, the more important is working capital management. Small businesses require less working capital than a larger firm because of the small scale of operations (Garg, 2015), whereas a large business requires more investment in WC because of their large scale of operations (Adekunle and Sunday, 2015) and high volume of sales (Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016). On the other hand, another group of scholars (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016) argued that small-size businesses require more WC. As there is a limited amount of financial resources available to SMEs, these sizes of businesses invest more in WC to avoid the risk of financial scarcity (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013). As a result, the conflicting findings related to the requirements of WCM in SMEs suggested a need for further research. Therefore, based on existing literature, the previous chapter analysed the extent of WCM and its components in the context of small food restaurants in the UK. Findings revealed that 22% of small food restaurants manage working capital (WC) to a high extent and 45% of owner-managers agreed that their restaurants manage WC to some extent. Only 2% responded negatively and 5% of restaurants do not know how to manage their WC. Chi-square tests (Table 5.2.2.b) established statistically a positive association between the extent of working capital management and the number of employees in small restaurants. This result corroborates the findings of Agyei-Mensah (2012); Wasiuzzaman (2015); Afrifa and Padachi (2016). Their studies identified that in smaller businesses WCM is crucial. The more an organization grows, the more important is working capital management (Agyei-Mensah, 2012).

Furthermore, this researcher used requirements prioritization scales to analyse the requirement of WC components (INV, AR, and AP) in small food restaurants. Findings resulting from the frequency table show that in total (43+21) 64 owner-managers agreed with the statement that all three components: inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable are useful for their small restaurants. Thus, the above findings corroborate the findings of Baños-Caballero et al. (2014);

Adekunle and Sunday (2015), and Zariyawati et al. (2017). Their studies confirmed the importance of inventories and cash receivables management in small businesses. Small food restaurants need to maintain an optimal level of accounts receivable (AR), inventories (INV), and accounts payable (AP) (Baños-Caballero et al., 2014). Additionally, this study analysed whether the priority given to the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM is related to the work experience of the owner-managers of small restaurants. One-way ANOVA results show that there is a significant difference between the priority given to the components of WCM based on the work experience of owner-managers of small restaurants with $F=3.732$, $p<0.01$. This finding is consistent with the findings of Afrifa (2013), who identified that experienced managers could manage all components and aspects of WCM.

6.2.1.1.2. The usefulness of WCM in small food restaurants

Furthermore, this study sought to identify the usefulness of WCM in small food restaurants to answer research question 1. The most significant reason for considering WCM was that the effective management of stock levels reduces maintenance costs in small food restaurants (73.7%). Furthermore, 63.9% of owner-managers agreed that restaurants maintain an optimal level of working capital to increase the performance of their businesses. This usefulness of WCM has been identified as the second main reason for managing WC. These findings corroborate the findings of Agyei-Mensah (2012) and Mun and Jang (2015). In addition, this study identified that small businesses invest in WC to avoid the risk of financial shortage (58.4%). WCM helped 54.2% of small restaurants to meet financial obligations, e.g. debt financing. These results are in line with the findings of Tauringana and Afrifa (2013) and Zariyawati et al. (2017). Despite the potential benefit to be derived from the effective management of working capital, 30.6% of respondents did not know about the usefulness of WCM.

6.2.1.2. RESEARCH QUESTION 2

‘What internal factors influence WCM in small restaurants in the UK?’

To achieve the second objective and answer this question, the following hypotheses were developed in chapter three (Table 3.1) to evaluate whether there is a negative or positive relation between different variables. The findings produced from the testing of each hypothesis and sub-hypotheses that emanated from the main hypotheses are discussed from this point onwards.

6.2.1.2.1. MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES AND THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM

H₁: Management competencies are positively related with the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

This study developed two sub-hypotheses H_{1a} and H_{1b} to investigate the main hypothesis H₁.

H_{1a}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on the managerial theoretical knowledge.

H_{1b}: Small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on the managerial practical knowledge.

As presented in the previous chapter, the analysis of hypothesis H₁ revealed that management competencies are positively related with the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Thus, H₁ was accepted for this study. Spearman's (.234**, p = 0.048) and Pearson correlation (.314**, p = 0.007) led to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance (Table 5.2.4.3.a.). Furthermore, the regression analysis (Table 5.2.4.3. b, c, d) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of management competency and the requirement of WCM in small restaurants at the 99% level (t = 7.555, .000 < 0.01). The management competencies had a 69.9% (R² = 0.699) impact on the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants. The results relating to this finding are broadly discussed in chapter five of this research. This impact of management competencies on the WCM has been noted in previous studies (Afrifa, 2013; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017). Educated and experienced managers can manage all components of WCM practices.

The findings from tabulated statistics (Table 5.2.4.3.e) and chi-square $\chi^2(2) = .957^a$, supported hypothesis H_{1a} and H_{1b} confirming that small food restaurants give priority to WCM components based on both practical and theoretical knowledge. These findings were accorded with those of Afrifa (2013); Orobia et al. (2013); Louw and Hall (2016); Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017); and were at odds with the findings of Agyei-Mensah (2012) and Orobia et al. (2016). The owners and managers of small businesses get knowledge and skills on WCM through prior experience and theoretical knowledge. Even though education and prior experience of managers are crucial factors in the management of WC components in the UK (Afrifa, 2013) demographic findings (Table 5.2.1 in chapter five) revealed that the importance of work experience was higher compared to education. Most of the owners and managers of small restaurants had completed GCSEs (62.5%).

According to the Department for Business Innovation and Skills (BIS) (2015), management skills are relatively underdeveloped in many British SMEs. Consequently, small businesses strive to employ knowledgeable, experienced, and qualified people to manage working capital effectively both in developing (Enow and Kamala, 2016; Orumwense and Mwakipsile, 2017) and developed (Howorth and Westhead, 2003; Afrifa, 2013) countries. Thus, this result implies that in UK small businesses most importantly, small restaurants cannot afford to recruit educated people. Owners think that experienced staff will demand high salaries. According to a survey (Winterbotham et al., 2018), skills shortage is another challenge faced by 87,000 employers across the UK; in particular, there is scarcity of efficient and skilled chefs in the restaurant sectors. Future research incorporating employee skills would help to clarify the above findings.

6.2.1.2.2. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM

The following hypothesis has been developed to investigate the effect of business size on the requirement of WCM and components of the small restaurants. This study developed three sub-hypotheses H_{2a} , H_{2b} , and H_{2c} to investigate the effect of the business size on the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM.

H₂: The size of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants.

H_{2a}. There is a significant relationship between inventory management and the size of small food restaurants.

H_{2b}. There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the size of small food restaurants.

H_{2c}. There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the size of small food restaurants.

As identified in the previous chapter, the hypothesis H_2 was accepted as the business size is positively related with the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants. The regression analysis (Table 5.2.4.4. b, c, d) shows how the effect of business size reveals the percentage (19.9%) of variation in the requirements of WCM. F statistics ($.000 < 0.01$) and the regression coefficient value (β 0.446) indicates a positive correlation between the business size and the requirement of WCM

in small food restaurants at the 99% level ($t = 4.168$, $.000 < 0.01$). The complete data analysis and findings were broadly discussed in chapter five of this research.

This finding collaborates the previous literature on the business size and WCM (Azeem and Marsap, 2015; Orobia et al., 2016). As the businesses grow, the need for managing working capital becomes relevant.

6.2.1.2.2.1. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND THE INVENTORY PERIOD (H2a)

As can be identified from the findings chapter, 61 owner-managers agreed that their business size has an impact on inventory management, and they review and control inventory (Table 5.2.4.4. c). Similarly, chi-square statistics $\chi^2(2) = .957^a$, supported hypothesis H2a confirming that the association between inventory management and the size of business is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05 (Table 5.2.4.4.d). This result is consistent with the findings of Baker et al. (2017) and Orumwense and Mwakipsile (2017), and contrary to the finding of Agyei-Mensah (2012) and Orobia et al. (2013). Their studies revealed that small businesses never review stock levels, stock turnover and stock reorder levels (Agyei-Mensah, 2012). However, the above studies investigated the effect of business size on inventory management in the context of developing countries. On the other hand, the financial structure of small food restaurants operating in the UK is different than those are operating in developing countries. Consequently, because of country-specific factors (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014), the effect of business size on inventory management is different in the UK. In the restaurant industry, maintaining raw materials effectively is one of the best ways to manage inventory. Future research incorporating country-specific factors would help to clarify these results.

6.2.1.2.2.2. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNT RECEIVABLES MANAGEMENT (H2b)

Chi-square statistics 30.029a and 15.916^a with a p-value = .000 as shown in chapter five, Table 5.2.4.4. (f) indicate that the association between receivables management and the size of business is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, H2b is accepted. This result is consistent with the findings of Paul and Boden (2011) and Mun and Jang (2015). Small firms are required to offer more generous credit terms to their customers, therefore extending the AR period to encourage customers to spend more. These outcomes are contradictory with the results of Agyei-

Mensah (2012); Azami and Tabar (2016); Baker et al. (2017). These studies elaborated that the size of businesses has no impact on accounts receivable management. Agyei-Mensah (2012) identified poor AR management in Ghana. However, this result was analysed in the context of a developing country. On the other hand, the UK exhibits a variety of restaurants with a multicultural base of customers (Crick et al., 2016). Small restaurants in the UK are facing growing competition from their rivals. Managing restaurant businesses is very difficult for small business owners due to the highly competitive environment. As a result, effective management of AR, computerized systems, and extending the AR period to encourage customers to spend more are crucial in the context of the UK.

6.2.1.2.2.3. THE SIZE OF BUSINESS AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE MANAGEMENT (H2c)

The results from the cross-tabulation as shown in Table 5.2.4.4. (g) indicate that business size has an impact on AP management, and they prefer to pay suppliers early, therefore small restaurants do not negotiate with their suppliers to extent credit periods. Pearson chi-square statistics 14.155a and the p-value 0.001, 25.826a with the p-value = 0.000: both values indicate that the association between AP management and business size is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05 (Table 5.2.4.4. h). These outcomes are contradictory with the results of Azami and Tabar (2016). They elaborated that there was no significant relationship between company size and the components of WCM. This result is consistent with the results of Mun and Jang (2015) and Enow and Kamala (2016). They identified that small businesses had a lower bargaining power in terms of credit purchasing with suppliers. Small food restaurants in the UK rely significantly on suppliers' credit for managing cash flow and business operations. As a result, small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain strong relationship with suppliers. Banks and investors consider small businesses as high-risk borrowers due to their insufficient assets, vulnerability to economic uncertainty, and market fluctuations (Padachi et al., 2012). Therefore, small businesses have limited access to capital through external financing (Zariyawati et al., 2016; Wapshott and Mallett, 2018). Small restaurants mostly depend on internal financing such as owner financing, supplier credit, etc. Nevertheless, shortage of employees is the main factor that inhibits small businesses from managing accounts payable effectively (Enow and Kamala, 2016). Considering efficient employees as an internal factor of WCM would add an agenda for future research.

6.2.1.2.3. LEVERAGE AND THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM (H₃)

The following hypotheses were tested in chapter five to investigate the effect of leverage on the requirement of WCM and components of small restaurants. This study developed three sub-hypotheses H_{3a}, H_{3b}, and H_{3c} to investigate the effect of the leverage on the components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM.

H₃: Leverage of business is positively related with the requirements of WCM.

H_{3a}: There is a significant relationship between inventory level and the debt level of small food restaurants.

H_{3b}: There is a significant relationship between accounts receivable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

H_{3c}: There is a significant relationship between accounts payable and the debt level of small food restaurants.

Correlation and regression were used to investigate the hypothesis H₃. As shown in Table 5.2.4.5. (a), Spearman's (.354**, p = 0.002) and Pearson correlation (.358**, p = 0.002) led to similar conclusions regarding statistical significance. Thus, hypothesis H₃ is accepted because leverage has significant positive effect on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants.

The regression analysis (Table 4.2.5.3. a, b, c) shows how the effect of leverage reveals the level (6.0%) of variation in the requirements of WCM. Further, the regression coefficient value (β .245) indicates a positive correlation between the leverage and the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants (t = 4.168, .0038 < 0.05). This finding is in line with the results of Valipour (2012) and Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014). Small businesses with high levels of leverage are required to maintain more working capital than other sizes of businesses. Elbadry (2018) found that SMEs with lower levels of internal finance depend on debt finance. Thus, this situation forces a business to manage its working capital efficiently. According to empirical research, the relationship between leverage and WCM is usually negative (Wasiuzzaman and Arumugam, 2013; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016). On the other hand, R square (0.006) results as discussed above revealed that leverage had only a 6.0% impact on the requirement of WCM. Further analysis (the frequency Table 5.2.4.5. e) identified that small food restaurants rely significantly on owner financing (91.7%) rather than debt financing, whereas only 12.5% of respondents reported that they rely on

debt financing. As a result, due to lower dependence on debt financing, the regression results identified a lower impact (0.06%) on the requirement of WCM. This result is consistent with the findings of Elbadry (2018).

6.2.1.2.3.1. LEVERAGE AND INVENTORY PERIOD (**H_{3a}**)

Hypothesis H_{3a} was tested in the previous chapter by using cross-tabulation and chi-square (chapter five, Table 5.2.4.5. f, g) to investigate the effect of leverage on the inventory level. 15 respondents agreed to both statements that leverage has an impact on WCM, and the high level of debt causes the inventory holding period to decrease. No significant association was found between INV holding period and the debt level (X^2 3.149a, p-value .533). Therefore, hypothesis H_{3a} was rejected. No evidence was found for an association between INV and the leverage of small food restaurants. This finding is aligned with the findings of Manoori and Muhammad (2012) and Qurashi and Zahoor (2017). Their studies identified an insignificant relationship between WCM components and debt ratio. Similarly, Zariyawati et al. (2017) stated that there is no relation between debt and inventory level as small restaurants cannot avoid investment in inventory. Small restaurants mostly sell foods; therefore, a high amount of raw materials is compulsory for daily operations.

6.2.1.2.3.2. LEVERAGE AND ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE (H_{3b})

Pearson chi-square statistics 16.289^a and the p-value .003 indicate that the association between the AR period and the debt level is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. H_{3c} is accepted. Further cross-tabulated statistics revealed that 29 respondents agreed with the statement that leverage has an impact on the WCM requirement, and they reduce debt level by collecting payments from customers early. Thus, small food restaurants prefer collecting payments from customers on time because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively (Mun and Jang, 2015). Koralun-Bereźnicka (2014) identified that the way leverage affects WCM and its compounds is determined by country-specific factors. Future research combining country specific factors with internal factors would explain this association appropriately.

6.2.1.2.3.3. LEVERAGE AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE (H3c)

As identified in the previous chapter from the cross-tabulation statistics (Table 5.2.4.5.j), only 11 owner-managers agreed that leverage has an impact on the WCM requirement, and they seek to expand credit terms with suppliers because of high levels of debt. 31 respondents do not know whether there is a relation between the payables period and debt level. No significant association was found via Pearson between the AP period and the debt level (X^2 3.826a and the p-value .430, Table 5.2.4.5.k). Therefore, H_{3c} is rejected. These results are aligned with the findings of Gill (2010); Manoori and Muhammad (2012); Qurashi and Zahoor (2017). Their studies identified an insignificant relationship between WCM components and debt ratio. As can be observed from Table 5.2.4.5. (e), small food restaurants rely significantly on owner financing (91.7%) rather than debt financing (12.5%). This result can be compared with the above association between AP and leverage (Table 5.2.4.5.j). Comparison between two tables (Table 5.2.4.5. e. and Table 5.2.4.5. j) reveal that the relation between AP and the leverage of the small food restaurants is insignificant. They reduce debt level by collecting receivables from customers early and paying their suppliers on time rather than expanding credit terms with suppliers.

It can be identified from the above relationship between leverage and WCM components that small restaurants with high levels of leverage decrease inventory days, account collection periods, and payables periods with suppliers because of high levels of debt. As working capital is an internal source of finance, it can be used as an alternative to external sources of finance (Abbadi and Abbadi, 2013). Small restaurants mostly depend on internal financing such as owner financing rather than supplier credit (Table 5.2.4.5. e). Banks and investors consider small businesses as high-risk borrowers due to their insufficient assets, vulnerability to economic uncertainty, and market fluctuations (Padachi et al., 2012). Small restaurants mostly sell foods; therefore, high a amount of raw materials is compulsory for daily operations. Food quality is crucial to maintaining good customer relationships and services. Therefore, small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain a strong relationship with suppliers (Mun and Jang, 2015).

6.2.1.2.4. THE PROFITABILITY AND THE REQUIREMENTS OF WCM (H₄)

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the findings of the Spearman's (.344^{**}, $p = 0.003$) and Pearson correlation (.400^{**}, $p = 0.000$) identified that profitability has a significant positive impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. The regression analysis (Table 5.4.2.4.4. a, b, c) reveals the level of variation (10.1%) that is caused by profitability in the requirements of WCM (dependent variable). Furthermore, the significant level of F statistics ($.007 < 0.01$) shows that the model is highly significant at the 99% level. The regression coefficient value (β 0.317) indicates a positive correlation between the effect of profitability and the requirement of WCM in small restaurants. These findings were in line with the argument provided by Atseye et al. (2015); Garg (2015); Padachi and Afrifa (2016); Bhatia and Srivastava (2016). As stated by Tauringana and Afrifa (2013), an optimal level of working capital is essential to maximize the profitability of small businesses. The finding is contrary to the findings of Alsie and Arora (2016) and Lyngstadaas and Berg (2016), who reported a negative association between the components of WCM and profitability of SMEs. Furthermore, it can be scrutinized from the above R square that the profitability has only 10.1% impact on the requirement of WCM in small food restaurants. Therefore, to investigate the lower level of the impact of profitability on WCM, this study developed the following hypotheses by placing components of WCM into sub-groups.

H_{4a}: A statistically significant relationship exists between the inventory holding period and the profitability of the small food restaurants.

H_{4b}: An insignificant relationship exists between the accounts receivable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

H_{4c}: An insignificant relationship exists between the accounts payable period and the profitability of small food restaurants.

6.2.1.2.4.1. PROFITABILITY AND INVENTORY PERIOD (H_{4a})

The results from the cross-tabulated output as shown in chapter five (Table 5.2.4.6. e) identified that 47 owner-managers agreed that the inventory holding period is important for the profitability of their businesses. They also think that profitability influences the WCM requirement in their restaurants. The chi-square statistics (18.498a and the p -value = .000) confirmed that the

association between the inventory holding period and profitability is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. H_{4a} is accepted. This result is in line with the findings of Louw and Hall (2016) and contrary to the findings of Tauringana and Afrifa (2013). Tauringana and Afrifa (2013) identified that inventory (INV) is not important for the profitability of SMEs. An opposite point of view argued that inventory management has the strongest statistically significant impact on a firm's profitability (Louw and Hall, 2016). Excessive inventory holding policy may surge inventory holding costs, whereas a reduced amount of inventory may cause an inventory stockout problem (Bhatia and Srivastava, 2016). This is probably because of the different types of inventory requirements by different types of businesses. In the small food restaurant industry, food quality is crucial; therefore maintaining inventory, e.g. raw materials, effectively is one of the best ways to enhance the profitability of the business. Future research investigating inventory management for small food restaurants would help to clarify these findings.

6.2.1.2.4.2. PROFITABILITY AND ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE PERIOD (H_{4b})

The cross-tabulation output shown in the previous chapter (Table 5.2.4.6.g), indicates that only 30 owner-managers agreed that collecting payments from customers early is important for the profitability of their businesses. 26 respondents do not know whether profitability influences the accounts receivable (AR) in their restaurants. Further statistical test (Pearson chi-square 4.245a and the p-value = .374) reveals an insignificant relation between AR and the profitability at the 0.05 level. This finding was consistent with the findings of Tauringana and Afrifa (2013) and Duru et al. (2014), but was at odds with the results of Mbawuni et al. (2016). Mbawuni et al. (2016) identified a positive association between AR and the profitability of firms. However, increasing AR days may result in opportunity cost of cash tied-up in AR. On the other hand, reducing AR days to collect AR early from customers increases profitability (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013). Shorter AR periods help SMEs to release funds from their customers to use elsewhere. Thus, reducing accounts receivable days and collecting payment from their customers early increases the profitability of this industry. Louw et al. (2019) revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail, e.g. restaurant, industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Therefore, accounts receivable is found to be insignificant in the restaurant industry. Restaurant businesses can generate extra cash from business operation sooner than other

industries; therefore, restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively (Mun and Jang, 2015).

6.2.1.2.4.3. PROFITABILITY AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE PERIOD (H4c)

The findings from the cross-tabulated Table 5.2.4.6. (i), as shown in chapter five, revealed that only 19 owner-managers agreed that late payment to suppliers is profitable for their businesses. 26 respondents disagreed with the statement, whereas 12 owner-managers did not know whether late payment to suppliers was profitable or not. Further statistical test (chi-square 6.740^a and the p-value = .150) revealed that the association between accounts payable period and the profitability is insignificant at the 0.05 level (Table 4.2.5.4. j). Thus, small restaurants pay suppliers on time as they think late payment is not profitable for their businesses. This result is consistent with the results of Pais and Gama (2015) and Enow and Kamala (2016), and contrary to the findings of Louw and Hall (2016). As Pais and Gama (2015) pointed out, excessive liabilities may have a negative impact on the profitability of SMEs. Small businesses purchase on cash basis and pay their creditors on time to take the benefits of discounts (Enow and Kamala, 2016). According to their findings, 92% of businesses purchased on cash and most businesses did not negotiate with their suppliers to extend credit periods. On the other hand, Louw and Hall (2016) identified a positive correlation between accounts payable and the profitability of firms. Increasing trade payables improved the profitability of South African retail firms.

Previous research (Tauringana and Afrifa, 2013; Atseye et al., 2015; Enow and Kamala, 2016) shows significant differences between WCM and the profitability of small businesses operating in different countries. As stated by Orobia et al, (2016), small business lacks the resources to manage the components of WC effectively. Accordingly, the risk of late payment increases due to late invoicing. Small businesses operating in emerging economies tend to neglect AP management. They use manual record-keeping methods to manage their accounts payable (Mensah-Agyei, 2012). In the UK, small food restaurants pay their creditors on time to take the benefits of discounts. Mun and Jang (2015) identified that paying by the due date or early is one way to maintain strong relationships with suppliers. Future research investigating the strategic link

between accounts payable management and the supply chain for small restaurants would clarify this relationship further.

6.2.1.3. RESEARCH QUESTION 4

‘How can a framework of the determinant’s factors be developed to enhance the financial performance of small restaurants the UK?’

To achieve the research objective three and answer to the research question four, this study developed a conceptual framework in chapter three (Table 3.1). The main aim of the conceptual framework was to investigate the internal factors influencing WCM and its components in small food restaurants in the UK. The existing literature (chapter three, Table 3.2) and the arguments based on the four internal factors: management competencies, size of business, leverage, and profitability, the requirements of WCM in small businesses and the main hypotheses of this research suggested the conceptual framework for this study. Development of this framework was based on the previous empirical researchers as summarized in chapter three, Table 3.2. Furthermore, the conceptual framework visually represents the dependent variable (the requirement of WCM), the independent variables (the four internal factors), and four main hypotheses: H1, H2, H3, and H4 for this study. By understanding the relation between the factors and WCM, the owner-managers of small businesses will be able to manage working capital efficiently. It evident that efficient management of working capital increases financial performance of a business (Micheal et al., 2017). The conceptual framework and the findings (chapter five) suggest how the impact of internal factors on the requirements of WCM can be an effective tool in enhancing the financial performance of small food restaurants in the UK.

.

6.2.2. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section takes the qualitative findings from the previous chapter (chapter five) and analyse the findings according to the empirical evidence (chapter two) relating the factors that influence the components of WCM: inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. As can be seen from the qualitative findings, 28 respondents answered the open-ended questions. Demographic findings (Table 5.3.1.b) revealed that the majority of participants were owner-managers of small

food restaurants. 14 respondents (50%) have completed GCSEs. The collected open-ended responses were imported in NVivo 12 to identify codes and themes nodes. The detailed explanations of these themes with reference to the research question and appropriate literature are discussed in the following sub-sections.

6.2.2.1. RESEARCH QUESTION 3

‘How do the internal factors influence the components of WCM in the small restaurant in the UK?’

To explore people’s opinion in response to research question 2, respondents were further asked four open-ended questions (chapter five, Table 5.3.1. a.: questions C1-C4 in the questionnaires) to achieve the research objective and answer the above research question 3. The qualitative data derived from the open-ended answers were analysed according to the themes and codes (chapter five, Table 5.3.2.) identified through the thematic analysis. As a result, two main themes: Theme 1 and Theme 2 were identified. The results were produced from the thematic analysis and can be found in the previous chapter. The brief discussion around the two themes follows in the next sections.

6.2.2.1.1. THEME 1: EXTERNAL FACTORS

Thematic analysis revealed that external factors such as inflation, competitors, and taxation have an impact on the components of WCM (Table 5.3.2 a, b, and c). The majority of the respondents reported that these uncontrollable factors can influence the management of inventory and accounts payable, e.g. late payments to suppliers. Based on the respondents’ responses (chapter five: Table 5.3.2.a, b), inflation affects inventory management, e.g. price of raw materials. All of them agreed that uncontrollable factors like inflation did not affect accounts payable and accounts receivable. This result is aligned with the result of Vijayalakshmi and Bansal (2013), who reported that price of raw materials, competitors, and weather can influence inventory management and accounts payable, e.g. paying suppliers on agreed terms. According to respondent 8 (table 5.3.2.c), cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices, therefore there are no effects on accounts receivable. This finding is in line with the results of Louw et al. (2019), who confirmed the importance of inventory management and accounts payable management in the retail industry. According to Susskind and Spies (2011), small restaurants require a shorter inventory turnover period than other

industry as raw food stocks are highly perishable. Accounts receivable are not an important component of restaurants.

However, this answer of respondent 8 can be contrasted with the answers of respondent 4, who noted that competition further can reduce receivables due to increased menu prices. This answer is in line with the conclusions reached by Mun and Jang (2015), who argued that commodity costs reflect on menu prices. According to Mun and Jang (2015), managing a restaurant businesses is very difficult for the small business owners due to a highly competitive environment; as a result, restaurants need to increase food quality and menu prices in uncertain economic conditions where commodity costs increase. Thus, inflation has no effect on accounts receivable, as inventory cost does not reflect on menu prices, whereas competition affects receivables due to increased menu prices.

All respondents' answers revealed that external factors such as inflation, competitors, taxation, and weather can influence inventory management and accounts payable. These uncontrollable factors affect paying suppliers on agreed terms. Effective management of inventory, e.g. a shorter inventory turnover period, would help small restaurants to maintain inventory effectively. These answers from respondents are also supported by Atseye et al. (2015) and Vijayalakshmi and Bansal (2013). The price of raw materials (Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013) and tax rate (Atseye et al., 2015) were the important exogenous or external factors to the firm and cannot be controlled. In contrast, all the respondents (1, 8, 14, 16, 17, 18, and 19) except respondent 4 confirmed that accounts receivable are not an important component of WCM in restaurants. Thus, the result from theme 1 revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Even though external factors, e.g. inflation, cannot be controlled (Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013), restaurant businesses can generate extra cash from business operation sooner than other industries (Mun and Jang, 2015). Therefore, uncontrollable factors like inflation did not affect the accounts payable and accounts receivable. The next section discusses theme 2.

6.2.2.1.2. THEME 2: INTERNAL FACTORS

As shown in chapter five (Table 5.3.2. d, f.), the results from theme 2 revealed that internal factors such as human resources, number of staff, wages, employee competencies, etc. influence the WCM components in small food restaurants. Efficient employees can maintain the inventory effectively,

therefore there is less waste and more profit. To some extent, the number of staff or human resources is related to firm size. Respondents most probably claimed their business size as an internal factor of WCM through the number of employees. As respondent 22 noted, trained employees can contribute to better receivables by building long-term relationships with customers. Employee training affect the payables in the business, as skilled and trained staff demand high wages. This participant reckons with a new internal factor ‘employee competency’, that influences inventory management, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. This result is in line with the result of Qurashi (2017), who identified that small businesses can not hire highly professional human resources as skilled and efficient employees demand a high salary. As a result, less employees provide less services and generate less profits. Small businesses like restaurants cannot afford to hire more employees because of high salary costs. As a result, small business owners need to maintain an adequate amount of working capital for the smooth running of their businesses. For example, excess amount inventory in stock increases the cost of maintenance, whereas a low level of inventory increases the risk of running out of stock and losing customers (Azami and Tabar, 2016). Efficient staff can manage inventory effectively.

According to respondent 23 (Table 5.3.2.f.), paying employees weekly helps to motivate employees. And the other reported ‘more employees, more payables. Less profit’ (respondent 24). This contrast indicates that respondent 23 thinks paying employees early helps to motivate employees. This idea is in line with the conclusions reached by Pais and Gama (2015), who identified that a reduction in numbers of days of inventory, accounts receivable and accounts payable and a shorter working capital cycle improves the profitability of small business. On the other hand, skilled and efficient staff demand high salaries, which eventually affects payables and profitability. Even though most of the external factors of WCM reported by the owner-managers of small food restaurants were consistent with the previous research in the field, the internal factor ‘human resources’ has not been discussed in the literature. Consequently, this internal factor identifies a possible gap in the literature. Except for the above issue, the results reflect the opinions and experiences of both owners and managers of small food restaurants in the UK regarding the factors of WCM. The section also came up with external factors of WCM. This study is interested only in the internal factors affecting WCM of small restaurants. Thus, qualitative analysis revealed that external factors as well as internal factors influence WCM and its components. Incorporating

external factors in future research would further clarify these findings. Therefore, a recommendation or gap has been identified for future research.

6.2.3. INTEGRATION OF MIXED FINDINGS

Finally, in this section, the results from quantitative and qualitative analysis are combined to identify the complete and accurate answer of the research problem. Quantitative findings identified a positive relation between the extent of WCM and the number of employees which confirms the importance of work experience in small restaurants. Similarly, the second theme identified that the majority of the respondents reported ‘number of employees’ as an internal factor of their WCM.

Quantitative findings identified a positive effect of business size (19.9%) on the requirements of WCM components (INV, AR, and AP) in small food restaurants. Qualitative findings revealed that small businesses like restaurants cannot afford to hire more employees because of high salary costs. Efficient and skilled human resources can manage all components of WCM. Thus, size of business has an impact on the components of WCM.

Thematic analysis revealed that uncontrollable factors: inflation, competition, and taxation can influence the management of inventory and payables, e.g. late payment to suppliers. Cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices. Therefore, there are no effects on receivables. Similar results were identified from the quantitative findings. Small food restaurants prefer collecting payments from customers on time because of the cash sales nature of the industry. An insignificant relation between the account collection period and profitability has been identified. Therefore, restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively. Both quantitative and qualitative analysis revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry.

Qualitative analysis identified that employee efficiency is positively related with the profitability of small food restaurants. Efficient employees can maintain inventory, receivables, and payables effectively. More employees provide more services and generate more profits, which eventually affect accounts payable and profitability. Furthermore, small business owners need to maintain inventory effectively for the smooth running of their businesses. Excess amounts of inventory in stock increases maintenance cost, whereas a low level of inventory increases the risk of running out of stock and losing customers. Similar results confirmed from the quantitative findings that

small restaurants prioritize inventory management, as effective management of stock (INV) helps to reduce the maintenance costs in their restaurants. Small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain strong relationships with suppliers.

6.3. IMPLICATIONS OF MIXED FINDINGS

The implications of mixed findings suggest that apart from management competencies, size, leverage, and profitability, 'number of employees or human resources' is an important internal factor which affects the extent of WCM in small restaurants. Even though the number of employees is a component of business size, concentration should be given on this internal factor as to reflect the opinions and experiences of both owners and managers of small food restaurants in the UK. Small restaurants mostly depend on internal financing such as owner financing and supplier credits. Restaurants owner cannot afford to hire more highly qualified employees because of high salary costs. As a result, most owner-managers had completed GCSEs. Notwithstanding, small restaurants prioritize WCM components based on managerial theoretical and practical knowledge. The findings from the mixed analysis concludes that efficient employees can maintain the inventory, receivables, and payables effectively. Small restaurants prioritize inventory management, as effective management of stock (INV) helps to reduce the maintenance costs in their restaurants. Small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain strong relationships with suppliers. Both quantitative and qualitative analysis revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. Further mixed findings revealed that both external factors and internal factors influence the requirement of WCM and its components. This study investigated only the internal factors affecting WCM of small restaurants. However, embedding open-ended questions within a survey questionnaire helped the researcher to gain better insight into the factors and deeper understanding of the research problem.

6.4. CONCLUSION

This chapter reviews, discusses, and integrates the mixed findings, summarizes the key findings and relates the findings directly to the aims of the research as stated in the introduction chapter. The next chapter discusses the conclusions, critical reflection, limitations, and weaknesses of the research, followed by recommendations for future studies.

Chapter 7

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1. INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter discussed and analysed the findings of the research. This chapter concludes the study and provide a reflective summary of the entire study. The structure of this chapter can be found in Figure 7.1. This summary captures the contents of all the seven chapters including a summary of the findings and conclusions reached therein with some contributions to knowledge and practices. This chapter will review research objectives identified earlier in the introductory chapter. Furthermore, limitations and recommendations for future research are discussed in the later sections of this chapter. Finally, this study provides a critical reflective summary. The next section summarizes the entire research including major findings that emanated from quantitative and qualitative data analysis in chapters five and six.

7.2. SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH

This research has been divided into seven main chapters (chapter one, Figure 1.1. outlines the structure of the thesis). Figure 7.2 draws together a summary of the study in its entirety. The introduction chapter covered background context of the study, statement of the research problem, rationale of the study, research objectives, contribution, and overview of the research. Chapter two critically reviews the literature on the concept of WCM, the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants, and factors affecting WCM that underpins the research. The literature review chapter addressed the first and third objectives of the research. These objectives will be reviewed in the next section of this chapter. Chapter three covered the development of the conceptual framework emanating from the literature review, followed by development of the four main hypotheses as set out in Figure 3.1. Philosophical underpinnings of the research, research paradigms, embedded mixed research approaches, research strategy, mixed methods research design, and data collection techniques are discussed in chapter four, including justification for choosing mixed method analysis. Findings and analysis were divided into two chapters: chapter five and chapter six. Quantitative and qualitative findings were presented in chapter five. The key highlights of the quantitative findings include the analysis of the research hypotheses by using descriptive statistics,

correlation, and multiple regression. Qualitative data analysis includes thematic analysis of the open-ended answers. Chapter six covers an extensive discussion of the research findings, followed by integrating quantitative and qualitative findings to identify the comprehensive and precise answer of the research problem. Finally, chapter seven contains the review of research objectives and the contribution of the research findings. Further, this chapter provides a summary of the entire research, limitations of the research, and recommendations for future research. The following flow chart outlines the structure of chapter seven.

Figure 7.1: The structure of chapter seven: conclusion

7.2.1. REVIEW OF RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this study was to evaluate the internal factors affecting the requirement of WCM of small food restaurants in the UK. The integration of the literature regarding the concept of WCM and investigation of the internal factors that contribute towards WC investment in small businesses generated three research objectives for this study. These objectives are reviewed below.

7.2.1.1. Objective 1

‘Critical review of the concept of working capital management (WCM)’

A critical review of the concept of WCM and literature on the extent of WCM in small businesses suggests that effective management of working capital is crucial for small businesses (Mun and Jang, 2015; Atseye et al., 2015; Wasiuzzaman, 2015; Afrifa and Padachi, 2016; Baños-Caballero et al., 2014; Zariyawati et al., 2017; Louw et al., 2019). Therefore, to achieve this objective based on the existing literature, this study examined the usefulness of WCM to identify the main purpose for prioritizing WCM and its components in small food restaurants. Additionally, literature on the extent of WCM were analysed by using descriptive statistical tools, e.g. frequency and chi-square tests. Association between the extent of working capital management by small restaurants based on the number of employees was further examined to provide the robustness to the findings.

7.2.1.2. Objective 2

‘To evaluate the internal factors affecting WCM of small food restaurants in the UK.’

To achieve this objective, hypotheses developed in chapter three (section 3.5.1 Hypothesis development) were analysed by using Pearson correlation, Spearman’s rho, and regression analysis. The key feature in the evaluation of this objective was the internal factors affecting the requirements of WCM and its components (Mansoori and Muhammad, 2012; Vijayalakshmi and Bansal, 2013; Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014; Adekunle and Sunday, 2015; Azami and Tabar, 2016; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017). Chapter five provides comprehensive analysis of findings, while chapter six covers extensive discussion of the research findings.

7.2.1.3. Objective 3

‘To develop a conceptual framework for the research based on the relevant literature on WCM.’

To achieve this objective, literature was reviewed in chapter two to form a conceptual framework for this study. The development of this framework was based on the review of the relevant literature on the concepts of WCM, components of WCM, and the internal factors that influence the WCM requirements of small businesses (Orobia et al., 2013; Lauw and Hall, 2016; Qurashi and Zahoor, 2017; Elbadry, 2018). Finally, the conceptual framework (Figure 3.1.) was emanated from the literature review, upon which the investigation of the entire research was framed. A summary of how previous empirical researchers contributed to the formulation of the framework can be found in chapter three, Table 3.2.

7.2.2. THE SUMMARY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

Quantitative analysis revealed that most of the owner-managers had completed GCSEs and educational qualification was not important in small food restaurants (Table 5.2.1.). Positive relation between the extent of WCM and the number of employees was identified, confirming the importance of work experience in small restaurants (Table 5.2.2.B). WCM is crucial for small food restaurants as effective management of stock (INV) helps to reduce the maintenance cost in their restaurants (Table 5.2.3.) The main four hypotheses confirmed the positive effect of management competencies (69.9%) (Table 5.2.4.3.b,c,d), business size (19.9%) (Table 5.2.4.4.b,c,d), leverage (6%) (Table 5.2.4.5.b,c,d) and profitability (10.1%) (Table 5.2.4.6. b, c, d) on the requirements of WCM in small food restaurants. Even though most of the owner-mangers were holding the highest educational qualification of GCSE, they agreed that management competencies such as managerial practical knowledge and theoretical knowledge both are important for the management of WCM components in small restaurants (Table 5.2.4.3. e. f).

The business size has a significant impact on all three components (INV, AR, and AP) of WCM (Table 5.2.4.4.). Leverage has significant impact on accounts receivable. Small food restaurants collect payments from customers on time to reduce debt level. Leverage did not impact the stock management and accounts payable of small food restaurants (Table 5.2.4.5). Small restaurants

cannot avoid investment in inventory as they mostly sell foods; therefore, a high amount of raw materials is compulsory for daily operations. In the restaurant industry, food quality is crucial to maintain good customer relationships and services. Therefore, small food restaurants pay their suppliers early to maintain strong relationships with suppliers. A significant relationship between inventory and accounts payable with the profitability of small food restaurants has been identified (Table 5.2.4.6). On the other hand, an insignificant relation between the account collection period and profitability has been identified. Small food restaurants prefer collecting payments from customers on time. Therefore, restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable effectively.

For qualitative analysis, this research adopted thematic analysis using NVivo 12 software. Open-ended answers were textually analysed for the in-depth understanding of the internal factors of WCM and implication for action. Two themes were identified: external factors and internal factors. Participants were asked in the questionnaires what other internal factors affect the WCM of small restaurants. Most of the respondents mentioned external factors, e.g. inflation, competition, and taxation, as having an impact on the components of working capital management (WCM) (Table 5.3.2. a, b, c). Based on the respondents' responses, these uncontrollable factors can influence the management of inventory and payables, e.g. late payment to suppliers. Cost of inventory does not reflect on menu prices. Therefore, there are no effects on receivables. This study revealed that the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the retail industry because of the cash sales nature of the industry. The second theme identified that the majority of the respondents reported 'number of employees' as an internal factor of their WCM (Table 5.3.2. d, e, f, g). Efficient employees can maintain the inventory and receivables effectively. Less employees provide less services and generate less profits, which eventually affect accounts payable and profitability. Thus, employee efficiency is positively related with the profitability of businesses. Small businesses like restaurants cannot afford to hire more employees because of high salary costs. Due to efficient human resources, small businesses cannot manage all components of WCM. Furthermore, small business owners need to maintain inventory effectively for the smooth running of their businesses. Excess amounts of inventory in stock increases maintenance costs, whereas a low level of inventory increases the risk of running out of stock and losing customers.

7.2.3. CONCLUSION

The volume of literature (Table 3.2, empirical researchers) investigated WCM in the context of the UK, but no research has yet been conducted in relation to the internal factors determining the requirements of WCM in small UK businesses, most importantly small food restaurants. Most of the studies related to the WCM of small businesses have been undertaken in the context of developing countries (Orobia et al., 2016; Oseifuah, 2016; Atseye et al., 2015; Ndagijimana and Okech, 2014). Therefore, while we explore this issue primarily by reference to the UK, it is likely that the nature of these problems is similar in all developed economies. Therefore, this study critically reviews the concept of WCM and investigates internal factors that influence the requirements of WCM of small food restaurants in the context of the UK. The disclosure of this knowledge gap is discussed within the context of theory, practice, and methodological contributions later in this chapter.

The researcher embedded open-ended questions within a survey questionnaire to collect data in a single phase for the better understanding of research problems (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). Data were collected from 72 small food restaurants in the UK through mixed questionnaires, with a blend of both close-ended and open-ended questions. The quantitative data from survey questionnaires were collected from August 2019 to February 2020 in the UK. Quantitative data was analysed separately by using SPSS software version 25. The relationship between internal factors and WCM requirements were analysed by inferential statistical tools such as mean, median, mode, and standard deviation, Pearson correlation, Spearman's rho and regression analysis and chi-square. 28 owner-managers wrote their answers in their own words. As a result, open-ended answers provided rich information on the WCM requirements. Closed-ended questions were useful to test the main four hypotheses (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). Initially, the researcher found the mixed approach a very time-consuming and complex method. The researcher was required to seek out support mechanisms such as Web resources and software training such as SPSS and NVivo workshops to cover the complex element of qualitative and quantitative approaches. However, it was worth it to overcome these limitations of mixed methods, as by embracing both qualitative and quantitative forms of data, the researcher gained better insights (Bazeley, 2019) into the factors associated with the WCM of small food restaurants. This study is unique as no

research has yet followed mixed approaches to identify the internal factors of WCM. The next section outlines the results that emanated from quantitative and qualitative findings.

7.3. CONTRIBUTION OF RESEARCH

The purpose of this was to make significant contribution to the existing body of knowledge in small business management. A substantial contribution can be identified in the context of theories, practice, and methodology.

7.3.1. CONTRIBUTION TO THEORY

In terms of contribution to theory, this study contributes in WCM, components of WCM: inventory, receivables and payables management, small business finance, and the impact of business-level factors on WCM of small food restaurants in the UK. Therefore, one of the vital implications of the research is that it benefits financial managers, academics, practitioners, and policymakers to intensify their knowledge curve on the importance of efficient working capital management in relation to the different internal and external factors that determine WCM.

The conceptual framework provides an understanding of the inter-relation between the internal factors and WCM practices as derived from the existing successful works therefore having the potential to impact on the WCM knowledge. This framework implies a significant academic contribution to the interactive literature on WCM and financial management in small restaurant businesses. In addition, this research further contributes towards various literary sources as associated with working capital management through the means of evaluation of different internal factors such as size of the business, management competencies, leverage, and profitability. This research would be a vital tool for academic practitioners for advancing theoretical understanding around the WC practice of the small business, workforce planning, and monitoring managerial competencies.

7.3.2. METHODOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

This study contributed to the field of methodology using mixed methodology, ‘a third methodological movement’. As mixed methods has become a more widely recognized approach (Cameron and Molina-Azorin, 2011; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Bazeley, 2019), the

extensive adoption of this method across the social and behavioural sciences has been described as ‘a third methodological movement’ (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Bazeley, 2019).

7.3.2.1. **Mixed methods**

This study followed a pragmatist philosophy that combines quantitative and qualitative methods to gain knowledge regardless of the methods used. By embedding open-ended questions within a quantitative survey, the researcher considered both objective aspects of WCM and opinions of managers to gain better insights into the factors associated with WCM of small restaurants. The selection of the embedded mixed method approach not only results in a better understanding of the research problems but also can benefit future studies to use this type of approach. Thus, the pragmatist standpoint, mixed research strategies, and the embedded mixed methods all contribute to mixed research approach that brings benefits for business and management practitioners and academics, particularly for those researchers who are continually trying to add value and gain better understanding into increasingly complex business and management phenomena (Cameron and Molina-Azorin, 2011).

7.3.2.2. **Reliability**

Further this study contributes to the reliable findings by calculating alpha for each of the variables or concepts rather than for the total scale (chapter five, Table 5.2.5.3.). Alpha increases as the number of items increase (Hayes and Coutts, 2020); as a result, a large number of items will inflate the value of alpha (Cohen and Swerdlik, 2010). Thus, α does not measure the homogeneity of variables directly. Therefore, to avoid the misinterpretation of alpha, this research computed the reliability coefficients for each of the variables rather than for the entire scales.

7.3.2.3. **Statistical analysis**

In this study, the researcher used both parametric (Pearson) and non-parametric (Spearman’s) correlation analysis to compare the results. These two methods have not been used together in investigating WCM requirements. Both tests gave similar answers, even when assumptions are violated (chapter five, Table 5.2.5.4.a). Therefore, linear models, e.g. Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis, used in this study without normal distribution of data should still produce valid results in a large sample size setting ($N=72$) (Norman, 2010; Micioiu and

Atkinson, 2017; Schmidt and Finana, 2018). This result provides a new insight into the use of parametric and non-parametric statistical tools to compare the robustness of the results even without normal distribution of data.

7.3.2.4. **Structure of chapters**

This study used diagrams to illustrate concepts to the reader. The content of each chapter was clearly presented by using diagrams. The rationale of drawing plans was to ensure the discussion of key contents linking to the conceptual framework of the study. Further it enhanced the audit process of the research in the context of addressing the main aim and purpose of the research.

Statistical analysis (correlation, regression, and chi-square) were also presented in a separate chapter by using diagrams to keep the investigation process simple and consistent to the reader. The diagrams that were contributory in achieving the aim and objectives of the study include Figure 1.1 (Structure of the study); Table 3.1 (Conceptual framework and resulting hypotheses); Table 3.2 (Summary of previous empirical research); Figure 5.1 (The structure of findings and analysis); Table 5.2.4. (c), (D) (Regression analysis of the internal factors and WCM; Figure 7.2 (The summary of the entire research). The use of these diagrams enhances the coherence of the methodological agenda to both the researcher and reader.

7.3.3. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The research concluded that there is a strong correlation between different internal factors of WCM and working capital management practices. The framework provides the necessary structure for the association between the four internal factors (size, management competency, leverage, and profitability) and the working capital requirement that until now has been lacking. After careful consideration of internal factors, e.g. managerial educational needs and overcoming challenges associated with external factors, e.g. inflation and competition, small food restaurants will be able to manage working capital more effectively. In terms of implications on an individual basis, the conceptual framework can provide understanding of the internal factors which should help owner-managers of small restaurants to focus on the potential factors influencing the effective management of working capital in their businesses. In wider terms, the resultant framework can

be used by small businesses to gain insight into the impact potential of business-level factors in terms of working capital management (WCM).

Further, this study identified that owner-managers use their prior experience to manage working capital. Even though the majority of owner-managers completed GCSEs, the requirement of both educational and practical knowledge is emphasized by small restaurants. These findings emphasize the requirement of theoretical knowledge in this sector, and therefore can be incorporated into the strategic planning of financial management. These results of qualitative findings pioneered a connection of human resource concepts, e.g. employee competencies with the efficient management of working capital in small food restaurants, which is giant in terms of its importance to the UK economy. This research would be an essential tool for business policymakers for understanding internal factors that influence the WC practice of small food restaurants, and planning cash flow strategy with a focus on the opportunities and future threats that may be caused by external factors, e.g. Covid-19 pandemic and macroeconomic factors.

7.3.3.1. **Economic**

Small restaurants in the UK are facing economic uncertainty because of the recent Covid-19 pandemic and Brexit. As a result, managerial educational and practical knowledge will help small restaurants to tackle future uncertainty in terms of working capital and cash flow management. Additionally, qualitative findings identified that macro-economic external factors: inflation, competition, and firm-specific internal factors such as employee competency affect the requirements of WCM of small food restaurants and managerial decisions regarding investment of WC. Uncertain economic circumstances such as Brexit and Covid-19 would force small businesses to become more competitive as economic uncertainty will remain ambiguous for subsequent years. Consequently, small restaurants will be required to face future uncertainties and focus on external and internal factors related to working capital. Small food restaurants mostly depend on owner financing and supplier credit. Therefore, owner-managers should retain more working capital than other size businesses. As Zariyawati et al. (2016) pointed out, large firms keep working capital low due to better access to capital. Due to limited access to external financing, managers of small businesses need to ensure that they manage WC effectively, in particular, before and during inflation.

Restaurant owners cannot afford to hire more highly qualified employees because of high salary costs. Therefore, the focus of small restaurants should be on employee competencies. Efficient and skilled employees will be able to manage all components of WC. For example, the key to accounts receivable management for a food restaurant is collecting cash from customers. Efficient employees can manage both inventory and receivables by maintaining food quality and providing excellent customer service which are important phases towards better cash flow, for example, managing all three components: stock levels, increasing receivables, and extending payables terms.

7.3.3.2. **Managerial implications**

In small restaurants, owner-managers are responsible for the overall management of working capital. As this study revealed, the management of accounts receivable shows low importance in the small food restaurant industry. Because of the cash sales nature of the industry, effective WCM and planning for the components such as inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable can be an internal source of finance that will benefit financial managers. Managers of small restaurants can implement the conceptual framework to identify the impact of the four business level factors, business size, management competencies, leverage, and profitability, on the WCM. Further, this framework will provide valuable insights for the owner-managers of small restaurants into the three main components of WCM: inventory, accounts receivable, and payables. As this framework suggests a positive relation between business size and WC requirements, managers can plan WCM strategies. As the business grows, managers will need to manage all three components of WCM, such as excess stock of raw foods, effective management of AR, computerized systems, extending AR periods to encourage customers to spend more, paying suppliers early, and so on. In addition, this framework suggests that management competencies are positively related with the requirement of WCM in the small food restaurant. This study identified that both education and work experience are important for small restaurant managers, as educated and experienced managers can manage all components of WCM practices. Regression analysis identified that restaurant managers think education and prior experience both are crucial factors in the management of WC components. However, demographic findings revealed in the present scenario that the importance of work experience was higher compared to education. Most of the owners and managers of small restaurants had completed GCSEs (62.5%).

As management skills are relatively underdeveloped in many British SMEs (BEIS, 2015), small businesses strive to employ knowledgeable, experienced, and qualified people to manage working capital effectively. Further results from thematic analysis revealed that small restaurants cannot afford to recruit efficient employees and educated staff.

Owners think that experienced staff will demand a high salary.

This framework suggests that leverage has a positive impact on WCM. Small businesses with high levels of leverage need to maintain more working capital than other sizes of businesses. This study identified from the relationship between leverage and WCM components (chapter five) that small restaurants with high levels of leverage decrease inventory days, account collection periods, and payables periods with suppliers because of high levels of debt. Small restaurants mostly sell foods; therefore, a high amount of raw materials is compulsory for daily operations. Small food restaurants prefer collecting payments from customers on time and paying their suppliers on time rather than expanding credit terms with suppliers. Small restaurants mostly depend on owner financing rather than supplier credit (Table 5.2.4.5. e). As working capital is an internal source of finance, it can be used as an alternative to external sources of finance. Because of the cash sales nature of the industry, restaurant firms do not need to hold extra cash if they manage accounts receivable and accounts payable effectively. Educated and experienced managers can improve supply chain management through interaction with suppliers. The managers may also be able to monitor and control the four business-level factors influencing the appropriateness of WCM in their organizations and take necessary actions to optimize the cash flow level. Thus, this conceptual framework can not only be beneficial for business owner-managers to improve the area of financial decision-making, particularly WCM strategy, but also to ensure sustainable growth and profitability.

In addition, macro-economic factors revealed from the qualitative findings can be beneficial for managers to ensure that restaurants can sustain economic growth and remain cash dynamic during the economic uncertainty that may be caused by Brexit and Covid-19. Managers must focus on inflation and competition to tackle any negative effects on WCM and its components.

Further, this study should help managers to focus on the both business-level (managerial competencies, business size, profitability) and macro-economic factors (inflation and competition) on the inventory, receivables, and payables management in their businesses. Further, the influence of these factors on the components of WCM were analysed. These results can be beneficial for managers in making decisions on the three main WCM components, inventory, receivables, and payables, as mismanagement of any one component may adversely affect the other components. The outcomes of this study in relation to WCM and its components will assist finance managers to achieve optimal working capital structure for their businesses and allow maximization of profit and stakeholders' wealth. Due to the recent pandemic, managers may need to change suppliers which will require a strategic approach focusing on future uncertainties about external and internal factors related to payables management. In this case, the effect of leverage can be considered while trading-off with new suppliers.

The regression results of this study confirm that management competencies have a significant positive impact (69.9%) on the requirement of WCM in small restaurants. The findings suggest that both educational and practical knowledge of the managers are vital for the management of WC components. Experienced managers will be able to manage stock effectively, train employees for effective customer services, and negotiate with creditors. Qualitative findings of this study revealed that human resources is one of the critical issues in small restaurants. Therefore, managers should emphasize employee competencies while managing their human resources. Efficient employees will be able to improve account collection procedures which are key steps towards a well-managed working capital and sustainable cash flow.

To conclude, the critical review of literature, mixed methodological approach, and mixed research findings all contribute to research knowledge, methodology and practices. It would be fruitful to extend the investigation into WCM practices outside the boundary of the small food restaurants and consider all types of small businesses.

7.4. LIMITATION OF THE RESEARCH AND CHALLENGES

As with all study, this research has been subject to limitations. This section captures the literature gap and the methodological limitations in relation to the data collection, sample size, time frame, and the potential desirability bias.

Social desirability bias

As the participants were mostly owner-managers of small restaurants, they were likely to provide a good impression of their businesses. Most of the owner-managers were responsible for the overall management of working capital in their restaurants. To lessen this potential desirability bias, owner-managers were offered anonymity as per the idea of Grimm (2010).

Sample size and data collection

The main limitation and challenge of this study was the time length. For this study, a questionnaire survey was administered for only a six-month period. As a result, out of 100 only 72 respondents responded to the closed-ended answers, whereas only 28 owner-managers answered the open-ended questions. Apart from time length, collecting data face to face was another challenge for the researcher due to the recent Covid-19 pandemic. The researcher was fortunate that there were only 10 participants left to return questionnaires at the time of the first lockdown in March 2020. The researcher employed another person to collect the remaining data remotely from 10 owner-managers. As a result, lower responses were received for the open-ended questions. Owner-managers were wearing hand gloves and face masks to protect them against the spread of the coronavirus. Despite these challenges, the researcher preferred the physical presence of respondents over the online methods. This limited sample size (N=72) was comparable to similar empirical research (Javid, 2014; Muhammad and Elias, 2013; Mohamad et al., 2017; Gorondutse et al., 2017) and still enabled generalization of research findings (Schmidt and Finana, 2018). Further, these above limitations in relation to time length and data collection methods however did not affect the conclusions, as mixed data collection methods provide strengths to the weakness of the study.

Generalization of the findings

This study was conducted to a specific sample containing only small restaurant industry businesses; therefore, formulating reflections regarding small businesses operating in other industries is restricted. More evidence is needed on WCM determinants of small businesses operating in the different industries before any generalization of the findings can be made. However, the results can be supportive for all types of small businesses operating in the UK to develop understanding of WCM.

Gap in the literature

Despite these findings, this study did not consider another important component of WCM, which is cash flow. The relation between the factors affecting WCM will be different for a business holding small amounts of cash than the business that holds a lot of cash. Therefore, cash flow management is crucial for small food restaurants because of the cash sales nature of the restaurants. However, absence of cash flow in the data analysis should not affect the robustness of findings. The focus of the three main components: inventory, receivables, and payables is to free up and obtain maximum cash benefits. In addition, it is evident from the qualitative findings that external factors such as competition, inflation, taxation, weather, etc. affect the WCM of small food restaurants. For this study, which only analysed the internal factors, this a limitation. As a result, this study recommends the need for further research on the impact of external factors as well as internal factors on the WCM based on the cash flow of small food restaurants.

In addition, this study did not analyse the effect of management competencies on the components of WCM due to the lack of previous studies. However, the limitation did not affect the findings of this study as the researcher identified the effect of three other internal factors: size, leverage, and profitability on the WCM components of the small restaurants to achieve the research objective. The above limitations of this study suggest a need for a longitudinal mixed methods future study. An in-depth insight into both internal factors and external factors affecting the WCM of small restaurants can be produced.

This study investigated the effect of business-level determinants such as business size and profitability on the WCM of small food restaurants. However, the researcher did not consider the possible effect of country-level determinants on the small food restaurants as the majority of the respondents were selling multinational cuisines. In addition, previous studies confirmed the effect of country specific factors (Koralun-Bereźnicka, 2014) such as legal environment and culture

(Falconer et al., 2016) on the capital structure decision and working capital of the multinational firms operating in the same country. Cultural diversity directly had an impact on capital structure decisions and leverage of the US multinational firms, after controlling business-level determinants such as business size and profitability (Frijns et al., 2017). The management of working capital could eventually be influenced by the cultural background of the owner-managers of small businesses in the context of the UK. Hence, the investigation of the country-level factors in the research data can be considered a limitation of this study and opportunity for future research.

Despite this limitation, the findings remain robust to endogenous influences of the business-level determinants on the requirements of WCM which was the main objective of this study. In addition, this study can give an insight into the development of business level strategy to monitor and control the business level factors such as management competencies, size, leverage, and profitability. Based on the research gaps, this research provides recommendations for future research in the following section.

7.5. OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Mixed methods analysis helped this research to identify limitations and gap in the literature; therefore, it could be an opportunity for future research.

Incorporating macro-economic factors

This study focused on the influence of internal factors on WCM of small food restaurants. However, the qualitative analysis revealed the importance of both external and internal factors that influence the requirements of effective working capital in this sector and so could be used as the opportunity for future research.

Covid-19 and Brexit-related uncertainty

This study opens an opportunity for future research to analyse the external factors of WCM in small businesses. After Brexit and Covid-19 pandemic, small businesses should be affected adversely in terms of working capital and cash flow. Therefore, it is essential for small restaurants to have well-managed and healthy WC. According to the National Institute of Economic and Social

Research (NIESR), despite the roll-out of vaccines, UK inflation rates are predicted to rise 2% in the latter half of 2021, closer to the Bank of England's target. Such escalations in inflation rate normally forces the Bank of England to increase the interest rate of borrowing, which eventually affects the ability of small businesses to borrow cash. Even if a negative external factor, for example inflation, influences the borrowing ability of a small business, with healthy WC small businesses can tackle uncertain economic changes for the coming years. Therefore, in future research the effect of Covid-19 and Brexit-related uncertainty should be considered as external factors of WCM, most importantly inflation and tax implications.

Country-specific factors (culture)

This study investigated the effects of business-level determinants such as business size and profitability on the WCM of small food restaurants. Nevertheless, evidence suggests that multinational small businesses operating in the same country manage their WCM differently due to country-specific factors: legal environment and culture (Falconer et al., 2016). A comparative study can also be done between the UK and other countries to identify country-specific factors affecting the WCM of small restaurants. As a result, cultural effects can be embedded in the future research as new economic environments would open new opportunities for the multinational firms operating in the UK.

Other areas for future research

This study focused on the three main components of WCM: inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. Therefore, these components have been taken as the measure of working capital requirement. However, the cash conversion cycle (CCC) can be used as a measure of WCM, so exists the opportunity for additional research. Further, this study recommends the need to incorporate other industry-specific factors such as employee competency in further research to add value to research findings. Comparison between small and large-size businesses in relation to their WCM could be used as an opportunity for further research.

7.6. CRITICAL REFLECTIVE SUMMARY

The researcher has previous experience of working within a small food restaurant while studying MSc Management with Finance. This experience helped the researcher to decide on the research topic, as WCM is one of the fundamental financial aspects of a small restaurant. While working as

an assistant manager, the researcher identified that small restaurants did not manage internal finance effectively. After completing the master's degree, the researcher wanted to study a DBA. Both previous work experience and education contributed significantly to decide on the DBA research topic.

As deduced from Figure 5.1, the reflective summary covers the major findings and answers to the research question that focused on the main hypotheses set to achieve the research aims and objectives. The key findings of this research are the summary of the contributions of the research in the context of theory, practice, and mixed methodology. Thus, findings contribute to the literature relating to working capital management requirements of small food restaurants in the context of the UK and the four determinant's factors: management competencies, business size, leverage, and profitability. The conceptual framework provides a structured approach to the internal factors that influence the working capital requirements which has been developed specially for the small food restaurants and validated by owner-managers of this sector. Therefore, this research can conclude that the conceptual framework developed in chapter three (Table 3.1) through the research signifies valuable implications to theory and can be practised by small food restaurants in the UK to enhance financial performance in their businesses. The researcher has personal connection with a few small business owners. This opportunity will help to build networks with other small businesses. Small restaurant owners can access the conceptual framework through trade association and local chambers of commerce. The in-depth analysis of WCM in small food restaurants has shaped the insight of the researcher as there were many critical episodes of information for the author in the last three years in terms of defining research questions, analysis, critical interpretation of mixed findings, etc. The research has provided many opportunities to build networks with other researchers, supervisors, and owner-managers of the small businesses. Overall, the journey of this research has been challenging and enjoyable.

Figure 7.2 Summary of entire research in a diagram

References

- Aktas, N., Croci, E. and Petmezas, D. (2015) 'Is working capital management value-enhancing? Evidence from firm performance and investments', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 30, pp. 98-113. doi: 10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2014.12.008
- Adeniji, A.A. (2008) *Management Accounting*. 4th edn. Nigeria: El-Toda Venture Limited, Lagos.
- Al-Mwalla, Muna. (2012) 'The impact of Working Capital Management Policies on firm's Profitability and Value: the case of Jordan', *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 85, pp. 147-153.
- Atrill, P. (2017) *Financial management for decision makers*. 8th edn. Prentice hall.
- Atseye, F.A., Ugwu, J.I. and Takon, S.M. (2015) 'Determinants of working capital management', *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(2), pp.1-11.
- Afrifa, G. A. (2013) 'Working Capital Management Practices of UK SMEs: The Role of Education and Experience', *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 3(4), pp.185–196. doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2354522.
- Afrifa, G. A., Tauringana, V. and Tingbani, I. (2014) 'Working capital management and performance of listed SMEs', *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 27(6), pp. 557-578.
- Azami, J. and Tabar, F.J. (2016) 'Investigating the Factors Affecting Working Capital of Companies Using the Generalized Method of Moments', *Bulletin of the Royal Society of Sciences of Liège*, 85, pp. 1402-1415.
- Adekunle, A. O. and Sunday, K. (2015) 'What are the Determinants of Working Capital Requirements of Nigerian Firms?', *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(6), pp. 118-127.
- Afrifa, G. A. and Tauringana, V. (2013) 'The relative importance of working capital management and its components to SMEs' profitability', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(3), pp. 453-469.

Afrifa, G. A. (2016) 'Net working capital, cash flow and performance of UK SMEs', *Review of Accounting and Finance*, 15(1), pp.21-44.

Afrifa, G. A. and Tingbani, I. (2018) 'Working capital management, cash flow and SMEs' performance', *International journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 9(1), pp. 19-43.

Abbadi, S. M. and Abbadi, R. T. (2013) 'The Determinants of Working Capital Requirements in Palestinian Industrial Corporations', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(1), pp. 65-75.

Ashhari, Z. M., Hirnissa, M.T. and Faiza, D.R. (2017). Working capital management and firm performance of small and large firms in Malaysia. *Journal of Global Business and Social Entrepreneurship (GBSE)*. 3(7): 166–177. doi:10.5539/ijef.v5n1p65

Afrifa, G. A. and Padachi, K. (2016) 'Working capital level influence on SME profitability', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 23(1), pp. 44-63. doi:10.1108/JSBED-01-2014-0014.

Agyei-Mensah, B. K. (2012) 'Working Capital Management Practices of small Firms in the Ashanti Region of Ghana', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 2(1), pp. 567-583. Available at:https://www.academia.edu/1604140/Working_Capital_Management_Practices_of_Small_Firms_in_the_Ashanti_Region_of_Ghana (Accessed: 9 March 2021)

Azeem, M. M. and Marsap, A. (2015) 'Determinant Factors and Working Capital Requirement', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(2): 280-292. doi:10.5539/ijef.v7n2p280.

Arnold, G. (2008) *Corporate Financial Management*. 3rd Edn. England: Pearson Education Limited.

Achari, P. D. (2014) *Research methodology: A guide to ongoing research scholars in management*. Asia: Horizon books.

Abuzayed, B. (2012) 'Working capital management and firm's performance in emerging markets: the case of Jordan', *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 8(2), pp.155-179. doi: 10.1108/17439131211216620.

Andrade, C. (2018) 'Internal, External, and Ecological Validity in Research Design, Conduct, and Evaluation', *Indian Journal of psychological medicine*, 40(5), pp. 498-499. doi: 10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_334_18.

- Boopathi, C. and Leeson, J. (2016). Concept of working capital management. *International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management (IJCBM)*. 5(2), pp. 372-377.
- Blaxter, L., *et al.* (2010) *How to research*. 4th edn. McGraw-Hill.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2015) *Business research methods*. 4th edn. UK: Oxford university press.
- Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B. (2019) *Business research methods*. 5th edn. UK: Oxford university press.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods*. 5th edn. New York: Oxford university press.
- Brannen, J. (2016) *Mixing methods: qualitative and quantitative research*. 2nd edn. USA: Routledge.
- Bhatia, S. and Srivastava, A. (2016) ‘Working Capital Management and Firm Performance in Emerging Economies: Evidence from India’, *Management and Labour Studies*, 41(2), pp. 71–87. doi.org/10.1177/0258042X16658733
- Baños-Caballero, S., García-Teruel, P.J. and Martínez-Solano, P. (2014) ‘Working capital management, corporate performance, and financial constraints’, *Journal of Business Research*, 67(3), pp. 332-338.
- Baker, K. H., Kumar, S., Colombage, S., Singh, P. H., (2017) ‘Working capital management practices in India: survey evidence’, *Managerial Finance*, 43(3), pp. 331-353.
- Bazeley, P. (2018) *Integrating analysis in mixed methods research*. London: Sage publications Ltd.
- Bazeley, P. (2019) *A practical introduction to mix methods for business and management*. London: Sage publications Ltd.
- Cowling, M., Liu, W. and Ledger, A. (2012) ‘Small business financing in the UK before and during the current financial crisis’, *International small business journal*, 30 (7), pp. 778-800. doi: 10.1177/0266242611435516
- Caballero, S.B., Teruel, P.J.G. and P.M. Solano (2014) ‘Working Capital Management, Corporate Performance and Financial Constraints’, *Journal of Business Research*, 67 (3), pp. 332–338
- Choudhary, H. and Tripathi, G. (2012) ‘An analysis of the inventory turnover and its impact on financial performance in Indian organized retail industry’, *Journal of Services Research*, 12(1) , pp. 43-64.
- Crick, D., Chaudhry, S. and Crick, J. M. (2016) ‘Trading in a Competitive Environment: South-Asian Restaurants in the UK’, *Strategic change*, 25, pp. 371-382.

- Chepkemoi, M., Patrick, E., Njoroge, C. (2017) ‘The effects of financial literacy training on business profitability in coastal region: a case of Kwale county SMEs’, *The strategic journal of business and change management*, 4(44), pp. 684-703.
- Chaudry, S. Crick, D. (2004). ‘The business practices of small Chinese restaurants in the UK: an exploratory investigation’, *Strategic Change*, 13, pp. 37–49.
- Creswell, J. W. and Plano Clark, V. L. (2007) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cohen R and Swerdlik M. (2010) *Psychological testing and assessment*. Boston: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014) *Research design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed methods approaches*. 4th edn. USA: Sage publications.
- Creswell, J. W. and Plano Clark, V. L. (2018) *Designing and conducting mix methods research*. 3rd. Edn. London: Thousand Oaks .
- Cameron, R. and Molina-Azorin, J. F. (2011) ‘The acceptance of mixed methods in business and management research’, *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 19(3), pp. 256 – 271.
- Creswell, J. W., & Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining validity in qualitative inquiry. *Theory into Practice*, 39, pp. 124–130.
- Department for Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2016). Small Business Survey reports 2016. [Online] Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/small-business-survey-reports>
(Accessed: 20 Feb 2018)
- Department for Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2015). Leadership and Management Skills in SMEs: Measuring Associations with Management Practices and Performance [Online] Available https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/407624/BIS-15-95_Leadership_and_Management_Skills_in_SMEs.pdf (Accessed: 11 May 2018)
- Dawson, C., (2013) *Advanced research methods: a practical guide for anyone undertaking a research project*. Oxford.
- Duru, A. N., Ekwe, M. C. and Okpe, I. I. (2014) ‘Accounts receivable management and corporate performance of companies in the food & beverage industry: evidence from Nigeria’, *European*

Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research, 2(10), pp. 34-47. ISSN 2053-4094(Online).

Dinku T., (2013) 'Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability of Micro and Small Enterprises in Ethiopia: The Case of Bahir Dar City Administration', *International Journal of Accounting and Taxation* 1(1), pp. 15-24.

Darun, M. R. (2011) 'The determinants of working capital management practices: a Malaysian perspective', *PhD theses*, Lincoln University, Christchurch.

Dall'Oglio, A. M., Rossiello B., Coletti, M. F., Caselli, M. C., Lucilla Ravà, L., Ciommo, V. D. Orzalesi, M., Giannantoni, P. and Patrizio Pasqualetti (2010) 'Developmental evaluation at age 4: Validity of an Italian parental questionnaire', *J Paediatr Child Health*, 46(7-8), pp. 419-26.

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS, 2018) Creating a responsible payment culture. Available at: https://beisgovuk.citizenspace.com/ccp/responsible-payment-culture-cfe/supporting_documents/creatingaresponsiblepaymentculturecallforevidence.pdf (Accessed 26 Feb 2020)

Eya, C. I. (2016) 'Effect of Working Capital Management on the Performance of Food and Beverage Industries in Nigeria', *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(5), pp. 1-7.

Enow, S.T. and Kamala. P. (2016) 'The accounts payable management practices of small, medium, and micro enterprises in the Cape Metropolis, South Africa', *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 13(1), pp. 77-83.

Elbadry, A. (2018) 'The Determinants of Working Capital Management in the Egyptian SMEs', *Accounting and Finance Research*. 7(2), pp. 155-165. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5430/afr.v7n2p155>.

Ebben, J. J. and Johnson, A. C. (2011) 'Cash Conversion Cycle management in small firm's relationships with liquidity, Invested Capital, and Firm Performance', *Journal of small business and entrepreneurship (JSBE)*' 24 (3), pp. 381-447.

Fan, J. P. H., Titman, S. and Twite. G. (2012) 'An International Comparison of Capital Structure and Debt Maturity Choices', *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 47(1), pp. 23-56.

Fethi, S. and Katircioglu, S. (2015) 'The role of the financial sector in the UK economy: evidence from a seasonal cointegration analysis', *Economic Research*, 28 (1), pp. 717-737.

- Fatimatu Zahra, M. and Kusumastuti, R. (2016) 'The Determinant of Working Capital Management of Manufacturing Companies. Faculty of Social and Political Sciences', 32 (2), pp. 276-281.
- Frijns, B., Tourani-Rad, A., and Zhang, F. J. (2017) 'Cultural diversity and capital structures of multinational firms', *Department of Finance, Faculty of Business, Economics and Law, Auckland University of Technology, Auckland, New Zealand*.
- Gill, A. (2010) 'Factors that Influence Working Capital Requirement in Canada', *Economic and Finance Review*, 1 (3), pp. 30 – 40.
- Garg, M. (2015) *Working capital management*. India: Edu creation publishing.
- Gibson, C. B. (2017) 'Elaboration, generalisation, triangulation, and interpretation: on enhancing the value of mixed methods research', *Organisational research methods*. 20(2), pp. 193-223.
- Guba, E. G. and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994) *Competing paradigms in qualitative research*. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 105–117). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Gimm, P. (2010) *Social Desirability Bias*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd.
- Ghosh, S.K., Burns, C.B., Prager, Zhang, D.L., and Hui, L. (2018) 'On nonparametric estimation of the latent distribution for ordinal data', *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*. 119, pp. 86-98.
- Gorondutse, A., Abubakar, A., Ali, R. and Naalah, M., (2017) 'The effect of working capital management on SMEs profitability in Malaysia', *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 16(2), pp.99-109.
- Hayes, A. F. and Coutts, J. J. (2020). 'Use Omega Rather than Cronbach's Alpha for Estimating Reliability', *Communication Methods and Measures*, 14(1), pp. 1-24.
- Hillary, R. (2017) *Small and Medium-Size Enterprises and the environment: Business imperatives*. 2nd ed. New York: Greenleaf publishing limited.
- Howorth, C. and Westhead, P. (2003). 'The Focus of Working Capital Management in UK Small Firms', *Management Accounting Research*, 14(2), pp. 94-111.
- Huckman, R.S. and Pisano, G.P. (2006) 'The firm specificity of individual performance: Evidence from cardiac surgery', *Management Science*, 52(4), pp. 473–488.
- Hill, MD, Kelly, GW & Highfield, MJ (2010), 'Net operating working capital behaviour: A first look', *Financial Management*, 9(2), pp783-805.

- House, J. (2018) 'Authentic vs elicited data and qualitative vs quantitative research methods in pragmatics: Overcoming two non-fruitful dichotomies', *System*. 75, pp. 4-12.
- Hayes, A. F. and Coutts, J. J. (2020) 'Use Omega Rather than Cronbach's Alpha for Estimating Reliability. But....', *Communication Methods and Measures*. 14(1), pp. 1-24.
- Ismail, N. (2018) 'Does It Really Matter? Learning Lessons from Conducting a Pilot Study for a Qualitative PhD Thesis?', *International Journal of Social Science Research*. 6(1).
- Insider, (2020). *Protecting your company's cash flow during the Covid-19 outbreak*. [online] Available at: < <https://www.insider.co.uk/sponsored/protecting-your-companys-cash-flow-21883763>> (Accessed 10 February 2021)
- Industrial Facts and Forecasting (IFF) research (2019), 'How has the UK Restaurant sector been affected by the fissuring of the worker-employer relationship in the last 10 years?' [Online] Available https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/814592/Restaurant_Sector_Director_of_labour_market_enforcement_July_2019_IFF_research.pdf (Accessed: 2nd June 2021)
- Jiang, J., Dong, F. and Du, B., (2018) 'Analysis on the Factors Affecting the Capital Structure of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in China', *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 08(01), pp. 156-162.
- Jain P.K., Singh S., Yadav S.S. (2013) *Working Capital Management. In: Financial Management Practices. India Studies in Business and Economics*. India: Springer.
- Javid, S. (2014) 'Effect of Working Capital Management on SME's Performance in Pakistan', *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(12), pp. 206-220.
- Johnson, R. B. and Christensen, L. B. (2017) *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches*. 6th edn. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Khan, M. Y., and Jain P. J. (2007) *Financial Management. Tax, Problems and Cases*. 5th edn. New Delhi: Tata, MC Graw Hill Publishing Company Limited.
- Kalsie, A. and Arora, A. (2016) 'Analysis of Working Capital Management of Indian FMCG Companies', *Effulgence*, 14 (2), pp. 73-86.
- Kasozi, J. (2017). 'The Effect of Working Capital Management on Profitability: A Case of Listed Manufacturing Firms in South Africa', *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 14(2), pp. 336-346. doi.org/10.21511/imfi.14(2-2).2017.05

- Koralun-Bereźnicka, J. (2014) 'Capital structure as a determinant of working capital management: empirical evidence across size groups of firms in the EU countries', *Journal of International Scientific Publications*. 8, pp. 36-54.
- Lloyd, C. and Payne, J., (2014) 'It's all hands-on, even for management: Managerial work in the UK cafe sector', *human relations*, 67(4), pp. 465-488.
- Lincoln, Y. S., and Guba, E. G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Lawrence.J.G and Chad.J.Z, (2012) Principles of managerial finance. 13th edn, United States of America: Pearson education Inc.
- Lyngstadaas, H., and Berg, T. (2016) 'Working capital management: evidence from Norway', *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 12(3), pp. 295–313.
- Louw, E. and Hall, J. (2016) 'Working capital management of south African retail firms', *Journal of Economic and Financial Sciences*. 9(2), pp. 545 – 560.
- Lei Ruan, L. and Li, C. (2017) 'Accounting Education, Knowledge Management and Working Capital Management Performance: Evidence from China', *Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*. 13(10), pp. 6823-6836.
- Leavy, P. (2017) *Research design*. New York: Guilford press
- Lub, V. (2015) 'Validity in Qualitative Evaluation: Linking Purposes, Paradigms, and Perspectives', *International journal of qualitative methods*, 1-8.
- Martin B (2003) *The structure of business*, 2nd edn. London: MacDonal and Evans Ltd.
- Mbawuni, J., Mbawuni, M. H. and Nimako, S. G. (2016) 'The Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability of Petroleum Retail Firms: Empirical Evidence from Ghana', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(6), pp. 49-62.
- Magoutas, A., Papadogonas, T.A. and Sfakianakis, G. (2012) 'Market Structure, Education, and growth', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(12), pp. 88-95.
- Mohamad, N. E. A., Rahman, N. R. B., and Saad, N. B. (2017) 'Linking working capital policy towards financial performance of small medium enterprise (SME) in Malaysia', *SHS Web of Conferences* 36, 00021.
- Mohamad, N. E. A. (2013) 'An analysis of working capital management with reference on listed companies in Bursa Malaysia', *American Journal of Economics*, 3(6), pp. 352–357.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2016) 'Expanding the history and ranged of mixed methods research', *Journal of mixed methods research*. 10(1), pp.12–27.

- Manoori, E. and Muhammad, D. J. (2012) 'Determinants of working capital management: Case of Singapore firms', *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 3(11), pp.15-23.
- Muhammad, N. E.A. B. and Elias, S. B. (2013) 'An Assessment on Determinant of Working Capital Management from Malaysian Public Listed Companies', *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*. 3(4), pp. 224–228.
- Mun, S. G. and Jang, S. (2015) 'Working capital, cash holding, and profitability of restaurant firms', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*. 48, pp. 1–11.
- Mack, L. (2010). *Philosophical underpinning of educational research*. Polyglossia. 19.
- McKim, C. A. (2015) 'The value of mixed methods research: A mixed methods study', *The journals of sage publications*. 11 (2), pp. 202-222.
- Morse, J. M. and Niehaus, L. (2009) *Mixed methods design: Principles and procedures*. Walnut Creek, CA: Left Coast Press.
- Molina-Azorin, J.F. (2016) 'Mixed methods research: An opportunity to improve our studies and our research skills. Jose F', *Journal of management and business economics*, 25, pp.37-38.
- Maxwell, J. A. (1992) 'Understanding and validity in qualitative research', *Harvard Educational Review*. 62(3), pp. 279–299.
- Micioiu, C. and Atkinson, J. (2017) 'A Comparison of Parametric and Non-Parametric Methods Applied to a Likert Scale', *Pharmacy*. 5(26), pp. 1-12.
- Micheal, A. A., Abogun Segun, A. and Taiwo H, O. (2017) 'Impact of working Capital Management on financial performance of quoted consumer goods Manufacturing firms in Nigeria', *Covenant Journal of Business & Social Sciences (CJBSS)*. 8(2), pp. 1-22.
- Ndagijimana, J. P. and Okech, T. C. (2014) 'Factors affecting working capital management practices in small and medium enterprises in Nairobi', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 5(12), pp. 160-164.
- Nimalathasan, B, (2010) 'Working Capital Management and its Impact on Profitability: A study of Selected Listed Manufacturing Companies of Sri Lankan', *Information management* 12, pp. 76 – 82.
- Norman, G. (2010) 'Likert scales, levels of measurement and the "laws" of statistics', *Adv in Health Sci Educ*. 15, pp. 625-632.
- Nazir, M.S. and Afza, T. (2009) 'Impact of aggressive working capital management policy on firms' profitability', *The IUP Journal of Applied Finance*. 15(8), pp. 19-30.

- Orobia, L., Byabashaija, W., Munene, J.C., Sejjaaka, S.K. and Musinguzi, D. (2013) 'How do small business owners manage working capital in an emerging economy? A qualitative inquiry', *Qualitative Research in Accounting and Management*. 10(2), pp. 127-143. doi: 10.1108/QRAM-02-2012-0008
- Orobia, L. A., Padachi, K., Munene, J.C. (2016) 'Why some small businesses ignore austere working capital management routines?', *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*. 6 (2), pp. 94-110
- Oseifuah, E. (2016) 'Determinants of Working Capital Requirements: Evidence from Selected non-financial firms listed on the Johannesburg Securities Exchange', *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, 6(1), pp. 35-45. Available at:
<http://journals.univdanubius.ro/index.php/jam/article/view/3200/3622> (Accessed 9 March 2021)
- Office for National Statistics (ONS) (2018) 'Number of public houses, licenced clubs, restaurants, and takeaways by Borough'. [Online] Available <https://data.london.gov.uk/dataset/pubs-clubs-restaurants-takeaways-borough> (Accessed: 2nd June 2021)
- Office for National Statistics (ONS) (2020) 'Number of restaurants, takeaways, cafes, bars and pubs in the UK'. [Online] Available
<https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/transparencyandgovernance/freedomofinformationfoi/numberofrestaurantstakeawayscafesbarsandpubsintheuk> (Accessed: 3rd June 2021)
- Orumwense, J. O. and Mwakipsile, G. (2017) 'Working Capital Management and Managerial Performance in some Selected Manufacturing Firms in Edo State Nigeria', *Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance Research*. 1(1), pp. 46-55.
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J. and Collins, K. M. (2007) 'A Typology of Mixed Methods Sampling Designs in Social Science Research', *The Qualitative Report*, 12(2), pp. 281-316.
- Pansiri, J. and Temtime, Z.T. (2008) 'Assessing managerial skills in SMEs for capacity building', *Journal of Management Development*, 27(2), pp. 251-60.
- Pieterse, A. (2012) 'Working Capital Management Practices of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Western Region', *The Institute of Distance Learning, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology*.
- Pais, M. A. and Gama, P. M. (2015) 'Working capital management and SMEs profitability: Portuguese evidence', *International Journal of Managerial Finance*. 11(3), pp. 341-358.

Preve, L.A. and Allende, V. S. (2010) *Working capital management*. Oxford: Oxford university press.

Parsa, H.G., John, T. S., Njite, D. and King, T., 2005. Why restaurants fail. *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*. 46 (3), pp. 304–322.

Paul, S. Y. and Boden, R. (2011) ‘Size matters: the late payment problem. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*. 18(4), pp.732-747

Paul, S. and Wilson, N. (2006) ‘Trade credit supply: an empirical investigation of companies level data’, *Journal of Accounting-Business and Management*. 13 (85), pp.113.

Padachi, K., Howorth, C. and Narasimhan, M. S., (2012) ‘Working Capital Financing Preferences: The Case of Mauritian Manufacturing SMEs’ *Asian academy of management journal of accounting and finance*. 8(1), pp. 125-157.

Patino, C. M. and Ferreira, J. C. (2018) ‘Internal and external validity: can you apply research study results to your patients?’, *J Bras Pneumol*. 44(3), pp.183.

Qurashi, M. and Zahoor, M. (2017) ‘Working Capital Determinants for the UK Pharmaceutical Companies Listed on FTSE 350’, *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*. 7(1), pp. 11–17.

Saunders, M., et.al. (2016). *Research methods for business students*. 7th edn. Harlow: Pearson education Ltd.

Schoonenboom, J. and R. Burke Johnson, R. B. (2017) ‘How to Construct a Mixed Methods Research Design’, *Kolner Z Soz Sozpsychol*. 69 (2), pp.107–131.

Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: a skill-building approach*. 7th edn. UK: John Wiley and Sons Ltd.

Susskind, A. M. and Spies, R. (2011). *Focus on finance: Aiming for restaurant success. The Cornell School of Hotel Administration on Hospitality*. New York: Wiley.

Sadiq R (2017) ‘Impact of Working Capital Management on Small and Medium Enterprises’ Performance in Nigeria’ *Arabian Journal of Business and Management*. Review 7(1), pp. 285.

Sagner, J. (2014). *Working Capital Management: Applications and case studies*. John Wiley and Sons.

- Salek, J.G. (2005). *Accounts Receivable Management Best Practices*. New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.
- Shaista, W., and Veeri C. A. (2013) 'Determinants of Working Capital Investment: A Study of Malaysian public listed firms' *Australasian Accounting Business and Finance Journal*. 7 (2), pp. 63-83.
- Sillars, J. (2021). 'COVID-19: How many pubs, restaurants and clubs closed their doors permanently in 2020' UK: Sky news publisher [Online] Available <https://news.sky.com/story/covid-19-how-many-pubs-restaurants-and-clubs-closed-their-doors-permanently-in-2020-12194754> (Accessed 3rd June 2021)
- Stokes, P. (2011). *key concepts in business and management Research methods*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Stokes, P. and Wall, T. (2014). *Research methods*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Schmidt, A. F and Finana, C. (2018) 'Linear regression and the normality assumption', *Journal of clinical epidemiology*. 98, pp. 146-151.
- Shrestha, N. (2020) 'Detecting Multicollinearity in Regression Analysis' *American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 8 (2), pp.39-42.
- Singhania, M and Mehta, P. (2017). Working capital management and firms' profitability: evidence from emerging Asian countries. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*. 6(1), pp. 80-97.
- Tran, H., Abbott, M., Yap, C. J., (2017) 'How does working capital management affect the profitability of Vietnamese small- and medium-sized enterprises?', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24 (1), pp. 2-11.
- Turner, S. F., Cardinal, L.B., and Burton, R.M. (2017). Research design for mixed methods: A triangulation-based framework and roadmap. *Organisational research methods*. 20(2), pp. 243-267.
- Tuffour, J. K. and Boateng, J. A. (2017) 'Is working capital management important? Empirical evidence from manufacturing companies in Ghana', *Review of innovation and competitiveness*. 3(1), pp. 5-20
- Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (2003). *Handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioural research*. Thousand oaks, California: Sage.

- Ukaegbu, B. (2013) 'The significance of working capital management in determining firm profitability: Evidence from developing economies in Africa', *Research in International Business and Finance*. 31, pp. 1–16.
- UK Government (2018) 'Ending late payments to small businesses. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/ending-late-payments-to-small-businesses>[Accessed 26 Feb 2020]
- UK Standard Industrial Classification of Economic Activities 2007 (SIC 2007) Office for national statistics [Online] Available <https://www.ons.gov.uk/file?uri=/methodology/classificationsandstandards/ukstandardindustrialclassificationofeconomicactivities/uksic2007/uksic2007web.pdf> (Accesses: 2nd June 2021)
- Vijayalakshmi, S. and Bansal, N. (2013) 'Determinants of Working Capital in Cement Industry- A case study of ACC Ltd', *Pacific Business Review International*. 6(1), pp. 45-50.
- Valipour, H., Moradi, J. and F. D. Farsi (2012) 'The Impact of Company Characteristics on Working Capital Management', *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*. 2(1), pp. 106-125.
- Wasiuzzaman, S and Arumugam, V.C (2013) 'Determinants of working capital investment: a study of Malaysian public listed firms', *Australasian accounting, business, and finance journal*, 7(2), pp. 49- 70.
- Wasiuzzaman, S. (2015) 'Working capital and firm value in an emerging market. *International journal of managerial Finance*', 11 (1), pp. 60-79.
- Wong, K. Y. and Aspinwall, E. (2004) 'Characterizing knowledge management in the small business environment', *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 8 (3), pp. 44-61.
- Wapshott, R. and Mallett, O. (2018) Small and medium-sized enterprise policy: Designed to fail? *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*. 36(4), pp. 750–772.
- Woodside, A. G. (2010) 'Bridging the chasm between survey and case study research: Research methods for achieving generalization, accuracy, and complexity', *Industrial Marketing Management*. 39, pp. 64–75.
- Winterbotham M, Vivian D, Kik G, Huntley-Hew Itt J, Tw Eddle T, Dow Ning C, Thomson D, Morrice N, and Stroud S (2018) 'Employer Skills Survey 2017, DfE, London Employer skills survey 2017: UK findings'. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/employer-skills-survey-2017-uk-report> (Accessed 2nd March 2021).

Winterbotham M, Vivian D, Kik G, Huntley-Hewitt J, Tweddle T, Downing C, Thomson D, Morrice N, and Stroud S (2018) Employer Skills Survey 2017, DfE, London

Available <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/employer-skills-survey-2017-uk-report>

Yadav.R. and Kamath.V (2009). *Financial Management, Theory and Practice*. Orlando: The Dryden Press.

Yilmaz, K. (2013) 'Comparison of quantitative and qualitative research traditions: epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences', *European Journal of education*. 48(2), pp. 311-324.

Zafar, S., Nazam, M., Hanif, A., Almas, I. and Sana, N. (2016) 'Impact of working capital management on firm's profitability: a case from food sector of Pakistan', *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*. 4(10), pp. 48-58.

Zariyawati, M. A., Annuar, M. N. and Pui-san, N. (2016) 'Working Capital Management Determinants of Small and Large firms in Malaysia', *International Journal of Economics & Management*. 10(2), pp. 365-377

Appendix: A

Demographic findings: descriptive statistics

What is the type of business enterprise?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sole proprietorship	24	33.3	33.3	33.3
Partnership	12	16.7	16.7	50.0
Limited liability company	36	50.0	50.0	100.0
Valid Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Highest qualification of respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	GCSE	45	62.5	62.5	62.5
	A Level/College	15	20.8	20.8	83.3
	Bachelor's Degree	7	9.7	9.7	93.1
	Master's degree	5	6.9	6.9	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Number of employees					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-9	40	55.6	55.6	55.6
	10-19	32	44.4	44.4	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

What is the current position/job?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Manager	1	1.4	1.4	1.4
	Director	4	5.6	5.6	6.9
	Manager	47	65.3	65.3	72.2
	Owner	9	12.5	12.5	84.7
	Owner/ Manager	6	8.3	8.3	93.1
	Partner	5	6.9	6.9	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Number of years of experience in your current position?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2	6	8.3	8.3	8.3
	4	16	22.2	22.2	30.6
	5	1	1.4	1.4	31.9
	6	11	15.3	15.3	47.2
	10	30	41.7	41.7	88.9
	20	8	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Appendix B

Frequency table: The extent of WCM in small food restaurants

The extent of WCM in small restaurants					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	To a high extent	22	30.6	30.6	30.6
	To some extent	45	62.5	62.5	93.1
	Not at all	2	2.8	2.8	95.8
	Do not know	3	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	
Statistics					
Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?					
N	Valid	72			
	Missing	0			
Mean		1.81			

Chi-square tests: Association between the extent of WCM and the number of employees.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.567 ^a	3	.006
Likelihood Ratio	14.567	3	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.474	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	72		

a. 4 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .89.

Chi-Square Tests (Inventory)

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	129.910 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	64.075	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	37.124	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	72		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

Chi-Square Tests (Accounts receivable)

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	65.842 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	47.576	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	19.513	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	72		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06.

Chi-Square Tests (Accounts Payable)

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	96.846 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	43.930	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	26.686	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	72		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

Does your company prioritize inventory as a component of WCM?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High priority	31	43.1	43.1	43.1
	Moderate priority	38	52.8	52.8	95.8
	Do not know	1	1.4	1.4	97.2
	Low priority	1	1.4	1.4	98.6
	Not a priority	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does your company prioritize accounts receivable as a component of WCM?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High priority	21	29.2	29.2	29.2
	Moderate priority	37	51.4	51.4	80.6

Do not know	2	2.8	2.8	83.3
Low priority	6	8.3	8.3	91.7
Not a priority	6	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does your company prioritize accounts payable as a component of WCM?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High priority	30	41.7	41.7	41.7
	Moderate priority	38	52.8	52.8	94.4
	Do not know	1	1.4	1.4	95.8
	Low priority	2	2.8	2.8	98.6
	Not a priority	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does your company prioritize all the above three components of WCM?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High priority	21	29.2	29.2	29.2
	Moderate priority	43	59.7	59.7	88.9
	Do not know	5	6.9	6.9	95.8
	Low priority	3	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

One-way ANOVA of priority given to WCM by work experience of the owner-managers:

ANOVA Table		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Does your company prioritize all the above three components of WCM? * Number of years of experience in your current position?	Between Groups	6.670	4	1.668	3.732	0.008
	Within Groups	29.941	67	0.447		
	Total	36.611	71			

The usefulness of WCM in small food restaurants in the UK:

Frequency tables: The usefulness of WCM

Does your business invest in working capital to avoid the risk of financial shortage?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	11	15.3	15.3	15.3
	Agree	31	43.1	43.1	58.3
	Neither agree nor disagree	23	31.9	31.9	90.3
	Disagree	3	4.2	4.2	94.4
	Strongly disagree	2	2.8	2.8	97.2
	Do not know	2	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Do you agree that effective management of stock level reduces the maintenance cost?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	13	18.1	18.1	18.1
	Agree	40	55.6	55.6	73.6
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	19.4	19.4	93.1
	Do not know	5	6.9	6.9	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does WCM help your business to meet financial obligations such as debt financing?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	11	15.3	15.3	15.3
	Agree	28	38.9	38.9	54.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	27	37.5	37.5	91.7
	Disagree	1	1.4	1.4	93.1
	Do not know	5	6.9	6.9	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does the performance of your business increase by maintaining optimal level of working capital?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	9	12.5	12.7	12.7
	Agree	37	51.4	52.1	64.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	22	30.6	31.0	95.8
	Do not know	3	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	71	98.6	100.0	
Missing	System	1	1.4		
Total		72	100.0		

Appendix C

Frequency Table 4.2.5. (a)

Does the management competency influence the WCM in your restaurants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	25	34.7	34.7	34.7
	Agree	43	59.7	59.7	94.4
	Neither agree nor disagree	4	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does the size of business influence the WCM in your restaurants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	20	27.8	27.8	27.8
	Agree	39	54.2	54.2	81.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	10	13.9	13.9	95.8
	Disagree	1	1.4	1.4	97.2
	Do not know	2	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	14	19.4	19.4	19.4
	Agree	33	45.8	45.8	65.3
	Neither agree nor disagree	21	29.2	29.2	94.4
	Disagree	1	1.4	1.4	95.8
	Do not know	3	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Does profitability influence the WCM in your restaurants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	21	29.2	29.2	29.2
	Agree	37	51.4	51.4	80.6
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	19.4	19.4	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.2.5. (b): Management competencies, size, leverage, and profitability

Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Yes	67	1.66	.538	.066	1.53	1.79	1	3
	No	5	2.40	.548	.245	1.72	3.08	2	3
	Total	72	1.71	.568	.067	1.57	1.84	1	3
Does the size of business influence	Yes	67	1.90	.837	.102	1.69	2.10	1	6
	No	5	3.40	1.517	.678	1.52	5.28	2	6

the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Total	72	2.00	.964	.114	1.77	2.23	1	6
Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Yes	67	2.21	.993	.121	1.97	2.45	1	6
	No	5	3.40	1.517	.678	1.52	5.28	2	6
	Total	72	2.29	1.067	.126	2.04	2.54	1	6
Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Yes	67	1.84	.665	.081	1.67	2.00	1	3
	No	5	2.80	.447	.200	2.24	3.36	2	3
	Total	72	1.90	.695	.082	1.74	2.07	1	3

Table 4.2.5. (c): ANOVA table

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Between Groups	2.571	1	2.571	8.862	.004
	Within Groups	20.304	70	.290		
	Total	22.875	71			
Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Between Groups	10.531	1	10.531	13.290	.001
	Within Groups	55.469	70	.792		
	Total	66.000	71			
Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Between Groups	6.600	1	6.600	6.221	.015
	Within Groups	74.275	70	1.061		
	Total	80.875	71			
Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Between Groups	4.325	1	4.325	10.095	.002
	Within Groups	29.994	70	.428		
	Total	34.319	71			

Table 4.2.5.1 (a, b, c, d): Correlation analysis

Correlations (Spearman's rho)

	Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?	Does management influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.234*	.350**	.354**	.343**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.048	.003	.002	.003
N	72	72	72	72	72
Correlation Coefficient	.234*	1.000	.630**	.300*	.562**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.048	.	.000	.010	.000
N	72	72	72	72	72
Correlation Coefficient	.350**	.630**	1.000	.472**	.644**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.	.000	.000
N	72	72	72	72	72
Correlation Coefficient	.354**	.300*	.472**	1.000	.679**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.010	.000	.	.000
N	72	72	72	72	72
Correlation Coefficient	.343**	.562**	.644**	.679**	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.000	.000	.
N	72	72	72	72	72

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Non-parametric correlation (Spearman's rho)

Management competencies and WCM: Mean differences between the priority given to all component (INV, AR and AP) basing on the management competencies: Managerial practical knowledge and theoretical knowledge.

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Do you manage working capital through practical knowledge and prior experience?	Equal variances assumed	18.114	0.000	-3.216	70	0.002	-1.069	0.332	-1.731	-0.406
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.330	4.066	0.253	-1.069	0.803	-3.285	1.147
Do you think educational qualifications contributes to the effective management of WC?	Equal variances assumed	0.271	0.604	0.391	70	0.697	0.116	0.297	-0.477	0.710
	Equal variances not assumed			0.452	4.873	0.670	0.116	0.257	-0.550	0.783

Linear Regression analysis of the individual factors of the WCM:

The management competencies and WCM (Linear regression analysis)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.670 ^a	.449	.441	.512	1.609

a. Predictors: (Constant), Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

b. Dependent Variable: Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.948	1	14.948	57.085	.000 ^b
	Residual	18.330	70	.262		
	Total	33.278	71			

a. Dependent Variable: Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.203	0.221		0.918	0.362		
	Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	1.499	0.198	0.670	7.555	0.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model		Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions	
				(Constant)	Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
1	1	1.962	1.000	0.02	0.02
	2	0.038	7.176	0.98	0.98

a. Dependent Variable: The requirement of WCM

The size of business and WCM (Linear regression analysis)

:

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.446 ^a	0.199	0.187	0.23076	2.464

a. Predictors: (Constant), Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.925	1	0.925	17.374	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.728	70	0.053		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.740	0.084		8.849	0.000	0.573	0.907		
	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	0.286	0.069	0.446	4.168	0.000	0.149	0.423	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model		Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions	
				(Constant)	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
1	1	1.946	1.000	0.03	0.03
	2	0.054	5.982	0.97	0.97

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Leverage and WCM (Linear regression analysis)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.245 ^a	0.060	0.047	0.24994	2.328

a. Predictors: (Constant), Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.280	1	0.280	4.478	.038 ^b
	Residual	4.373	70	0.062		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.903	0.084		10.749	0.000	0.735	1.071		
	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	0.124	0.058	0.245	2.116	0.038	0.007	0.240	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model		Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions	
				(Constant)	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?
1	1	1.937	1.000	0.03	0.03
	2	0.063	5.523	0.97	0.97

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Profitability and WCM (Linear regression analysis)

;

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.317 ^a	0.101	0.088	0.24451	2.283

a. Predictors: (Constant), Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.468	1	0.468	7.828	.007 ^b
	Residual	4.185	70	0.060		
	Total	4.653	71			

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.864	0.079		10.969	0.000	0.707	1.021		
	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	0.166	0.059	0.317	2.798	0.007	0.048	0.284	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model		Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions	
				(Constant)	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
1	1	1.931	1.000	0.03	0.03
	2	0.069	5.279	0.97	0.97

a. Dependent Variable: Do you manage WC in your restaurant?

Multiple regression: All internal factors and WCM

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.685	.069		24.388	.000
	Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	-.679	.064	-.811	-10.570	.000
	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	-.040	.059	-.063	-.683	.497
	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	.024	.051	.047	.461	.646
	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	-.012	.056	-.022	-.211	.833

a. Dependent Variable: The requirement of WCM

Correlation: The effect of internal factors on the components of WCM

Correlations						
Spearman's rho		Components of WCM	Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
Components of WCM	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.639**	.513**	.263*	.251*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.026	0.033
	N	72	72	72	72	72

Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Correlation Coefficient	.639**	1.000	.593**	.335**	.455**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.004	0.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Correlation Coefficient	.513**	.593**	1.000	.503**	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Correlation Coefficient	.263*	.335**	.503**	1.000	.734**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.026	0.004	0.000		0.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Correlation Coefficient	.251*	.455**	.587**	.734**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.033	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	72	72	72	72	72
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

Appendix D

Test of reliability:

Item-Total Statistics: Requirements of WCM							
	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale if Item Deleted	Variance Deleted	Corrected Item- Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
B1 (The extent of WCM)	7.37		7.464		0.795	0.680	0.794
B2 (Inventory)	7.52		7.539		0.723	0.851	0.807
B2 (Receivables)	7.04		6.527		0.488	0.555	0.909
B2 (Payables)	7.49		7.511		0.665	0.841	0.819
B2 (all the above)	7.31		7.131		0.850	0.751	0.777
Reliability Statistics: Requirements of WCM							
N of Items	Mean		Variance		Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	
5	9.18		10.895		3.301	0.850	
Item-Total Statistics: Usefulness of WCM							
Question B3	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale if Item Deleted	Variance Deleted	Corrected Item- Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
B3 (Use 1)	7.10		8.976		0.857	0.737	0.887
B3 (Use 2)	7.27		8.799		0.806	0.726	0.903
B3 (Use3)	7.00		8.571		0.768	0.647	0.919
B3 (Use 4)	7.15		9.133		0.864	0.761	0.886
Reliability Statistics: Usefulness of WCM							
N of Items	Mean		Variance		Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	
4	9.51		15.368		3.920	0.922	
Item-Total Statistics (Internal factors of WCM)							
	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale if Item Deleted	Variance Deleted	Corrected Item- Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
B4 (Management competency)	6.19		4.919		0.538	0.408	0.722
B4 (Size)	5.90		3.582		0.571	0.376	0.686
B4 (Leverage)	5.61		3.368		0.533	0.390	0.727
B4 (Profitability)	6.00		4.197		0.672	0.497	0.646
Reliability Statistics of the internal factors of WCM							
N of Items	Mean		Variance		Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	
4	7.90		6.596		2.568	0.752	
Item-Total Statistics (Management competencies)							

	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
B5 (Knowledge and skills)	5.40		3.483	0.542	0.361	0.680
B5 (Prior experience)	5.21		3.491	0.513	0.296	0.695
B5 (Educational qualifications)	5.31		3.933	0.472	0.240	0.719
B5 (Sharing knowledge)	5.13		2.618	0.645	0.452	0.618

Reliability Statistics (Management Competencies)

N of Items	Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
4	7.01	5.535	2.353	0.742

Item-Total Statistics: The size of business

	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Does your business depend on owner financing?	18.94		27.715	0.243	0.284	0.849
Does your restaurant keep high inventory level?	19.65		23.835	0.648	0.751	0.790
Does your business review and control inventory or stock level?	19.54		23.801	0.627	0.729	0.793
Does your business use computers in managing receivables?	20.13		22.702	0.606	0.645	0.796
Does your business extend account receivables period?	20.21		21.970	0.716	0.666	0.776
Do you maintain good relationship with suppliers by paying in due date?	19.29		22.914	0.580	0.498	0.801
Does you rely on suppliers' credit for managing AR and INV?	19.82		24.235	0.590	0.456	0.799

Reliability Statistics: The size of business

N of Items	Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
7	22.93	31.587	5.620	0.713

Item-Total Statistics: Leverage

	Scale if Deleted	Mean Item	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Does your restaurant depend on debt financing from banks?	9.44		11.249	0.728	0.704	0.861
Do you prefer debt finance as the debt financing is tax deductible?	9.15		11.019	0.700	0.555	0.869
Does the high level of debt cause inventory holding period to decrease?	9.37		9.807	0.745	0.698	0.854

Do you reduce debt level by shortening AR periods?	9.61	9.242	0.837	0.800	0.815
Reliability Statistics: Leverage					
N of Items	Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	
4	12.52	17.682	4.205	0.884	
Item-Total Statistics: Profitability					
	Scale Mean if Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Do you think INV days is important for the profitability of business?	7.65	4.483	0.266	0.345	0.628
Do you think collecting AR from your customers, increase profitability?	7.38	3.618	0.520	0.453	0.453
Do you pay your suppliers on time to take the benefits of discounts?	7.69	4.215	0.451	0.421	0.521
Do you think late payments to suppliers are profitable?	6.74	3.014	0.406	0.374	0.563
Reliability Statistics: Profitability					
N of Items	Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	
4	9.82	6.037	2.457	0.614	

Item total

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.786	.814	33

Validity test:

Correlation between the internal factors effecting the management of working capital and the requirements of WCM:

Correlations

		Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?	Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?
Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?	Pearson Correlation	1	.314**	.428**	.358**	.400**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007	.000	.002	.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Pearson Correlation	.314**	1	.540**	.253*	.534**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007		.000	.032	.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Pearson Correlation	.428**	.540**	1	.425**	.462**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants?	Pearson Correlation	.358**	.253*	.425**	1	.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.032	.000		.000
	N	72	72	72	72	72
Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants?	Pearson Correlation	.400**	.534**	.462**	.589**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

N	72	72	72	72	72
---	----	----	----	----	----

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Test of Normality:

Tests of Normality

Does the management competency influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants? Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
			Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Strongly agree			0.388	25	0.000	0.625	25	0.000
	Agree		0.348	43	0.000	0.691	43	0.000
	Neither agree nor disagree		0.151	4		0.993	4	0.972

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants? Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
			Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Strongly agree			0.369	14	0.000	0.639	14	0.000
	Agree		0.344	34	0.000	0.711	34	0.000
	Neither agree nor disagree		0.463	20	0.000	0.585	20	0.000
Do not know			0.385	3		0.750	3	0.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

b. Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital? is constant when Does leverage effect the WCM in your restaurants? = Disagree. It has been omitted.

Does profitability influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants? Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
			Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Strongly agree			0.372	21	0.000	0.633	21	0.000
	Agree		0.392	37	0.000	0.683	37	0.000
	Neither agree nor disagree		0.390	14	0.000	0.741	14	0.001

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Does the size of business influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants? Please indicate to what extent does your agree			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
			Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Strongly agree			0.387	20	0.000	0.626	20	0.000

restaurant manage Working Capital?	Agree	0.376	39	0.000	0.692	39	0.000
	Neither agree nor disagree	0.422	10	0.000	0.628	10	0.000
	Do not know	0.260	2				

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?	0.319	72	0.000	0.713	72	0.000
WC_Components	0.267	72	0.000	0.789	72	0.000
Internal_Factors_Compencies_Size_Leverage_Profitability	0.205	72	0.000	0.914	72	0.000
Management_Compencies_Skills_Education_experience	0.150	72	0.000	0.902	72	0.000
Size_Stock_Computer_Suppliers	0.123	72	0.009	0.959	72	0.019
Leverage_Loan_INVAR_AP_period	0.280	72	0.000	0.780	72	0.000
Profitability_INV_Customers_Late_payment	0.230	72	0.000	0.909	72	0.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistic	Skewness	Kurtosis
Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage Working Capital?	1.08088859917761 (Std. Error 0.283)	2.65754800568443 (Std. Error 0.559)
WC_Components	1.2099740643473 (Std. Error 0.283)	3.63400174507662 (Std. Error 0.559)

Internal_Factors_Competerencies_Size_Leverage_Profit ability	0.572968880488147 (Std. Error 0.283)	1.34558193963061 (Std. Error 0.559)
Management_Competerencies_Skills_Education_expeience	0.283 (Std. Error 0.283)	-0.570 (Std. Error 0.559)
Size_Stock_Computer_Suppliers	-0.605 (Std. Error 0.283)	0.292 (Std. Error 0.559)
Leverage_Loan_INVAR_AP_period	1.562 (Std. Error 0.283)	2.072 (Std. Error 0.559)
Profitability_INV_Customers_Late_payment	-0.890 (Std. Error 0.283)	0.429 (Std. Error 0.559)

Appendix E

Total size of population

Expected response	Actual response
150	72 (72% response rate)

Number of respondents by ethnic origin

Number of small restaurants	Ethnic origin
55	Bangladeshi
5	Indian
5	Pakistani
3	Turkish
2	Chinese
2	British

Number of restaurants by region

Number of small restaurants	England and North Wales
51	London
15	Wrexham
2	Oswestry
4	Bala, Gwynedd

Number of restaurants by diversity

Number of restaurants	Types of restaurants
50	Family style
10	Coffee house
3	Bistro
7	Buffet
2	Fine dining

Thematic analysis: Themes and Nodes (Codes) as implemented in NVivo 12

External factors	0	0
Competition	1	5
Inflation	1	60
Other	1	13
Tax	1	12
Internal factors	0	0
Human resources	0	0
Employee compete	1	5
Number of staffs	1	50
Salary	1	22

Appendix F

Questionnaires **Working capital management (WCM) practices**

Dear entrepreneur/ manager

I am a Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting a research on “the internal factors effecting working capital management of small food restaurants in the UK”.

I would be indebted to you and your company if you could take part in this study by answering the questions in the attached questionnaires. All information collected will be kept confidential and will be used only for research purposes. I truly appreciate your time and thank you for any information you can provide.

Warm regards

Fatema Tahura Ponny

University of the West of Scotland

London

Section A

Please mark (✓) to answer questions.

A1. What is the type of business enterprise?

Sole proprietorship Partnership Limited liability company Other _____

A2. Highest qualification of respondents

GCSE A level/ College Bachelor Degree Master degree Doctoral

A3. Number of employees in your restaurants

0-9 10-19 20-29 30-49

A4. What is your current job in the restaurant? _____

A5. Please specify number of years of experience in your current position. _____

Section B

B1. Please indicate to what extent does your restaurant manage working capital. (Response variable)

To a high extent To some extent Not at all Do not know

B2. Which of the following three components of working capital management do you give priority?

Components of WCM	High priority	Moderate Priority	Do not know	Low priority	Not a priority
Inventory					
Account receivables					
Account payables					
Other					
All the above					

B3. what is the main purpose of managing WC components?

To what extent do you agree or disagree to the following usefulness of WCM

Usefulness of WCM	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
Does your businesses invest in working capital to avoid the risk of financial shortage?						
Do you agree that effective management of stock level reduces the maintenance cost?						
Does WCM help your business to meet financial obligations such as debt financing?						
Does the performance of your business increase by maintaining optimal level of working capital?						
Other usefulness						

B4. Internal factors (Explanatory variables)

What internal factors influence the WCM in your restaurants?

Factors influence the choice of the WCM in your restaurants	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
Management competencies						
The size of business						
Leverage						
Profitability						
Other.....						

B5. Please indicate the extent to which the management competencies effect the working capital management in your restaurants

Management competencies (Education, Experience, and skills)	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
Do you require accounting knowledge and technical skills for the effective management of WC?						
Do you manage working capital through practical knowledge and prior experience?						
Do you think educational qualifications contributes to the effective management of WC?						
Do you agree that sharing knowledge and team-working are useful to manage working capital?						
Other						

B6. Please indicate the extent to which the size of your business effects the working capital management.

Difficulties that small business encounters in the management of WC and its components	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Does your business depend on owner financing?					
Does your restaurant keep high inventory level?					
Does your business review and control inventory or stock level?					
Does your business use computers in managing receivables from customers?					
Does your business extend account receivables period to encourage customers to spend more?					
Do you maintain good relationship with suppliers by paying in due date?					

Does your restaurant rely significantly on suppliers' credit for managing account receivables and inventories?					
Other					

B7. Please indicate the extent to which the leverage or debt ratio effect the working capital management in your restaurants

The effect of Leverage or debt ratio on the WCM	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
Does your restaurant depend on debt financing e.g. loan from banks?						
Do you prefer debt finance as the interest payable on debt financing is tax deductible?						
Does the high level of debt cause inventory holding period to decrease?						
Do you reduce debt level by shortening account collection periods?						
Do you seek to expand payables period and credit terms with suppliers because of high level of debt?						

B8. To what extent do you agree or disagree to the effects of profitability on the WCM in your restaurants?

The effect of profitability on the WCM	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know
Do you think inventory holding period is important for the profitability of your business?						
Do you prefer to decrease the level of inventory to enhance the profitability?						
Do you think collecting payment from your customers early, increase profitability?						
Do you pay your suppliers or creditors on time to take the benefits of discounts?						
Do you think late payments to suppliers are profitable?						

B9. Who is responsible for the overall WCM of your business?

Section C

Open ended questions

(How the internal factors influence the components of WCM in the small restaurant in the UK?)

C1. Indicate the internal factor(s) (if any) that you encounter in managing working capital other than the factors mentioned above.

C2 How do any of the factor identified in QC1 effect the inventory in restaurant?

C3. How do any of the factor identified in QC1 effect the receivables in restaurant?

C4. : How do any of the factor identified in QC1 effect the payables in restaurant?

Key concepts

Working Capital Management

WCM is the process of controlling the interrelationship between current assets and current liabilities to maintain the liquidity of the business.

The components of Working Capital Management (WCM)

Different elements of current assets and current liabilities such as inventory, account payables and account receivables etc. establish the structure of WCM. These elements are the main components of WCM.

Inventories include raw materials, work-in progress, finished or unfinished goods etc.

Receivables: Businesses usually sell their products on credit and allow customers a specified time to pay their invoices.

Account payables: Account payable is important as paying suppliers on time enables small business to minimize the risk of late payment.

Cash conversion cycle (CCC): CCC is the amount of time or a cycle a business takes in which it purchases inventory or raw materials, sells finished goods on credit, and then receives the amount due from the sale of the goods.

Leverage: Leverage is the relation between the debt ratio and the total assets of a firm. Debt ratio or leverage of a business is an important factor affecting WC requirement. Small business owners prefer debt finance as the interest payable on debt financing is deducted from the amount of tax payables.

Participant Consent Form

Title of research study: An investigation into the internal factors affecting the requirements of working capital management (WCM) and its components: a case study of UK small food restaurants

The research is described in the attached information sheet. Please read information sheet before giving your consent. If you agree to participate in this study, please answer the following questions by ticking the response that applies.

- | | YES | NO |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| • I have received a copy of the information sheet for this study and have read the details of the study. I understand that I cannot be identified. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| • I agree to participate in the research under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the Information Sheet. I understand that my words may be recorded and may be quoted in publications, reports, and other research outputs. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| • I voluntarily agree to participate in the research. I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Participant's Signature: _____ **Date:** _____

Participant's Name (Printed): _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

Researcher's contact details: _____

Please keep your copy of the consent form and the information sheet together

Participant's Information Sheet

Title of the study: The determinants of factors affecting the requirements of working capital management (WCM) and its components: a case study of UK small food restaurants.

Research investigator: Fatema Taura Ponny **Email:** [REDACTED]

Address and Contact details: University of the West of Scotland, 235 Southwark Bridge Rd, London SE1 6NP

You are invited to take part in a research study on working capital management of small food restaurant in the UK. Please read the following information carefully before deciding whether you will participate in the research. I am attaching a consent form for you to sign. Take your time and sign the Consent form before participation.

About the study

Management of working capital is important to small businesses. However, the detail study on the internal factors that specifically focuses and influences the level of WCM in the UK small food restaurants is still lacking. Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate the internal factors of WCM practices in small restaurant businesses in the UK.

What is involved in the study?

Questionnaires will be distributed physically to the owners or managers of small food restaurants in the UK. The researcher Fatema Tahura Ponny is responsible for the data collected in this study. Questionnaires consists of some open-ended and closed ended questions. Closed ended questions are contained of identifying the internal factors that influence WCM of your business. Open-ended questions will allow you to include more information and opinions. Each participant will require to spend no more than 40 minutes.

Is participation obligatory?

Participation in the research is voluntary. Participants can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason for their withdrawal. If participant does not carry on with the study, all the information collected to date, will be destroyed, and removed.

What are the anticipated benefits of taking part?

An anticipated outcome of the research will help small business to identify different internal factors that are affecting practices of working capital management. The results of this study if accepted by educational assessment board, people can find out about the results. If participant wants a copy of any reports resulting from the study, should ask researcher to put on list.

What are the potential risks of taking part?

There is no known risk associated with the research. No vulnerable participant will be involved. Participants have no risk of compulsion or undue influence to take part in the research. After voluntary

participation, they can withdraw from the study. Participants are free to decline to provide any personal information in the study without consequences or loss of benefit to their future treatment by the researcher.

Will taking part be kept confidential?

Appropriate safeguard will be followed by researcher to protect the confidentiality of data. Data will be collected anonymously to ensure the confidentiality of the participant. Identifiable data will be not be shared with any other organisation other than researcher, educational supervisor, and education assessment board.

How will information be recorded, stored, and protected?

Researcher will anonymise any documents through the coding process, so that participants and their organisation cannot be identified. Research data will be securely destroyed once research is approved by the assessment board. The results of this study if accepted by educational assessment board, will be used for publication, conference presentation etc. Participant will not be identified in any report or publication.

Who is funding the research?

This study is a part of self-funding DBA (Doctor of business administration) programme. The main investigator is a self-funded DBA student of the University of the West of Scotland. Researcher will receive no payment for your participation.

Who has reviewed the project?

This research has been reviewed and approved by the Chair of the Ethics Review Committee of University of the West of Scotland. In addition, educational supervisor of researcher has reviewed this study to protect your interests.

What if there is a problem?

If you are not sure about any of the above information relating to the research, please ask researcher for further information. Any complaint and concern about the participation process will be addressed; please contact Fatema Tahura Ponny, principal investigator on [REDACTED] in the first instance. You may also contact investigator’s educational supervisor on [REDACTED]

If you decide to take part, you will receive a copy of the information sheet and a signed consent form to keep. Thank you for your willingness to participate in this study.